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PROMETEO

A **PRO**abilistic fra**ME**work for coas**T**al and harbor
d**E**fense in the c**O**ntext of climate change

D4.1

Report on updated conceptual/empirical
formulations describing failure mechanisms of
rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls
and of artificial beach nourishments

**WP4 - Response characterization - Failure mechanisms of coastal and
harbor defense solutions**

M4.1 - Assessment of existing and adapted defense solutions

M4.2 - Experimental and numerical datasets on failure mechanisms for the definition of
probabilistic reliability functions for ultimate and serviceability limit states

O3

Task 4.1 – Task 4.6

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List of symbols

Symbol	U.m.	Description
$A_{e,i}$	[m ²]	Eroded area of the i-th cross section
A_c	[m]	Crest freeboard of rubble mound structures
$APSD$	[m ⁴]	Areal power spectrum
a_E	[-]	Coefficient of the EurOtop (2008) formula for the prediction of q^*
a_q	[-]	Coefficient of the Stagnitti et al. (2023b) formula for the prediction of q^*
a_{q2}	[-]	Coefficient of the proposed simplified formula for the prediction of q^*
a_r	[-]	Coefficient of the Zanuttigh and van der Meer (2008) formula
a_V	[-]	Scale parameter of the Weibull distribution of the individual wave overtopping volumes
B	[m]	Base of the rectangular beach fill
B_b	[m]	Width of berm at the toe of the vertical breakwater
B_{eq}	[m]	Equivalent berm width
B_s	[m]	Width of tested section
$BIAS$		BIAS
BSS	[-]	Brier Skill Score
b_E	[-]	Coefficient of the EurOtop (2008) formula for the prediction of q^*
b_q	[-]	Coefficient of the Stagnitti et al. (2023b) formula for the prediction of q^*
b_{q2}	[-]	Coefficient of the proposed simplified formula for the prediction of q^*
b_r	[-]	Coefficient of the Zanuttigh and van der Meer (2008) formula
b_V	[-]	Shape parameter of the Weibull distribution of the individual wave overtopping volumes
c_F	[-]	Empirical parameter of the added mass coefficient
C_{Fi}	[-]	Reduction factors for determining the probability of impulsive loads on vertical breakwaters
c_{Po}	[-]	Coefficient of the Stagnitti et al. (2023b) formula for the prediction of P_o
c_q	[-]	Coefficient of the Stagnitti et al. (2023b) formula for the prediction of q^*
cor	[-]	Correlation coefficient
d	[m]	Submergence of mound berm at the toe of vertical breakwaters
d_{n50}	[mm]	Median nominal diameter of beach porous medium
D_B	[m]	Berm height
D_C	[m]	Depth of closure
D_{n50}	[m]	Median nominal diameter of armor units
$D_{n50,core}$	[m]	Core nominal median stone diameter
EV	[m ³]	Eroded Volumes
$F_{0.4\%}$	[N/m]	Force with exceedance frequency of 0.4%
F_{GODA}	[N/m]	Force determined with Goda's formula

$facua$	[-]	Calibration factor time averaged flows due to wave skewness and asymmetry
f_c	[-]	Experimental coefficient of van der Meer (1988) formula
f_i	[N/m]	Elementary impact forcing
f_{LC}	[N/m]	Wave load per unit of caisson length
$f_{LC-1/250}$	[N/m]	Wave load per unit of caisson length with 1/250 non-exceedance level
$f_{x,c}$	[1/m]	Spectral centroid frequency along x direction
$f_{y,c}$	[1/m]	Spectral centroid frequency along y direction
f_w	[-]	Short-wave friction coefficient
f^*	[-]	Non-dimensional load variable
G	[-]	Armor units gradation factor
G_c	[m]	Crest width of rubble mound structures
g	[m/s ²]	Gravity acceleration
$H_{2\%}$	[m]	Wave height exceeded by 2 percent of the waves in time domain
H_{bc}	[m]	Limiting wave height for wave breaking occurrence
H_{bro}	[m]	Limiting wave height for broken wave occurrence
H_{m0}	[m]	Significant (spectral) wave height in frequency domain, $H_{m0}=4(m_0)^{1/2}$
H_s	[m]	Incident significant wave height
$H_{s,d}$	[m]	Design significant wave height
$H_{s,0}$	[m]	Deep-water significant wave height
H_s^t	[m]	Target significant wave height
HD	[m]	Macro-roughness maximum wave height along y
HH	[-]	Symmetrically normalized root mean square error (Hanna and Heinold, 1985)
h	[m]	Water depth at the toe of the structure
h_b	[m]	Height of berm at the toe of the vertical breakwater
h_r	[-]	Relative water depth, $h_r=H_{m0,o}/h$
h_s	[m]	Water depth in front of the vertical breakwater
k	[m ² /s ²]	Turbulent energy
k_r	[1/m]	Reflection coefficient
k_b	[-]	Correction factor that accounts for mound berm
k_t	[-]	Transmission coefficient
k_1, k_2	[-]	Transport coefficients
L	[m]	Stretch coast's length
L_0	[m]	Deep-water wavelength
L_c	[m]	Caisson length
LT	[-]	Length to thickness ratio
m_0	[m ²]	Zero th moment of the frequency spectrum
m^{IG}_0	[m ²]	Infragravity (IG) zero th moment of the frequency spectrum
m^{TOT}_0	[m ²]	Total zero th moment of the frequency spectrum
M	[-]	Reduction percentage of the initial beach fill volume
N_w	[-]	Number of incident waves
N_o	[-]	Number of wave overtopping events
N_{od}	[-]	Damage parameter of Hedar (1960)

N_L	[-]	Geometric scale weight of prototype and model unit
N_{wa}	[-]	Stability number (Hudson et al., 1979)
$N_{\gamma a}$	[-]	Ratio between the specific weight of prototype and model unit
$N_{\gamma a/\gamma w-1}$	[-]	Ratio between the buoyant density of prototype and model unit
NBI	[-]	Normalized bias
n	[-]	Porosity of the rubble-mound layers
n_{cs}	[-]	Number of cross-sections
P_o	[-]	Probability of wave overtopping
P_i	[-]	Percentage of impacting waves
p_i	[Pa]	Pressure field
\bar{p}_i	[Pa]	Mean component of the pressure field
p'_i	[Pa]	Turbulent component of the pressure field
Q	[m ³ /s]	Longshore sediment transport rate
Q^*	[-]	Non dimensional mean overtopping discharge per meter (1)
q	[m ³ /s m]	Mean overtopping discharge per meter
q^*	[-]	Non dimensional mean overtopping discharge per meter (2)
q^*_1	[-]	Non dimensional mean overtopping discharge per meter (3)
r	[-]	Ratio between force with exceedance frequency of 0.4% and force determined with Goda's formula
R^2	[-]	Coefficient of determination
Re_A	[-]	Reynolds number at the armour layer
Re_p	[-]	Reynolds number inside the structure core
R_c	[m]	Structure freeboard
$R_{u,2\%}$	[m]	Wave run-up level corresponding to the 2%-value of the hypothesized Rayleigh distribution
$RMSE$		Root mean square error
RR_q	[-]	Overtopping reduction ratio
$S_{d,c}$	[-]	Calculated damage parameter of Broderick and Ahrens (1982)
$S_{d,m}$	[-]	Measured damage parameter of Broderick and Ahrens (1982)
$s_{m,0}$	[-]	Deep water steepness
$\tan(\alpha)$	[-]	Foreshore slope
t_M	[y]	Reduction time related to a given percentage M of the initial beach fill volume
t_M^*	[-]	Non-dimensional reduction time
T_m	[s]	Mean wave period
$T_{m-1,0}$	[s]	Spectral wave period
T_p	[s]	Peak wave period
T_p^t	[s]	Target peak wave period
u_i	[m/s]	Velocity field
\bar{u}_i	[m/s]	Mean component of the velocity field
u'_i	[m/s]	Turbulent component of the velocity field
V_i	[m ³ /m]	Generic individual wave overtopping volume
V_{max}	[m ³ /m]	Maximum individual wave overtopping volume
X_g	[m]	Nourishment barycentre
α	[°]	Structure seaward slope angle

α_0	[°]	Offshore wave angle attack
α_b	[°]	Breaking wave angle attack
α_F	[-]	Empirical coefficient associated with the linear porous drag force
β	[°]	Wave direction of long crested waves
β_0	[°]	Mean wave direction of short crested waves
β_F	[-]	Empirical coefficient associated with the nonlinear porous drag force
γ_f	[-]	Friction factor of the armored slope
γ	[-]	Spectrum enhancement factor
γ_b	[-]	Breaking coefficient
η	[m]	Water free surface elevation
Δ	[-]	Relative buoyant density of the armor units
Δh	[m]	Increase of mean sea level
Δq_{SLR}	[%]	Increase of q due to SLR
Δq_{E-}	[%]	Decrease of q due to the upgrade of the structure
Δx	[m]	x-dimension of cells of the numerical grid
Δy	[m]	y-dimension of cells of the numerical grid
Δz	[m]	Height difference between 3D models of the armor layer
ε	[m ² /s ³]	Turbulent dissipation
ε^*	[m ² /γ]	Shoreline diffusivity
λ_M	[m]	Micro-roughness spectral wavelength
$\xi_{m-1,0}$	[-]	Iribarren number associated to the spectral wave period
Π_0	[-]	Nonlinearity parameter
ρ	[kg/m ³]	Density of the generic fluid
ρ_w	[kg/m ³]	Density of water
ρ_{qs}	[kg/m ³]	Density of employed quarry stones
ρ_s	[kg/m ³]	Density of artificial blocks
σ		Standard deviation
σ_{fc}	[-]	Standard deviation of f_c
$\bar{\tau}_{ij}$	[N/m ²]	Mean viscous stress tensor
$\zeta_{1/4}$	[m]	Average of the highest one-fourth water levels

1. Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty to describe their response to wave loads as well as to include the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans.

Uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. To this scope, the critical review of existing design regulations, the collection of state-of-art design formulas, and the study of possible adaptation solutions of aging structures are carried out, with reference to four types of coastal and harbor defense solutions, namely rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

The present document briefly provides an overview of methodologies for the characterization of existing and adapted solutions and the comparison between failure mechanisms typical of rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments. Moreover, a collection of experimental and numerical datasets for these kinds of coastal and harbor defense structures is presented, which derive from both existing and new experimental and numerical campaigns. These data were fundamental for the development of the activities described in deliverable D2.1.

1.2 Phases of the work

The present document is organized in the following two parts:

1. Chapter 2 focuses on the adaptive sea defense solutions, which aim at enhancing the protective role of existing structures, and thus describes any potential failure mechanism;

2. Chapter 3 reports various numerical and experimental analysis that examine some of the failure mechanism described in Chapter 2.

The above-mentioned chapters are made up by a specific section for each type of coastal and harbor defense considered here, namely rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

Finally, Chapter 4 provides a summary of the performed analyses and draws the conclusion of the presented work.

2. Assessment of existing and adapted defense solutions

2.1 Overview

Coastal engineers are facing new challenges in designing sea defenses to mitigate coastal risks, particularly in view of expected sea level rises. Particularly, adaptive solutions that increase the protective capability of classic defense structures are increasingly engaging coastal scientific and engineering communities. In the following, we will briefly describe several possible adaptive solutions for different coastal defense structures.

2.2 Characterization of existing and adapted solutions

Generally, there are different types of adaptive solutions, which can be distinguished according to their effect. Solutions that consist of modifying the structure shape (such as designing a recurved wall) act by increasing the dissipation on the structure; on the other hand, some solutions attempt to act by dissipating energy before waves reach the structure (e.g., introducing a beach nourishment or a rubble mound breakwater in front of the existing structure). However, the identification of possible adaptation options cannot be separated from an assessment of the current condition of the existing defense solution. Nonetheless, at present, there is not a consolidated methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions, nor for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options.

As regards rubble-mound breakwaters, the choice of the most suitable upgrading must be addressed considering several factors (Croeneveld et al., 1985; Burcharth et al., 2014; Foti et al., 2020). First, a field survey is required to assess the magnitude of the damage and identify its possible causes, in order to avoid the failure of the restored breakwater for the same reasons. Traditional monitoring of the emerged part of rubble-mound breakwaters based on visual inspections and topographic techniques have some weaknesses, mainly linked to physical restrictions, long time, and high costs for the accurate measurement of highly irregular armor layer surfaces. In addition, the sparse data coverage of in situ topographic surveys can lead to significant interpolation errors, and hence to low-resolution reconstructions of the armor layer surface. The limitations of traditional monitoring techniques can be overcome by using UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) and ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles) for the acquisition of both subaerial and underwater data as a mapping and measurement tools. These technologies allow to acquire high-resolution data set useful for the 3D reconstruction of the breakwater and the identification of specific cross-sections requiring maintenance as well as armor volumes analyses to allow for a targeted repair that minimizes expenditure (Drummond et al., 2015; González-Jorge et al., 2016; Henriques et al., 2017).

Once the deterioration level of the existing structure has been assessed and its possible causes identified, the required structure performances and acceptable risk of failure must be fixed, on the basis of the structure function (e.g. coastal or harbor defense) and economic relevance. Furthermore, the geometric characteristics of the breakwater and the local topography must be considered, together with specific environmental restrictions which could influence the design. Information about these aspects could be deduced from new monitoring data, which, if possible,

should be combined with the original project documentation, including bathymetric data, geotechnical analyses, granulometric analyses, and detailed construction schemes of the structure cross-sections. Finally, the available materials, equipment and financial resources play a fundamental role for the evaluation of the economic and technical feasibility of different upgrading options.

On the basis of the above-mentioned factors, four main repair methods are usually contemplated for the upgrade of damaged rubble-mound breakwaters (Croeneveld et al., 1985): i) addition of units of the same type of the existing ones, eventually reinforced or slightly greater to increase their weight; ii) replacement of the entire armor layer, removing all the original units; iii) reconstruction of the rubble-mound structure, replacing not only the original armor layer, but also the underlayers; iv) provision of a submerged toe berm or detached breakwater to reduce the wave impact on the existing structure. If the adaptation of existing rubble mound breakwaters to the effects of climate change is considered, the above-mentioned upgrading strategies can be applied with some tricks to face the increased external forcing. For instance, the overtopping rates can be reduced by heightening the existing wave wall or by the construction of a new one. Furthermore, besides the addition of a submerged toe berm or detached breakwater, if the construction of an extra or totally new armor layer is considered, the rise of the structure crest level to reduce the overtopping discharges or the reduction of the seaside slope to limit wave runup and increase the armor layer stability can be designed (Burcharth et al., 2014; Foti et al., 2020).

The selection of the blocks for the armor layer restoration is a difficult issue, because there is a lack of in-depth investigations on the interaction between the existing units and the additional ones. In this regard, Carver (1989) provided an inventory of existing US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) projects that have used dissimilar armor blocks for repair and rehabilitation of rubble mound coastal breakwaters. The results of the survey showed that in 1989 only the 24% of the considered districts had experienced the use armor units different from the existing ones for the armor layer restoration, thus highlighting the necessity to perform further systematic experimental studies for the evaluation of the interfacing and stability response of different armor blocks. Currently, the only guidance for the choice of shape and size of the additional armor units comes from traditional formulations for new constructions, prototype experience, engineering judgment, inferences from model tests of similar structures, or site-specific model tests. The use of additional armor units heavier than the existing ones could be considered if the present structure appears undersized with respect to the design wave action, in the absence of technical or practical limitations (Croeneveld et al., 1985). Instead, to the best of the author's knowledge, the use of additional armor units smaller (i.e. lighter) than the existing ones, which could be contemplated to fill the voids of the damaged breakwater with limited movements of the present blocks, has not been investigated yet. Certainly, in this case the structural response of the whole armor layer to the design wave load must be evaluated by means of physical model tests. The same applies to the use of units with different interlocking level than the existing ones, for which special attention on the regularization of the laying surface and on the transition zones should be paid.

As regards the available numerical models, they have not been sufficiently calibrated to simulate all the common restoration concepts, particularly concerning the stability of the armor layer

(Burcharth et al., 2014; Lara et al., 2019). As a consequence, physical modeling represents the most reliable approach not only to describe the response of existing or upgraded rubble mound structures and their possible failure modes, but also to calibrate existing or new numerical models. Both physical and numerical modeling should be performed considering update climate scenarios, which must take into account the effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels.

The above-described methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing rubble-mound breakwaters and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options can be adapted for the case of vertical breakwaters. Also in this case, field activities to assess the magnitude of the damage and identify its possible causes can be performed through traditional monitoring of the emerged part of the structure and the use of UAVs and ROVs for the acquisition of high-resolution data useful for the 3D reconstruction of the breakwater. Then, the required structure performances and acceptable risk of failure can be set on the basis of the structure function and economic relevance. In this regard, it is worth to point out that this kind of breakwater is commonly employed for harbor defense. The availability of the original project documentation should be verified, as it may provide valuable information for the design of an optimal adaptation solution, together with the newly acquired field data and the results of cost-benefit analyses considering both technical and financial aspects.

In particular, three main categories of adaptation strategies can be identified: i) foundation stabilization through jet grouting, as well as cement or nanosilica injections into the subsoil; ii) structural enhancement, e.g. through the installation of a new crown wall or the raising of the existing one to reduce overtopping discharges, and the implementation of longitudinal reinforcements such as connecting spanners to improve structural integrity; iii) wave energy dissipation measures, e.g. armor layers or rock revetments or specially designed wave barriers. As in the case of rubble-mound breakwaters, the effectiveness of the possible adaptation solutions should be verified by performing both physical and numerical modeling, including test cases which considers effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels.

The assessment of the current state of existing seawalls and the selection of potential adaptation options can be carried out using an approach similar to that described for rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters. In this case, special attention should be paid to the evaluation of the conditions of the structure toe, which represent its most critical component, as it is frequently exposed to scour phenomena. The possible adaptation options should be selected based on the results of cost-benefit analyses which include design requirements, technical issues and economic aspects. In particular, overtopping can be reduced by constructing rubble-mound dampers, either as toe structures or detached low-crested/submerged breakwaters (LCB), which dissipate part of the incoming wave energy before reaching the wall. It is worth to point out that the cross-sectional width of the dampers depends on the desired overtopping reduction. Also in this case, physical and numerical investigation could provide useful insights for the evaluation of the performances of different possible options under a changing climate.

For the implementation of new beach nourishments and adaptations of existing ones, the methodology described above for assessing the current state of coastal and harbor defense structures must be complemented with two specific preliminary studies: a diachronic analysis of the coastline and a granulometric analysis of the sediments composing the existing beach.

The first analysis, together with the results of the met-ocean present and future climate study, is essential for assessing the beach's tendencies over time, whereas the second enables the identification of appropriate sediments for nourishment. As for the rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters and the seawalls, the selection of the optimal adaptation solution should be based on the results of a cost-benefit analysis which considers design requirements, technical issues and economic aspects. Possible adaptation solutions of existing beach nourishments include periodic beach nourishment (eventually based on regular monitoring the beach profile, sediment transport, and shoreline changes), submerged breakwaters to prevent the loss of nourishment sediments due to wave action, dune restoration and stabilization to provide additional protection against erosion and storm damage, the use of advanced engineering techniques to enhance the effectiveness and longevity of beach nourishment projects (e.g. Beach Drainage Systems, geotextile tubes or offshore sediment sources), sand bypass systems to restore natural sediment flow disrupted by coastal structures, creation or restoration of coastal wetlands. The efficacy of the above-mentioned solutions should be assessed through physical and numerical modeling, including test conditions representative of future climate scenarios. In addition to hard and soft structural adaptation options, shoreline setback policies to accommodate future erosion as well as nature-based solutions that enhance coastal resilience in the face of climate-related impacts should be considered.

2.3 Comparative analysis of failure mechanisms

This Section illustrates the various failure mechanism that might affect the maritime and coastal defense solutions. Specifically, we briefly discuss the potential failures for each sea defense.

2.3.1 Rubble-mound breakwaters

Rubble-mound breakwaters are among the most widely adopted coastal defense solutions for the protection of harbors and coastlines. They are typically composed of an armor layer, one or more underlayers or filter layers, a core of smaller stones, a toe berm, and a foundation resting on the seabed. Their hydraulic performance relies on a combination of wave energy dissipation, structural permeability, and geometrical stability.

Unlike rigid structures, rubble-mound breakwaters are designed to tolerate a certain level of damage without losing their primary protective function. As a consequence, failure is rarely sudden or binary, but rather occurs through progressive damage mechanisms that develop over time under repeated wave loading. This characteristic makes the identification and classification of failure mechanisms a key aspect for both design and risk-based assessment. Based on established guidelines and experimental evidence (e.g., CEM, Part VI), the main failure mechanisms of rubble-mound breakwaters can be classified as follows (Figure 2. 1).

- **Armor layer hydraulic instability:** This is the most common and well-documented failure mechanism. It consists of the displacement, or extraction of individual armor units due to wave-induced hydrodynamic forces. Damage typically initiates locally and progressively propagates along the slope, leading to partial reshaping of the structure. Design approaches usually distinguish between initiation of damage (limited displacement) and failure (extensive armor loss with exposure of the underlayer or core), a distinction that underpins damage-based design methods.

- **Armor unit structural instability:** In addition to hydraulic instability, concrete armor units may experience structural failure, such as breakage, cracking, or loss of interlocking. These mechanisms are often associated with repeated impacts, rocking and rolling motions, and stress concentrations, and may significantly reduce armor effectiveness even in the absence of large-scale displacement.
- **Toe instability and scour:** The toe berm provides essential support to the armor slope. Toe instability may result from local scour, undermining, or stone displacement induced by wave breaking, reflected currents, and near-bed flow acceleration. Failure at the toe can act as a trigger mechanism, leading to progressive instability of the entire armor layer.
- **Filter instability and internal erosion:** Damage or malfunction of filter layers may allow fine material from the core to be washed out, initiating internal erosion. Progressive loss of filter efficiency increases permeability and weakens the structural integrity of the breakwater, especially under long-duration storm loading.
- **Core exposure and settlement:** Progressive loss of armor and filter units may expose the core, leading to internal rearrangement, settlement, and increased deformation. Core exposure enhances internal flow and pore pressure gradients, accelerating damage progression.
- **Crest lowering and profile reshaping:** Repeated wave attack can cause crest settlement and flattening of the seaward slope. Although not always associated with immediate failure, crest lowering significantly increases wave overtopping and reduces the functional performance of the structure.
- **Overtopping-induced damage and rear-slope erosion:** Excessive wave overtopping may induce erosion of the rear slope, displacement of crest elements, and damage to superstructures such as crown walls, including sliding, tilting, or breakage.
- **Foundation and global instability:** Less frequently, rubble-mound breakwaters may experience global instability mechanisms, including slip failure, bearing capacity failure, or large-scale sliding, particularly in the presence of weak subsoil conditions, excessive pore pressures, or extreme hydrodynamic loading.

Overall, these mechanisms are strongly interrelated and may occur sequentially or simultaneously, highlighting the need for an integrated and mechanistic interpretation of breakwater stability.

Figure 2. 1 Failure modes of rubble-mound breakwaters. Adapted from Burcharth and Liu (1995).

The activation and evolution of failure mechanisms in rubble-mound breakwaters are controlled by several hydrodynamic processes:

- Wave breaking and impact type, ranging from non-breaking to plunging and surging waves;
- Wave steepness and spectral characteristics, influencing armor stability and pressure fluctuations;
- Water depth and foreshore slope, which govern wave transformation processes such as shoaling and breaking;
- Long-wave and infragravity motions, particularly relevant in shallow and very shallow water, where they may enhance internal flow and pore pressure variations.

In shallow water conditions, the combined effects of wave breaking over the foreshore, nonlinear wave transformation, and long-period motions can substantially modify the hydraulic loading at the toe of rubble-mound breakwaters. These processes may activate failure mechanisms that are not adequately captured by design formulations derived under deep-water assumptions, particularly when waves break offshore of the structure and energy is redistributed towards lower frequencies.

Traditional design methods for rubble-mound breakwaters are largely based on deterministic or semi-probabilistic approaches, often calibrated using laboratory experiments conducted under idealised and stationary conditions. Although these methods provide practical tools for preliminary design, their reliability decreases significantly when applied outside their original calibration range, especially under shallow and very shallow water conditions and during nonstationary storm events. Damage-based design concepts represent a significant advancement, as they explicitly account for the progressive nature of armor degradation rather than relying on binary failure criteria. Nevertheless, existing damage formulations often exhibit considerable scatter and uncertainty, and their applicability under changing climatic conditions remains limited. Moreover, the complex interactions among different failure mechanisms such as armor instability, toe erosion, internal flow processes, and overtopping-induced damage are frequently treated in a simplified manner or neglected altogether.

The classification of failure mechanisms therefore highlights several key aspects for the planning of experimental and numerical investigations. Experimental tests should be designed to capture progressive damage evolution, rather than focusing solely on single failure thresholds. Shallow water conditions and long-wave effects should be explicitly considered, with particular emphasis on the role of infragravity (IG) waves, whose influence on armor stability and internal pressure response is still poorly quantified. Both physical experiments and CFD simulations should focus on resolving near-structure hydrodynamics, including wave breaking at the toe, flow infiltration into the porous medium, pore pressure development within the core, and wave–structure interaction at the armor unit scale. Coupling between hydrodynamics and structural response remains a major challenge and requires carefully selected modelling simplifications. This issue is particularly critical for concrete armor units, where complex failure mechanisms such as rocking, loss of interlocking, and rotation-induced instability remain largely unexplored, especially in shallow and very shallow water environments.

Overall, rubble-mound breakwaters represent a complex and highly coupled system, in which failure mechanisms are strongly interdependent. A comparative and mechanistic understanding of these processes is essential to support the development of advanced experimental programmes and high-fidelity numerical models within the PROMETEO framework. In this context, a key research priority is the acquisition of new experimental and numerical data, particularly under shallow and very shallow water conditions, where existing datasets remain scarce. Equally important is the systematic quantification of uncertainties associated with hydraulic loading, wave transformation processes, structural response, and damage evolution. These uncertainties must be explicitly characterised and incorporated into modelling frameworks. Such an approach is fundamental to enable the implementation of Level III probabilistic design methodologies, in which all relevant sources of uncertainty are propagated through the analysis, allowing for a fully risk-informed assessment of breakwater performance (Scaravaglione and Melby, 2026). Future research efforts should therefore move decisively towards this direction, combining targeted experimental campaigns, advanced CFD modelling, and probabilistic reliability analysis, in order to overcome the limitations of traditional deterministic design and to support more robust, resilient, and climate-adaptive coastal defence solutions.

2.3.2 Vertical breakwaters

Vertical breakwaters are exposed to a range of failure mechanisms, which can differ in nature, origin, and triggering conditions. These failures can be classified according to their cause, such as design inadequacies, insufficient knowledge of environmental parameters (e.g., underestimated geotechnical characteristics or incomplete wave data), inappropriate construction methods, low-quality materials, or long-term deterioration due to insufficient maintenance.

From a structural perspective, failure mechanisms can be divided into global (overall) and local (localized) categories. Global failures affect the entire structure and include:

- Horizontal sliding: occurs when the resultant horizontal forces acting on the seaward face exceed the frictional resistance between the caisson base and the foundation soil.
- Overturning and foundation overloading: takes place when wave-induced moments surpass the stabilizing moments generated by the weight of the structure. This typically occurs without rupture of the foundation soil, particularly when the seabed or base reef has high mechanical strength.
- Settling or sinking: results from consolidation of the foundation soil under the weight of the caisson.
- Foundation soil slip: arises when the load transmitted by the base slab exceeds the soil's shear strength, often influenced by cyclic pore pressure variations due to waves, causing rotation and potential failure of the caisson.
- Rift slip rupture: occurs when the foundation reef fails under excessive loads from the caisson, potentially propagating into the underlying soil.

Local failures are generally initiated by wave action and affect portions of the structure or surrounding seabed. Key mechanisms include:

- Sea-side cliff erosion: can induce rotation and damage to the seaward portion of the caisson, with maximum stresses occurring in wave hollows in front of the wall.
- Seabed excavation: wave-induced scour may destabilize the caisson's seaward base, particularly under certain wave line conditions.
- Ejection of reef material: oscillatory motion of the caisson generates alternating water flows through the reef and subsoil voids.
- Displacement of cape boulders in front of composite breakwaters: increases wave loads on the caisson front, potentially causing slippage and enhanced overtopping.
- Breakage of the caisson wall: results from impulsive wave loads or ship impacts.
- Displacement and ejection of structural boulders: undermines the integrity of the vertical breakwater.
- Breakage of localized overburden or wall sections: due to wave overtopping onto the structure.

Comparative assessment and relative criticality: Global mechanisms, particularly horizontal sliding and foundation failure, are generally the most critical due to their potential to compromise the entire structure. Overturning, while significant, is usually less frequent, as the caisson's weight provides stabilizing resistance. Local failures, although often less catastrophic individually, can act as precursors to global failure by altering load distributions, eroding support, or amplifying wave pressures. Among local failures, seabed erosion and boulder displacement are particularly relevant because they directly influence the likelihood of subsequent global failures.

Triggering conditions and interactions: The probability of each failure type depends on environmental and structural conditions. Horizontal sliding is favored by low foundation friction relative to wave forces, whereas overturning occurs when stabilizing moments are insufficient. Local failures are primarily triggered by wave dynamics, including extreme wave hollows, overtopping, or oscillatory flows. Interactions between mechanisms are common and complex; for instance, erosion at the base of the structure can initiate rotation, which may then trigger horizontal sliding. Similarly, displacement of reef boulders increases wave stresses on the caisson, potentially leading to local wall breakage and further foundation instability.

Implications for design: Understanding the relative importance, likelihood, and interactions of failure mechanisms is crucial for effective design and probabilistic assessment of vertical breakwaters. Particular attention should be given to horizontal displacement and wave overtopping, which are the most relevant for determining structural safety under extreme conditions.

2.3.3 Seawalls

Seawalls are a pioneering coastal protection measure that is widely used to protect properties and facilities along the coast. They are designed to protect viaducts and coastal roads from overtopping and flooding, as well as defend coastal properties from overtopping, flooding, and

coastal erosion. Furthermore, the impact of seawalls on the coastal landscape and environment is not as severe as that of other structures (e.g., emerged detached breakwaters).

However, a proper design of the structure has to take any possible failure mechanism into account.

In the particular case of rigid seawall structures, the main failures modes can be detailed as (CEM, pt VI):

- undermining: it occurs when the sand or rubble toe level drops below the footing of the wall, causing the wall to subside and collapse into the hole.
- sliding, in which the wall moves away from the retained profile.
- overturning, in which the wall topples over slip circle failure, in which the entire embankment fails.
- loss of structural integrity, due to wave impact.
- erosion of the backfill, caused by wave overtopping, high watertable levels, or leaching through the seawall.
- outflanking and end scour.

Several failure modes described above are mainly due to beach erosion. The foundations are typically undermined during storm events, when the sand moves seaward to form a berm. This process could lead to failure of the seawall by exposing its toe to wave impact or by reducing foundation support. Within this context, wall's location is crucial. Indeed, seawalls located high up the beach interact occasionally with wave and sediment transport processes; on the other hand, structures placed in the active beach zone interact frequently with hydrodynamic and sediment transport processes. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the structure's presence limits the sediment budget, which in turn affects the seawall's stability during various sediment transport processes. Furthermore, rear erosion can occur due to either wave overtopping or poor drainage. Water accumulating behind the wall can lead to soil erosion, creating pockets or channels that undermine the wall's structural integrity.

Another responsible mechanism of seawall failures is wave overtopping phenomenon. Indeed, the impact of waves against the structure can damage it. Furthermore, the water discharged above the seawall crest jeopardizes seawall crest and promenade, along with people and infrastructure located directly behind the wall. Finally, as mentioned above, wave overtopping can also cause the soil to become saturated, increasing pore water pressure and the likelihood of failure due to sliding, overturning or the removal of retained soil.

Finally, the direct wave action on seawalls can severely determine structure's failure. Indeed, wave impacts on the offshore parapet of the wall can exert significant loadings that mines structural integrity. Moreover, wave reflection in front of the seawall is higher compared to other sea defense due to its geometrical shape. Thus, this phenomenon could easily determine scour erosion, which jeopardizes seawall's foundations.

Within this framework, adaptive solutions may mitigate the causes of the seawall's failure. Indeed, seawalls can be protected by other structures (e.g., rubble-mound breakwaters) that limit the negative effects of wave-seawall interactions and beach-erosion-related problems.

2.3.4 Beach nourishment

Artificial beach nourishments are widely adopted as soft coastal defense solutions to mitigate shoreline erosion and reduce wave impact on hinterland areas. Unlike hard structures, beach nourishments do not rely on structural resistance but on the morphodynamic response of sediment to wave and current forcing. Their effectiveness is therefore intrinsically time-dependent and strongly influenced by hydrodynamic and sedimentological conditions. Beach nourishments are designed to dissipate wave energy through breaking in the surf zone and to provide an increased dry beach width that acts as a buffer during storm events. Consequently, failure does not occur through structural collapse but through progressive sediment loss or redistribution, which may compromise the intended level of protection.

Failure mechanisms of beach nourishments can be classified according to the dominant sediment transport processes and morphological responses, and are reported herein:

- Cross-shore erosion: Storm-induced cross-shore sediment transport may lead to significant lowering of the beach profile, erosion of the berm, and offshore displacement of sediment. This mechanism is typically associated with energetic wave conditions and plunging breakers.
- Longshore sediment losses: In the presence of oblique wave incidence, nourished material may be transported out of the project area by longshore currents. This process can result in rapid reduction of the nourished volume if not properly accounted for in the design.
- Profile flattening and shoreline retreat: Repeated wave action can progressively flatten the beach profile, reducing beach slope and causing shoreline retreat. Although gradual, this mechanism directly affects the protective function of the nourishment.
- Loss of dry beach width: Even in the absence of significant sediment volume loss, redistribution of material may lead to a reduction of dry beach width, increasing vulnerability to overtopping, overwash, and flooding during storm events.
- Overwash and dune erosion (when present): In nourished beaches with dune systems, extreme water levels and wave run-up may cause overwash and dune erosion, accelerating sediment losses and compromising the long-term stability of the system.

These mechanisms often act simultaneously and are highly sensitive to wave climate variability, making their prediction inherently uncertain.

The response of beach nourishments is governed by a complex interplay of hydrodynamic and morphodynamic processes, including:

- Wave breaking and surf-zone dynamics, which control energy dissipation and sediment mobilisation;
- Storm duration and sequencing, as cumulative effects may dominate over single extreme events;
- Sediment characteristics, such as grain size, fall velocity, and sorting;
- Depth of closure, defining the offshore limit of significant sediment exchange;
- Water level variability, including tides, storm surge, and sea level rise.

In shallow water environments, nonlinear wave transformation and infragravity motions may enhance sediment transport and contribute to unexpected erosion patterns. These effects are often insufficiently captured by simplified design formulations.

Current design approaches for beach nourishments are largely based on deterministic concepts, such as equilibrium beach profiles, empirical closure depth formulations, and volumetric balance methods. While these approaches are widely used in practice, they are affected by significant uncertainties related to wave climate variability, sediment transport processes, and long-term morphological evolution. Probabilistic and risk-based approaches are still rarely applied to beach nourishment design, despite the inherently stochastic nature of the governing processes. Climate change effects, such as sea level rise and changes in storm characteristics, further amplify these uncertainties and challenge the reliability of traditional design methods. As a result, beach nourishment performance is often assessed in terms of expected lifetime and maintenance requirements rather than strict failure thresholds.

The classification of failure mechanisms for beach nourishments provides important guidance for the design of experimental and numerical investigations. Laboratory experiments should focus on sediment transport processes and beach profile evolution under controlled wave and water level conditions, allowing the identification of dominant erosion and accretion mechanisms during storm events. Particular attention should be devoted to scaling issues, which are critical in physical modelling, especially with respect to sediment mobility, fall velocity, and the correct reproduction of morphodynamic response. Numerical modelling plays a key complementary role. CFD and depth-averaged morphodynamic models should aim to accurately resolve nearshore hydrodynamics, wave breaking, and the coupling between hydrodynamic forcing and sediment transport processes. In this context, the use of process-based models such as XBeach, possibly coupled with spectral wave models or calibrated against laboratory data, is fundamental for investigating storm-induced erosion, overwash, and beach profile adjustment.

Long-term morphological evolution and cumulative storm impacts cannot be efficiently addressed through full-resolution CFD alone, which remains computationally prohibitive. Therefore, simplified, reduced-complexity, or hybrid modelling approaches, combining numerical simulations with experimental observations, are required to assess beach nourishment performance over engineering time scales. In addition, growing attention is being devoted to nature-based and eco-friendly solutions aimed at increasing the stability and resilience of beach nourishments. These include the use of vegetated dunes, bio-engineered reinforcements, submerged or low-crested structures, and hybrid solutions in which nourished beaches are combined with permeable or environmentally compatible hard structures. Such approaches can partially “stiffen” the nourishment system, reducing sediment losses while preserving its adaptive and reversible character. The investigation of these hybrid and green defence concepts requires an integrated experimental–numerical framework, as the interaction between soft sediments, ecological components, and protective structures introduces additional complexity. Coupled modelling approaches, supported by laboratory experiments, are therefore essential to study the combined action of beach nourishments and protective measures, such as nourished beaches sheltered by submerged breakwaters, reef-like structures, or other eco-engineered solutions.

Overall, beach nourishments represent highly dynamic systems, in which failure mechanisms are governed by gradual morphodynamic adjustment rather than abrupt collapse. A robust understanding of these processes, including the role of hybrid and nature-based interventions, is essential for designing effective experimental programmes and for developing predictive tools capable of supporting adaptive, sustainable, and risk-informed coastal management strategies within the PROMETEO framework.

3. Experimental and numerical datasets on failure mechanisms

3.1 Overview

The present Chapter describes experimental and numerical datasets collected to examine different failure mechanisms for each sea defense structure. Furthermore, the beneficial rules of the adaptive solutions have been investigated.

3.2 Failure mechanisms of rubble-mound breakwaters

3.2.1 Experimental dataset acquired by UniCT

This section presents the experimental dataset on existing and upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters acquired by UniCT. A portion of the data was previously published by Stagnitti et al. (2023a), whereas the remaining data were obtained within the framework of the PROMETEO Project.

Experimental setup

The experimental campaign has been carried out in Hydraulic Laboratory of the University of Catania. Tests were performed in a wave tank measuring 18 m in length, 1.20 m in height and 3.60 m in width; the final part of the tank houses a gravel beach profile about 2.00 m long was used as a working area (Stagnitti et al. 2023). For the new performed test, the width of the tank has been reduced to 1.00 m. Figure 3.1 shows the 3D sketch of the section of the wave tank. The initial and final walls are made up of reinforced concrete, whereas the two side walls are made up of transparent glass panels about 0.01 m thick, fixed on a metallic frame.

Figure 3.1 3D sketch of the section of the wave tank of the Hydraulic Laboratory of the University of Catania used for the experimental campaign on the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater, and location of the measuring instruments.

The waves have been generated by a flat-type wave maker placed on the initial part of the tank and the wave maker is activated by an electronically controlled oleo-dynamic system, whose components are slotted into an external control panel, as shown in Figure 3.2a. Such a panel allows the generation of sinusoidal, triangular and square waves of specified frequency and amplitude. In addition, the system provides the possibility be controlled by external inputs thanks to a coaxial cable (type RG-59) connected to a National Instruments I/O board and a laptop equipped with an on-purpose developed software for the generation of random waves using JONSWAP spectra, as shown in Figure 3.2b.

The wave motion characteristics have been measured by means of five resistance gauges, whose location in the wave tank is showed in Figure 3.1. Gauges n. 1, 2, 3 and 4 were properly spaced (see Table 3.1) to measure the incident and reflected wave motion following the four gauges method proposed by Faraci et al. (2015). In addition, gauge n. 5 was placed 5.0 m from the wave maker to further monitor the hydrodynamic conditions in the wave generation zone.

Each gauge consisted of two stainless steel wires 0.30 m long, placed in parallel at 0.012 m. A high frequency voltage passes through the wires, whose conductance changes proportionally to the immersion depth of the gauge. The changes in conductance due to the variation of free surface elevations corresponds to an analogical voltage output, which is controlled through a wave monitor, converted into a digital signal by an acquisition board (National Instruments NIUSB 6008) and then recorded and visualized through a laptop, thanks to a specially developed LabView code (see Figure 3.3). Such a code has allowed the synchronization between all the measurement instruments (i.e. resistance gauges, video cameras and acoustic gauge). The conversion of the resistance gauges output from voltage to free surface elevation in meters has been performed through static calibration. Since the voltage output linearly dependent on the free surface elevation, before each set of tests with constant water level the calibration has been performed by vertically raising and lowering the wave gauges at known distances. For each wave gauge the mean voltage outputs correspondent to three heights were recorded: -0.08 m, 0.00 m and +0.08 m, being the second one the properly fixed working position. Then, the conversion law from Volts to meters has been calculated through the least-squares linear regression method.

Figure 3.2 Control panel for the generation of regular waves (a); coaxial cable (type RG-59) and National Instruments I/O board used for the connection to common laptop equipped with a specially developed software for the generation of random waves by means of JONSWAP spectra (b).

Table 3.1 Distance from the toe of the model of the four resistance gauges placed for the application of the four-gauge method proposed by Faraci et al. (2015).

Gauge 1	Gauge 2	Gauge 3	Gauge 4
1.15 m	1.25 m	1.75 m	1.86 m

Figure 3.3 Interface of the LabView code specially developed for the synchronized acquisition of the output coming from the employed resistance gauges, video cameras and acoustic gauge.

For the experiments presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023a), the video camera R1 Sony FDR-AX53 (see Figure 3.4a) has been placed on a scaffolding at 2.40 m from the toe of the structure, as shown in Figure 3.1, so as to frontally frame the whole model. For the experiments conducted in the context of the PROMETEO, the video camera R1 is the Sony HDR-CX410VE (see Figure 3.4b).

An on purpose developed LabView code has allowed the synchronization between video camera R1 and all the other measurement instruments. In this way, records of the movements of the armor units during wave attack have been acquired. The calculation of the traditional damage parameter N_{od} could be performed by using the following equation (Hedar, 1960):

$$N_{od} = \frac{N_{moved}}{B_s D_{n50}} \quad (3.1)$$

where N_{moved} is the number of displaced units, B_s is the width of the tested section and D_{n50} is the median nominal diameter of the armor units. The cumulative N_{od} has been calculated at the end of each sea state.

The Structure from Motion (SfM) technique (Torres et al., 2012; Hofland et al., 2018; van Gent and van der Werf, 2014), used by Stagnitti et al. (2023a), has been used to recover the 3D point cloud of the structure at the beginning and at the end of the tests from a set of 2D images acquired from the dry model by a camera Sony Cyber-shot DSC-HX9V 16.2 MP G Lens (see Figure 3.4). Image overlapping was about 80%. The software Agisoft Metashape has been employed for the calculation of the point clouds. First, the alignment of each set of 2D images has been performed, setting high accuracy. Then, the resulting point clouds have been converted into dense point clouds, setting the parameter quality to high. The very dense 3D point clouds (density of about 50 points cm^2) have been scaled using a reference marker, which is a graduated metallic bar placed above the model to be always visible in the 2D shoots (see Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.4 Optical devices employed during the experimental campaign: (a) Sony FDR-AX53; (b) Sony HDR-CX410VE; (c) Sony Cyber-shot DSC-HX9V 16.2 MP G Lens.

Figure 3.5 Marker used to scale the 3D point clouds of the model recovered by means of the SfM technique.

Then, the scaled 3D point clouds have been converted into meshes using a calculation grid 0.001 x 0.001 m. Such meshes have been employed to monitor the progression of the armor layer erosion under increasing wave load, using both traditional and novel techniques.

The evaluation of the traditional armor layer damage parameter $S_{d,m}$ defined by Broderick and Ahrens (1982) has been performed at the end of each sea state with reference to the entire width of the model B (Campos et al., 2014):

$$S_{d,m} = \frac{1}{n_{cs}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{cs}} \frac{A_{e,i}}{D_{n50}^2} \quad (3.2)$$

where n_{cs} is the number of cross sections of 3D reconstruction of the armor layer (spatial step of 0.001 m), $A_{e,i}$ is the eroded area of the i -th cross section with respect to the zero-damage condition and D_{n50} is the median nominal diameter of the armor units. Damage maps have been calculated as the difference between the armor layer mesh recovered at the end of each sea state and the initial one. Negative values of the height difference indicate the presence of excavations due to the displacements of one or more armor units, which can deposit in other zones of the armor later or near the structure toe, generating positive height differences. The study of the modifications of the armor layer surface roughness can give useful information concerning the damage or simple settling models experienced by the structure, even if significant damage levels are not reached. In addition, information about the roughness of the existing armor layer is of great interest if damaged rubble mound breakwaters are considered, since their section could be very different from the design one. Therefore, a novel analysis of the armor layer dynamics has been carried out, considering the surface macro-roughness and micro-roughness. A simplified sketch of the armor layer macro and micro roughness is shown in Figure 3.6 the first one represents the blocks laying surface (wavelength is of the order of 4 – 5

times D_{n50}), whereas the latter one gives a measure of the surface porosity of the armor layer (wavelength is of the order of D_{n50}).

The employed technique for the analysis of the armor layer surface is based on the 3D reconstructions of the structure recovered using the SfM technique at the beginning and at the end of each sea state. For the first time, the mesh processing procedure described by Blateyron (2014) for the analysis of the surface topography of metal foils used in industry has been employed to study the surface roughness of the armor layer of a rubble mound structure. First, the mesh has been properly rotated referring to a horizontal plane and denoised using a low pass 2D Gaussian filter with a cut off frequency equal to 0.001 m^{-1} . It is important to point out that in correspondence of the cut off frequency of a low pass 2D Gaussian filter, only the 50% reduction of the signal power occurs, and such a reduction increases towards smaller frequencies (Whitehouse, 2002). Another 2D Gaussian filter, with a cut off frequency equal to inverse of the median nominal diameter of the armor units (i.e. $1/D_{n50}$), has been applied to the elaborated mesh, to distinguish the macro-roughness and micro-roughness. As regards the macro-roughness, bidimensional traditional roughness descriptors have been calculated for the ensemble average of the y profiles of the armor layer surface, such as the mean wavelength λ_M and the maximum wave height HD (Gadelmawla et al., 2002).

A two-dimensional spectra analysis of the micro-roughness has been carried out implementing a 2D Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the surface (Sidick, 2009; Dong and Stout, 1995; Czifra et al., 2011). The micro-roughness surface is not periodic as required for FFT analysis. Hence, a preliminary removal of the edge artifacts (i.e. several crosses of high amplitude coefficients in the frequency domain) has been performed by applying the windowing approach, which consists in progressively attenuating the edges of the surface. To this aim a radially symmetric Hann windows has been applied (Jacobs et al., 2017). Then the micro-roughness spectral wavelength λ_M relative to the spectrum centroids has been calculated using the following equation (Nelson and Voulgaris, 2014; Nelson and Voulgaris, 2015; Voulgaris and Morin, 2008):

$$\lambda_M = \frac{1}{\sqrt{f_{x,c}^2 + f_{y,c}^2}} \quad (3.3)$$

where $f_{x,m}$ and $f_{y,m}$ are the spectral frequencies relative to the spectrum centroid respectively along x and y directions.

Figure 3.6 Sketch of the armor layer surface (1) macro-roughness and (2) micro-roughness analyzed through the SfM based technique. The dashed and continuous lines respectively represent the generic design and damaged cross section.

Only for the experiments presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023a), the overtopping phenomenon has been monitored by the video camera R2 (Sony HDR-CX410VE, see Figure 3.4b), which has been placed on a side scaffolding to record the waves going beyond the crest of the structure, as shown in Figure 3.1. It is worth pointing out that video camera R2 has been synchronized with the other measurement instruments thanks to LabView code. In addition, the measurement of the mean overtopping discharge rate per linear meter q has been performed, by using a specially designed system placed behind the model (see Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.7) as suggested by Iuppa et al. (2019). A collection tank (0.40 x 0.40 x 0.30 m) has been properly anchored to the ground and equipped with a trapezium shaped inclined ramp (largest side 0.98 m, smaller side 0.22 m, height 0.60 m) to channel the water that overflow behind the structure.

An acoustic sensor (Pepperl Fuchs UC500-30GM70-IE2R2-V15) measured the water level inside the reservoir, in sync with the other measurement instruments. The continuous measurement of the water volume inside the collection tank has allowed the calculation of the mean overtopping discharge for a certain time interval, by means of a calibration law which relates levels and volumes inside the collection tank. Such a law has been defined before starting the physical model tests. In particular, the water levels correspondent to subsequent 0.002 m³ poured water volumes have been measured by the acoustic gauge until a total volume of 0.024 m³ was collected inside the tank. Then parabolic volumes levels law has been calculated through the last squares method. Three parallel drainage pumps (NEWA JET 6000) connected to the reservoir have ensured its emptying until a minimum threshold (i.e. 0.12 m) when reached the fixed maximum water level (i.e. 0.30 m), thanks to the LabView code. The tank emptying process lasted about 10 s, and hence it is fast enough to not significantly influence the measurement of the mean overtopping discharge.

Figure 3.7 System for the measurement of the mean overtopping discharge per meter q placed behind the physical model.

Design and construction of the physical model

The 1:70 geometrically undistorted model has been constructed according to most current state of art of physical modeling of rubble mound structures (Frostick et al., 2011). The size of quarry stones and of artificial blocks used for the construction of the physical model has been selected to guarantee the similarity in terms of stability number between model and prototype, according to the methodology proposed by Hudson et al. (1959). Therefore, the weight of each kind of employed unit has been scaled by dividing the prototype weight by the following factor:

$$N_{wa} = \frac{N_{\gamma a} N_L^3}{N_{\gamma a/\gamma w-1}^3} \tag{3.4}$$

where N_{wa} is the stability number, $N_{\gamma a}$ is the ratio between the specific weight of prototype and model unit, N_L is the geometric scale (i.e. 70 in this case) and $N_{\gamma a/\gamma w-1}$ is the ratio between the buoyant density of prototype and model unit.

Table 3.II reports the densities of the prototype and model units and of water, whereas in Table 3.III are showed the results of the application method proposed by Hudson et al. (1979) for the calculation of the D_{n50} of both quarry stones and artificial blocks.

It is worth to point out that the used resin to produce the artificial armor units (see Figure 3.8) has been chosen so that the calculated D_{n50} was sufficiently large to minimize the viscous scale effects, i.e. to ensure Reynolds number of the armor units greater than $1 - 4 \times 10^4$ (Van der Meer, 1988). In addition, the armor blocks have been painted to both reduce the friction scale effects and facilitate the optical analysis of the armor unit dynamics.

Table 3.II Density of water ρ_w and of the employed quarry stones and artificial blocks (respectively ρ_{qs} and ρ_s) at prototype and model scale.

	ρ_w [kg/m ³]	ρ_{qs} [kg/m ³]	ρ_s [kg/m ³]
Prototype	1030	2600	2300
Model	1000	2600	1560

Table 3.III Median nominal diameter D_{n50} of the employed quarry stoned and artificial blocks at prototype and model scale.

	D_{n50} [m]				
	I category	II category	III category	Cube	Antifer
Prototype	0.268-0.727	0.727-1.049	1.049-1.391	2.998	2.354
Model	0.004-0.010	0.010-0.014	0.014-0.019	0.059	0.046

Figure 3.8 Artificial cubes ($D_{n50} = 0.059$ m) and Antifer ($D_{n50} = 0.046$ m) employed for the construction of the physical model.

The construction of the physical model within the wave tank (see Figure 3.1) for each testing phase consisted of the following steps:

1. building of an impermeable wall as back support of the rubble mound structure (see Figure 3.9a);
2. installation of the specially designed concrete wave wall (see Figure 3.9b);
3. placement of reference side plywood shapes and wired for the correct reproduction of the structure layers (see Figure 3.10a);
4. construction of the structure core by placing I and II category quarry stones, previously by means of 1/6'' and 1/2'' sieves, over plastic squared meshed net of 0.005 m to avoid the removal of the finest bottom material (see Figure 3.10a);
5. construction of the structure core using III category quarry stones, previously selected by means of 1/2'' and 3/4'' sieves (see Figure 3.10b);
6. construction of existing armor layer by randomly placing the cubic units (see Figure 3.11a);
7. construction of the toe berm using III category quarry stones, previously selected by means of 1/2'' and 3/4'' sieves, to support the additional armor layer (see Figure 3.11b);
8. construction of the additional armor layer by randomly placing the cubic units or the Antifer blocks (see Figure 3.12).

It is worth to point out that the values of armor layer porosity are comparable to the ones of literature experimental campaigns on rubble mound breakwaters made up of cubic (van Gent, 2014) or Antifer armor units (Frens, 2007).

Figure 3.9 Construction of the physical model: (a) impermeable wall as back support of the rubble mound structure; (b) specially designed concrete wave wall.

Figure 3.10 Construction of the physical model: (a) core of the rubble mound structure made up of I and II category quarry stones; (b) filter layer of the rubble mound structure made up of III category quarry stones.

Figure 3.11 Construction of the physical model: (a) existing armor layer made up of cubic units; (b) toe berm made up of III category quarry stones.

Figure 3.12 Construction of the physical model: (a) additional armor layer made up of cubic units; (b) additional armor layer made up of Antifer units.

Test conditions and experimental procedure

Five representative sections of the Catania harbor breakwater have been tested: in particular, Stagnitti et al. (2023a) tested two representative cross-sections of the Catania harbor breakwater, i.e. cross-section no. 10 and section no. 40, whereas during the activities of the PROMETEO project experiments on cross-sections no. 17, no. 21 and no. 34 have been conducted. Figure 3.13 shows the layout of the Port of Catania with the indication of the outer breakwater representative cross-sections.

Figure 3.13 Layout of the Port of Catania and indication of the outer breakwater representative cross-sections no. 10 ($H_s/d = 0.39$), no.17 ($H_s/d = 0.38$), no. 21 ($H_s/d = 0.37$), no. 34 ($H_s/d = 0.42$) and no. 40 ($H_s/d = 0.34$).

Sections no. 10, n. 17 and no. 21 (see Figure 3.14a-c) has been selected because of their strong geometric irregularities and characterized by a ratio between the design significant wave height and the water depth $H_{s,d}/h$ equal, respectively to 0.39, 0,38 and 0.37. Sections n. 34 and n. 40 (see Figure 3.14d-e) has been chosen because of there are the representative of the most offshore sections, and hence the most exposed part of the breakwater to the wave load, being $H_{s,d}/h$ equal, respectively to 0.42 and 0.34.

For cross-sections no. 10 and 40, the six upgrading solutions described in Table 3.IV and illustrated in Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16 have been tested. For cross-sections no. 17, 21, and 34 only configuration AS has been studied (see Figure 3.17)

Figure 3.14 Sketches of the representative cross-section of the Catania harbor breakwater: (a) cross-section no. 10; (b) cross-section no. 17; (c) cross-section no. 21; (d) cross-section no. 34; (e) cross-section no. 40.

Table 3.IV Summary of the tested configurations of the Catania Harbor breakwater. Weights and heights are given in the prototype scale.

Configuration	Description
E	Existing structure with wave wall crest raised up to +8.50 m above MSL
EM	Existing structure with wave wall crest raised up to +9.50 m above MSL
AS	Originally proposed armor layer restoration with 30 t Antifer units, a quarry stone toe berm and wave wall crest raised up to +8.50 m above MSL
AD	Double layer 30 t Antifer blocks armor layer restoration, a quarry stone toe berm and wave wall crest raised up to +8.50 m above MSL
CM	Single layer 62 t cubic blocks armor layer restoration, a quarry stone toe berm and wave wall crest raised up to +8.50 m above MSL
CS	Armor layer restoration with 62 t cubic blocks laid following the AS section, also moving the existent blocks if necessary, a quarry stone toe berm and wave wall crest raised up to +9.50 m above MSL

Figure 3.15 Sketches of the proposed upgrading solutions for the Catania harbor breakwater, cross-section no. 10: (a) configuration E; (b) configuration EM; (c) configuration AS (originally proposed by the Port authority); (d) configuration AD; (e) configuration CM; (f) configuration CS. Measures are given at prototype scale.

Figure 3.16 Sketches of the proposed upgrading solutions for the Catania harbor breakwater, cross-section no. 40: (a) configuration E; (b) configuration EM; (c) configuration AS (originally proposed by the Port authority); (d) configuration AD; (e) configuration CM; (f) configuration CS. Measures are given at prototype scale.

Figure 3.17 Sketches of the proposed upgrading solution AS for the Catania harbor breakwater: (a) cross-section no. 17; (b) cross-section no. 21; (c) cross-section no. 34. Measures are given at prototype scale.

A precise experimental procedure has been defined to ensure reliability and comparability of the test outcomes. Moreover, to this aim, about two hundred preliminary tests have been carried out to properly calibrate the hydrodynamic parameters that govern the wave motion inside the wave tank, and to examine the outputs of the measurement instruments. The input hydrodynamics conditions are summarized in Table 3.V, Table 3.VI, and

Table 3.VII, in terms of significant wave height H_s and peak wave period T_p of random JONSWAP wave motion, mean sea level h and number of incident waves N_w . Note that the design h is equal to the water depth at the toe of the structure plus the increase due to meteorological and astronomical tide, which for the site of Catania is equal to 0.50 m.

For each configuration (see Table 3.IV), first, a shakedown test has been carried out for the setting of the structure with three consecutive sea state of 1500 waves corresponding to 5 years return period. Then, traditional tests considering sea states of 4500 waves, divided into three equal intervals, corresponding to 10, 50 and 100 years return period (the latter is the return period) have been performed. If no damage has been observed, a further sea state of 4500 waves, divided into three identical intervals, characterize by significant wave height equal to 120% of the 100 years return period one (i.e. $H_{s,d}$) has been reproduced. Finally, the effects of mean sea level rise (SLR) have been investigated, considering the existing structure with wave wall raised up to +8.50 m above MSL (i.e. configuration E, see Figure 3.15a, Figure 3.16a and Table 3.IV). Indeed, sea states corresponding to 50 and 100 years return period of 4500 waves, divided into three intervals of 1500, have been simulated in the presence of 0.02 (i.e. 1.40 m in the prototype scale, see Table 3.V and

Table 3.VII) increase in mean sea level (Lambeck et al. 2011). Therefore, a total of 192 tests have been performed for the six upgrading options of the Catania harbor breakwater at cross-sections

no. 10 and no. 40, and a total of 45 test have performed for the configuration AS at cross-sections no. 17, 21, and 34.

Table 3.V Input hydrodynamics conditions in terms of significant wave height (H_s), peak wave period (T_p), mean sea level (h) and number of waves (N_w) simulated during tests on the physical model of cross-section no. 10. The values are given at both prototype and model scale.

Wave ID	Prototype scale			Model scale			N_w [n. of waves]
	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	
I	4.49	9.63	17.00	0.06	1.15	0.24	3 x 1500
II	4.91	10.06	17.00	0.07	1.20	0.24	3 x 1500
III	5.81	10.971	17.00-8.40	0.08	1.31	0.24-0.26	3 x 1500
IV	6.16	11.34	17.00-8.40	0.09	1.36	0.24-0.26	3 x 1500
V	7.39	11.34	17.00	0.111	1.36	0.24	3 x 1500

Table 3.VI Input hydrodynamics conditions in terms of significant wave height (H_s), peak wave period (T_p), mean sea level (h) and number of waves (N_w) simulated during tests on the physical model of cross-sections no. 17 and no. 21. The values are given at both prototype and model scale.

Wave ID	Prototype scale			Model scale			N_w [n. of waves]
	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	
I	4.66	9.62	19.00	0.067	1.15	0.25	3 x 1500
II	5.08	10.05	19.00	0.073	1.20	0.25	3 x 1500
III	5.92	10.96	19.00	0.085	1.31	0.25	3 x 1500
IV	6.24	11.33	19.00	0.089	1.35	0.25	3 x 1500
V	7.49	11.33	19.00	0.107	1.35	0.25	3 x 1500

Table 3.VII Input hydrodynamics conditions in terms of significant wave height (H_s), peak wave period (T_p), mean sea level (h) and number of waves (N_w) simulated during tests on the physical model of cross-sections no. 34 and no. 40. The values are given at both prototype and model scale.

Wave ID	Prototype scale			Model scale			N_w [n. of waves]
	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	
I	4.68	9.65	19.00	0.067	1.15	0.29	3 x 1500
II	5.14	10.08	19.00	0.073	1.20	0.29	3 x 1500
III	6.21	11.00	19.00	0.089	1.31	0.29	3 x 1500
IV	6.65	11.37	19.00	0.095	1.36	0.29	3 x 1500
V	7.98	11.37	19.00	0.114	1.36	0.29	3 x 1500

Evaluation of the armor layer roughness descriptors

The SfM technique has been used for the 3D reconstruction of the tested configurations of the Catania harbor breakwater, at the beginning and at the end of each sea state, following the methodology proposed by Stagnitti et al. (2023a). As mentioned in the description of the experimental setup, such recovered point clouds have been used to perform a novel analysis of the armor layer surface dynamics, in terms of variation of the macro and micro roughness under increasing wave loads. In the following, the procedure for the evaluation of the macro and micro roughness descriptors used for the study of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater is described.

First, the mesh of the armor layer surface has been recovered from the 3D point cloud derived from the application of the SfM technique. Figure 3.18 shows the case of configuration AS of section n.10 after the simulation of the 5 years return period sea state. The mesh represents both the armor layer and the toe berm. Therefore, only mesh of the armor layer has been considered for the analysis of the macro and micro roughness. Once the mesh of the armor layer has been isolated, a plane has been adapted to the surface through the least squares method, to create a reference for the evaluation of the roughness in terms of discrepancy from a smooth plane. Both the plane and the mesh have been rotated around the x axis, so as to obtain a null inclination with respect to the $x - y$ plane (x axis orthogonal to the direction of the wave motion, y axis parallel to the direction of the wave motion, origin in the right upper corner of the mesh), as showed in Figure 3.19. Note that the origin of the z axis corresponds to the previously fitted plan. Then, the removal of measurement noise from the mesh has been performed using a low pass 2D Gaussian filter with a cut off frequency equal to 0.01 m^{-1} .

The filtered mesh of the armor layer has been further elaborated using another 2D Gaussian filter, with a cut off frequency equal to the inverse of the median nominal diameter of the armor units (i.e. $1/D_{n50}$), for the identification of the macro and micro roughness (see Figure 3.20). The macro roughness represents the waviness of block laying surface (wavelength of the order $4 - 5$ times D_{n50}), whereas the micro roughness is a measure of the porosity of the armor layer due to the relative position of the units (wavelength of the order of D_{n50}). The armor layer macro roughness (see Figure 3.20a) has been analyzed through a bi-dimensional approach along the y direction, to characterize the cross section mean profile. Therefore, the ensemble average of all the y profiles has been evaluated, as showed in Figure 3.21. The mean wavelength λ_M and the maximum wave height HD have been calculated for the quantitative description of the ensemble average curve.

Figure 3.18 Example of the mesh calculated from the SfM 3D reconstruction of the physical model of the Catania harbor breakwater: configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 after the simulation of wave I.

Figure 3.19 Example of rotated mesh around the x axis to obtain a null inclination with respect to the $x - y$ plane: configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 after the simulation of wave I.

As regards the armor layer micro-roughness (see Figure 3.20b), a 2D spectral analysis has been carried out, through the implementation of 2D FFT for the evaluation of the areal power spectral density (*APSD*), after making periodic the considered surface by means of radially symmetric Hann window. Figure 3.22 shows an example of areal power spectrum, for the case of configuration AS of section n. 10 after the simulation of the 5 years return period sea state. Note that the areal power spectra contain many useful information for the characterization of surfaces. In addition, in the input data to the 2D FFT are real numbers, the knowledge of a half of the spectrum is sufficient for the description of the surface (Krogstad, 2004). Under such an assumption, the centroid spectral wavelength λ_M (see equation (3.3)) has been identified as the most significant descriptor of the micro-roughness, and its relationship with the damage mechanisms has been investigated.

Figure 3.20 Example of armor layer (a) macro roughness and (b) micro roughness meshes: configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 after simulation of wave I.

Figure 3.21 Example of ensemble average of the *y* profiles of the armor layer macro roughness: configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 after the simulation of wave I.

Figure 3.22 Example of 2D spectrum of the armor layer micro roughness: configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 after the simulation of wave I.

Analysis of the experimental results

The experimental results on the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater regard both the armor layer damage evolution and the overtopping rates caused by increasing wave load. In the following, a description of the simulated wave motions is presented, which focuses on the reflection phenomenon.

Therefore, in the following a description of the simulated wave motions is presented, which focuses on the reflection phenomenon. Then, the armor layer damage dynamic is discussed, referring to both traditional analysis (i.e. counting of displaced units and damage maps) and novel ones (i.e. investigation on macro and micro-roughness of the armor layer surface). Finally, the characterization of the hydraulic performances of each tested configuration is given in terms of mean overtopping discharge.

Incident wave motion

The incident wave motion has been calculated for each test using the four-gauge method proposed by Faraci et al. (2015), which allows the calculation of the incident and reflected wave spectra and of the reflection coefficient.

Figure 3.23 shows the comparison between the input JONSWAP spectrum and the typical experimental incident and reflected wave spectra, smoothed out according to the method proposed by Boccotti (2004). The incident wave spectrum is characterized by some peaks for frequency close to 1.0 Hz, about 2.5 times higher than the JONSWAP spectrum. Instead, at low frequencies the experimental spectrum is quite well approximated by the theoretical one. The discrepancies between measured and theoretical incident wave spectra are likely due to intrinsic characteristics of the input transmission system, and to the generation procedure typical of the flap type wave maker. Nevertheless, the simulated waves are sufficiently similar to the JONSWAP ones for the scope of the present work.

As shown in Figure 3.24, wave reflection is quite moderate, considering that active wave absorption has not been employed. In particular, the reflection coefficient k_r , measured during the tests is 0.25 on average. Table 3.VIII, Table 3.IX, Table 3.X, Table 3.XI, and Table 3.XII report

the reflection coefficient evaluated for each tested configuration, as a function of the Iribarren number $\xi_{m-1,0}$, which is defined as follows:

$$\xi_{m-1,0} = \frac{\tan \alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi H_s}{gT_{m-1,0}^2}}} \quad (3.5)$$

where α is the armor slope angle (equal to 0.5 for the considered configurations), H_s is the significant wave height and $T_{m-1,0} = m_{-1}/m_0$ is the spectral wave period. The measured reflection coefficients have been compared with the experimental formulation suggested by Zanuttigh and van der Meer (2008):

$$k_r = \tanh(a_r \zeta_{m-1,0}^{b_r}) \quad (3.6)$$

$$a_r = 0.167 [1 - e^{-3.2 \gamma_f}] \quad (3.7)$$

$$b_r = 1.49 (\gamma_f - 0.38)^2 + 0.86 \quad (3.8)$$

where a_r and b_r are two parameters dependent on the friction factor γ_f , which is equal to 0.47 for both double layer of cubes and Antifer blocks (EurOtop, 2018).

Figure 3.24 shows that the experimental points are quite close to the Zanuttigh and van der Meer (2008) curve, despite a slight tendency to underestimate theoretical values. Such results can be due to the fact the Eq. (3.6) and Eq. (3.8) were calibrated for a homogeneous database on wave reflection referred to newly built breakwaters. Indeed, the smaller slope compared to the design one and irregular surface of damaged rubble mound structures may likely induce lower reflection than a straight slope. As regards the configurations with additional armor layer, the differences between predicted and experimental reflection coefficient can be due to the influence of a more complex layering on the overall porosity of the structure.

Figure 3.23 Example of incident and reflected wave spectra evaluated through the four-gauge method proposed by Faraci et al. (2015) and smoothed according to the procedure of Boccotti (2004): configuration AS of section n. 10 under wave IV.

Figure 3.24 Comparison between the experimental reflection coefficient k_r , expressed as a function of the Iribarren number $\xi_{m-1,0}$, and the equation suggested by Zanuttigh and van der Meer (2008).

Table 3.VIII Reflection coefficient and correspondent Iribarren number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 10.

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS		AD		CM		CS	
		$\xi_{m-1,0}$	k_r										
I	1	2.57	0.20	2.42	0.23	2.48	0.29	2.20	0.23	2.40	0.30	2.47	0.33
	2	2.56	0.20	2.52	0.23	2.61	0.30	2.36	0.22	2.35	0.30	2.55	0.35
	3	2.31	0.19	2.47	0.24	2.39	0.29	2.37	0.22	2.41	0.31	2.53	0.35
II	1	2.35	0.21	2.70	0.26	2.37	0.28	2.45	0.23	2.41	0.30	2.60	0.34
	2	2.32	0.20	2.45	0.24	2.33	0.29	2.30	0.23	2.37	0.29	2.75	0.34
III	3	2.36	0.21	2.38	0.23	2.37	0.28	2.39	0.23	2.47	0.29	2.46	0.34
	1	2.63	0.23	2.50	0.26	2.36	0.27	2.34	0.21	2.46	0.28	2.65	0.32
	2	2.68	0.24	2.64	0.28	2.57	0.27	2.54	0.23	2.45	0.27	2.68	0.32
IV	3	2.89	0.27	2.66	0.27	2.48	0.26	2.31	0.22	2.54	0.28	2.61	0.33
	1	2.66	0.25	2.63	0.26	2.57	0.28	2.81	0.23	2.58	0.26	2.71	0.31
	2	2.54	0.27	2.64	0.28	2.55	0.30	2.57	0.22	2.52	0.27	2.49	0.32
	3	2.55	0.27	2.52	0.26	2.71	0.28	2.31	0.24	2.39	0.26	2.61	0.30
	1 SLR	2.24	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	2 SLR	2.34	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	3 SLR	2.29	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1	2.73	0.27	2.57	0.28	2.76	0.26	2.72	0.24	2.66	0.26	2.61	0.30
	2	2.49	0.26	2.67	0.29	2.40	0.26	2.94	0.27	2.71	0.27	2.52	0.32
	3	2.71	0.27	2.37	0.26	2.85	0.27	2.34	0.25	2.55	0.26	2.68	0.31
	1 SLR	2.16	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2 SLR	2.18	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
3 SLR	2.34	0.27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 3.IX Reflection coefficient and correspondent Iribarren number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 17.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\xi_{m-1,0}$	k_r
I	1	2.38	0.29
	2	2.40	0.28
	3	2.39	0.30
II	1	2.38	0.29
	2	2.48	0.30
	3	2.30	0.28
III	1	2.35	0.29
	2	2.44	0.28
	3	2.48	0.29
IV	1	2.50	0.30
	2	2.33	0.28
	3	2.44	0.28
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	2.51	0.28
	2	2.47	0.28
	3	2.42	0.29
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.X Reflection coefficient and correspondent Iribarren number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 21.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\xi_{m-1,0}$	k_r
I	1	2.33	0.25
	2	2.31	0.22
	3	2.37	0.24
II	1	2.41	0.22
	2	2.28	0.23
	3	2.58	0.23
III	1	2.40	0.23
	2	2.51	0.21
	3	2.48	0.21
IV	1	2.60	0.22
	2	2.60	0.22
	3	2.54	0.21
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	2.40	0.19
	2	2.65	0.21
	3	2.43	0.21
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XI Reflection coefficient and correspondent Iribarren number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 34.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\xi_{m-1,0}$	k_r
I	1	2.40	0.25
	2	2.61	0.25
	3	2.36	0.25
II	1	2.66	0.25
	2	2.46	0.25
	3	2.41	0.23
III	1	2.39	0.25
	2	2.40	0.25
	3	2.40	0.24
IV	1	2.50	0.24
	2	2.43	0.25
	3	2.42	0.24
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	2.42	0.26
	2	2.60	0.28
	3	2.49	0.28
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XII Reflection coefficient and correspondent Iribarren number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 40.

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS		AD		CM		CS	
		$\xi_{m-1,0}$	k_r										
I	1	1.99	0.19	2.44	0.21	2.34	0.27	2.15	0.26	2.27	0.23	2.24	0.22
	2	1.92	0.19	2.09	0.19	2.38	0.28	2.27	0.26	2.45	0.24	2.07	0.22
	3	2.00	0.19	2.36	0.21	2.45	0.27	2.2	0.25	2.28	0.26	2.14	0.21
II	1	2.17	0.19	2.35	0.21	2.51	0.27	2.21	0.26	2.31	0.25	2.12	0.23
	2	2.15	0.2	2.40	0.22	2.64	0.28	2.28	0.27	2.41	0.25	2.1	0.23
	3	1.84	0.19	2.48	0.23	2.36	0.26	2.32	0.26	2.45	0.25	2.03	0.22
III	1	2.23	0.21	2.54	0.23	2.44	0.27	2.39	0.27	2.4	0.24	2.25	0.23
	2	2.29	0.21	2.46	0.24	2.31	0.26	2.18	0.25	2.38	0.24	2.58	0.24
	3	2.25	0.22	2.59	0.26	2.12	0.25	2.39	0.25	2.58	0.24	2.32	0.23
IV	1	2.40	0.24	2.33	0.25	2.21	0.26	2.21	0.23	2.43	0.24	2.58	0.25
	2	2.54	0.25	2.84	0.28	2.34	0.23	2.25	0.23	2.32	0.23	2.7	0.25
	3	2.39	0.22	2.77	0.27	2.13	0.24	2.36	0.23	2.39	0.24	2.65	0.25
	1 SLR	2.43	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	2.49	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	2.20	0.28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	1	2.39	0.24	2.72	0.29	2.1	0.23	2.38	0.21	2.38	0.21	3.02	0.28
	2	2.38	0.25	2.60	0.25	2.49	0.25	2.27	0.22	2.26	0.22	2.28	0.22
	3	2.21	0.23	2.62	0.26	3.57	0.28	2.22	0.22	2.3	0.21	2.58	0.24
	1 SLR	2.37	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	2.18	0.28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	2.18	0.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Armor blocks displacements

The evaluation of the damage suffered by the structure under increasing wave load has been performed through the calculation of the parameter N_{od} , which is defined by equation (3.1). Each simulated sea state has been divided into three wave series, having the same input significant wave height and peak wave period, but different frequencies combinations. The cumulative damage parameter N_{od} has been calculated at the end of each wave series, to identify possible influences of the sea state duration on the structure response.

Table 3.XIII, Table 3.IV, Table 3.XV, Table 3.XVI, and Table 3.XVII report the experimental cumulative N_{od} measured after each test, together with the corresponding stability number (i.e. the ratio between the incident significant wave height H_s and the product between the relative buoyant density Δ and the median nominal diameter of the armor units D_{n50}).

Table 3.XIII Damage parameter N_{od} and stability number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 10.

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS		AD		CM		CS	
		$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$	N_{od}										
I	1	1.82	0.00	1.82	0.00	2.33	2.00	2.33	2.09	1.82	0.28	2.12	0.08
	2	1.82	0.00	1.82	0.00	2.33	2.06	2.33	2.13	1.82	0.28	2.12	0.08
	3	1.82	0.00	1.82	0.03	2.33	2.08	2.72	2.15	1.82	0.33	2.12	0.08
II	1	2.12	0.00	2.12	0.03	2.72	2.12	2.72	2.23	2.12	0.33	2.12	0.08
	2	2.12	0.00	2.12	0.03	2.72	2.12	2.72	2.25	2.12	0.33	2.12	0.08
	3	2.12	0.00	2.12	0.03	2.72	2.12	2.72	2.27	2.12	0.33	2.12	0.08
III	1	2.42	0.03	2.42	0.03	3.11	2.41	3.11	2.54	2.42	0.41	2.42	0.08
	2	2.42	0.06	2.42	0.03	3.11	2.79	3.11	2.94	2.42	0.44	2.42	0.11
	3	2.42	0.06	2.42	0.03	3.11	3.06	3.11	2.98	2.42	0.44	2.42	0.11
IV	1	2.72	0.09	2.72	0.03	3.49	3.80	3.49	3.10	2.72	0.62	2.72	0.11
	2	2.72	0.09	2.72	0.03	3.49	3.88	3.49	3.22	2.72	0.65	2.72	0.14
	3	2.72	0.09	2.72	0.03	3.49	4.01	3.49	3.34	2.72	0.65	2.72	0.17
	1 SLR	2.60	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	2.51	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	2.60	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	1	3.33	0.09	3.33	0.03	4.27	5.54	4.27	4.52	3.33	0.83	3.33	0.28
	2	3.33	0.09	3.33	0.03	4.27	5.71	4.27	4.52	3.33	1.03	3.33	0.36
	3	3.33	0.09	3.33	0.03	4.27	6.04	4.27	4.96	3.33	1.18	3.33	0.39
	1 SLR	2.81	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	2.88	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	2.78	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3.XIV Damage parameter N_{od} and stability number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 17.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$	N_{od}
I	1	2.72	0.00
	2	2.72	0.00
	3	2.72	0.00
II	1	2.72	0.00
	2	2.72	0.05
	3	3.11	0.05
III	1	3.11	0.05
	2	3.11	0.05
	3	3.11	0.05
IV	1	3.49	0.09
	2	3.49	0.09
	3	3.49	0.09
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	3.88	0.09
	2	4.27	0.19
	3	3.88	0.19
V	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XV Damage parameter N_{od} and stability number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 21.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$	N_{od}
I	1	2.72	2.40
	2	2.72	2.40
	3	2.72	2.50
II	1	2.72	2.50
	2	2.72	2.50
	3	2.72	2.50
III	1	3.11	3.11
	2	3.11	3.11
	3	3.11	3.13
IV	1	3.49	3.19
	2	3.88	3.25
	3	3.88	3.27
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	4.27	3.60
	2	4.27	4.00
	3	4.27	4.13
V	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XVI Damage parameter N_{od} and stability number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 34.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$	N_{od}
I	1	2.72	0.89
	2	2.33	0.94
	3	2.72	0.94
II	1	2.72	0.94
	2	2.72	0.94
	3	2.72	0.94
III	1	3.49	1.00
	2	3.49	1.02
	3	3.49	1.04
IV	1	3.88	1.08
	2	3.88	1.10
	3	3.49	1.12
V	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
	1	4.27	1.18
	2	3.88	1.20
	3	3.88	1.22
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XVII Damage parameter N_{od} and stability number evaluated for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 40.

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS		AD		CM		CS	
		$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$	N_{od}										
I	1	2.12	0.83	2.12	0.25	3.11	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.05	2.12	0.00
	2	2.12	0.86	2.12	0.30	3.11	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.05	2.12	0.00
	3	2.12	0.86	2.12	0.30	3.11	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.08	2.12	0.00
II	1	2.12	0.86	2.12	0.35	2.72	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.08	2.12	0.00
	2	2.42	0.86	2.12	0.35	2.33	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.08	2.12	0.00
	3	2.42	0.86	2.12	0.35	2.72	0.43	2.72	0.92	2.12	0.08	2.12	0.00
III	1	2.72	0.94	2.42	0.50	3.11	0.43	3.49	1.07	2.72	0.08	2.72	0.00
	2	2.72	0.99	2.72	0.50	3.49	0.43	3.49	1.11	2.72	0.08	2.42	0.00
	3	2.72	1.02	2.72	0.50	3.49	0.43	3.49	1.11	2.72	0.08	2.72	0.00
IV	1	3.03	1.11	3.03	0.53	3.49	0.56	3.88	1.15	3.03	0.14	3.03	0.00
	2	3.03	1.11	3.03	0.53	3.88	0.60	3.88	1.25	3.03	0.14	2.72	0.00
	3	3.03	1.11	3.03	0.53	3.88	0.62	3.88	1.27	3.03	0.17	3.03	0.00
V	1 SLR	2.72	1.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	2.72	1.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	2.72	1.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1	3.33	1.14	3.33	0.53	4.27	0.62	4.27	1.31	3.33	0.17	3.33	0.00
	2	3.33	1.14	3.33	0.53	4.27	0.84	4.27	1.37	3.33	0.17	3.33	0.00
	3	3.33	1.14	3.33	0.53	4.27	1.02	4.27	1.49	3.33	0.17	3.03	0.00
	1 SLR	3.03	1.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	3.03	1.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	3.03	1.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The experimental data on armor blocks displacement after 4500 waves are summarized in Figure 3.25 where the cumulative values of damage parameter N_{od} evaluated for each tested configuration are expressed as a function of the stability number. Since there are no state of art damage progression model for upgraded rubble mound breakwater, the formula proposed by van der Meer (1988) for double layer of cubes laid on a slope of 1:1.5 with a notional permeability equal to 0.4 (hereinafter vdM formula) has been compared with the experimental results. Such a formula can be applied also for Antifer units, whose geometry is very similar to the cubic ones.

The results shown in Figure 3.25a demonstrate that the already damage existing armor layer of configurations E and EM (see Figure 3.15a-b, Figure 3.16a-b and Table 3.IV) is quite stable and that its behavior is not adequately represented by vdM formula. The different response of the two sections demonstrates that the deterioration processes suffered by the present armor layer of the Catania harbor breakwater led to the creation of voids of different shape and size along the structure, causing a geometric and thus structural non-uniformity.

The results on damage dynamics of the four analyzed upgrading options that consist in rising the wave wall and in adding an extra armor layer over the existing one (i.e. configurations AS, AD, CM and CS, see Table 3.IV) highlight the existence of two different responses of the structure in the case of presence or absence of a sufficient support at the toe of the additional units. Indeed, configurations AS, AD and CM present a quarry stone toe berm able to support the extra armor blocks only for cross-sections no. 17 and no. 40. Instead, configuration CS always ensure an adequate support to the additional armor layer, thanks to the proper reshaping of the existing structure. Figure 3.25b-c shows that, for the same stability number, the damage parameter N_{od} measured for the configurations with sufficient support (hereinafter SS) at the toe of the extra armor layer reaches values up to 3÷7 times lower than the options which do not provide a proper support (hereinafter NSS). Figure 3.25b-c reveals also that the vdM formula cannot describe the structural response of the upgraded structure with additional armor layer. Such a result, which in part could be due to the lower wave turbulence caused by the small scale of the physical model (i.e. 1:70), seems to be mainly linked to the non-conventional nature of the considered structure, which is significantly different from the sections tested by van der Meer (1988) in terms of geometry, layering and porosity. Therefore, the vdM formula has been adapted to the experimental data on the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater, by means of the evaluation of the multiplicative empirical factor f_c , which allows to discriminate between SS and NSS behavior:

$$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = f_c \left(6.7 \frac{N_{od}^{0.4}}{N_w^{0.3}} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{2 \pi H_s}{g T_m^2} \right) \quad (3.9)$$

where N_{od} is the damage parameter, see equation (3.1), N_w is the number of incident waves, Δ and D_{n50} are respectively the relative buoyant density and the median nominal diameter of the armor blocks, H_s is the incident significant wave height, T_m is the mean wave period and g is the gravity acceleration. It is worth pointing out that the traditional vdM formula contains an empirical multiplicative factor equal to 1.00 with standard deviation equal to 1.00 with standard deviation equal to 0.10, which was here substituted by the factor f_c . Table 3.XVIII presents the estimate of the correction factor f_c and its standard deviation σ_{f_c} , for the two cases of sufficient (i.e. SS) and not sufficient support (i.e. NSS) at the toe of the additional armor layer.

Figure 3.25 Damage parameter N_{od} as a function of the stability number: (a) upgrading options which present the simple heightening of the wave wall; (b) upgrading options with a sufficient support at the toe of the additional armor layer (SS); (c) upgrading options without a sufficient support at the toe of the additional armor layer (NSS). The grey areas indicate the 95% confidence bounds of the damage considered results.

Table 3.XVIII Coefficient f_c for the vdM formula evaluated from the experimental results on damage dynamics.

	Sufficient support (SS)	Not sufficient support (NSS)
f_c	1.77	1.37
σ_{f_c}	0.30	0.22

Figure 3.25b-c indicates that the vdM formula returns N_{od} greater than the adapted one for the same stability number. In other terms, the vdM formula is more conservative and could lead to an expensive over sizing of the armor blocks, if applied for the design of upgrading solutions where the underlying structure has reached a stable configuration.

Armor layer erosion

The damage dynamics has been further investigated using the 3D reconstructions of the armor layer surface derived from the application of the SfM technique. Data for 3D reconstruction of the armor layer have been acquired for all the tested structures in no-damage conditions. However, the data relative to configuration AS at cross-section no. 34 are not usable due to technical issues that arose during the acquisition phase. Moreover, these data have been acquired: i) at the end of the last wave I, wave III, wave IV, and wave V tests for configurations AD, E, and CM at cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40, EM and CS at cross-sections no. 10, and AS at cross-section no. 21; ii) at the end of the last wave I, wave III, and wave IV tests for configuration AS at cross-section no. 10; iii) at the end of the last wave III, wave IV, and wave V tests for configuration AS at cross-sections no. 40; iv) at the end of the last wave I and wave V tests for configuration EM at cross-sections no. 40; v) at the end of the last wave IV and wave V tests for configuration CS at cross-sections no. 40; vi) at the end of the last wave I, wave II, wave III, wave IV, and wave V tests for configuration AS at cross-section no. 17 vii) at the end of the last wave I, wave II, wave III, wave IV, and wave V tests for configuration AS at cross-section no. 34 The elaboration of the experimental data has been completed for cross-sections no. 10, no. 21, and

no. 40, whereas it is in progress for the other two. The validity of the SfM elaborations has been verified by means of the comparison between the damage parameter $S_{d,m}$ evaluated for all the tested configurations from Eq. (3.2) and the damage parameter $S_{d,c}$ calculated as a function of N_{od} , using the following empirical relationship (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002):

$$S_{d,c} = \frac{N_{od}}{G(1 - n)} \quad (3.10)$$

where G is the armor units gradation factor (equal to 1 for artificial blocks) and n is the porosity of the armor layer.

The scatter plot in Figure 3.26 shows that the estimates of $S_{d,m}$ and $S_{d,c}$ agree fairly well, being the data points closely distributed around the bisector, with a root mean square error *RMSE* equal to 0.13. In addition, the *BIAS* between the mean values of $S_{d,m}$ and $S_{d,c}$ is equal to -0.07, which means that $S_{d,m}$ evaluated from the SfM technique tends to slightly underestimate $S_{d,c}$. Finally, the correlation coefficient r is equal to 0.87, hence the scatter component of the error between $S_{d,m}$ and $S_{d,c}$ is limited. Therefore, the data acquired through the SfM technique are consistent with the results obtained for N_{od} .

The meshes of the armor layer surface calculated from the application of the SfM technique at the beginning and at the end of each sea state have been used for the construction of damage maps for all the tested configurations. The damage maps display the spatial final distribution of the armor layer erosion indicating erosion and deposition, respectively with negative and positive values of Δz . For the case of upgrading options where an additional armor layer is adopted, Figure 3.27, Figure 3.28 allow the comparison between the final erosion of configurations AS, AD and CM at cross-sections no. 10 and 40, whose structural behavior is influenced by the geometry of the existing armor layer, and configuration CS, whose response to the wave load does not depend on the geometry of the existing structure. It is observed that, in any case, the toe berm showed a sufficient resistance to the wave load and is subjected only to minimum adjustments. Therefore, the toe berm does not lose its functionality during the tests.

Configuration AS of section n. 10 (see Figure 3.27a) has been subject to a quite uniform erosive process in the region close to the free surface, which has caused the displacement of some Antifer units that the toe berm has not been able to stop. For the same configuration, section n. 40 (see Figure 3.27b) presents greater stability than section n. 10. Indeed, the sliding of the units removed by the wave action has been interrupted by the toe berm, with the exception of the zone in the vicinity of the left side wall of the tank, which is affected by boundary effects.

Figure 3.26 Comparison between the experimental damage parameter $S_{d,m}$ evaluated by means of the SfM technique and $S_{d,c}$ calculated as a function of the damage parameter N_{od} using the formula proposed by US Army Corps of Engineers (2002). Data refer to cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023a).

Figure 3.27 Final damage maps calculated for: (a) configuration AS of cross-section no. 10 (at the end of the last test with wave IV); (b) configuration AS of cross-section no. 40; (c) configuration AD of cross-section no. 10; (d) configuration AD of cross-section no. 40. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.28 Final damage maps calculated for: (a) configuration CM of cross-section no. 10; (b) configuration CM of cross-section no. 40; (c) configuration CS of cross-section no. 10; (d) configuration CS of cross-section no. 40. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Configuration AD of section n. 10 (see Figure 3.27c) is characterized by a large excavation uniformly distributed over the entire submerged armor layer. Clearly, the toe berm is not able to avoid the sliding of the armor blocks, which mainly deposit at the toe of the structure. Instead, configuration AD of section n. 40 (see Figure 3.27d) appears significantly more stable. Few units have moved away from the submerged zone and mainly have stopped close to the crest of the toe berm, which has properly supported the armor additional layer.

Configuration CM also shows better stability performances for section n. 40 than section n. 10. Indeed, in the former case no significant movements of the armor blocks have been recorded (see Figure 3.28b), whereas in latter one some units (see Figure 3.28a) have overcome the toe berm and have deposited at the base of the structure (note that the wave motion dragged the removed blocks out from the study area), thus causing the excess of the limit of intermediate damage level (CIRIA et al., 2007).

Considering configuration CS (see Figure 3.28c-d), both sections n. 10 and n. 40 show a comparable damage level, thanks to the presence of a sufficient support at the toe of the additional armor layer. Indeed, although in section n. 10 some blocks have moved from the submerged armor layer towards the toe of the structure, the overall damage level is still close to the initial damage threshold (CIRIA et al., 2007) for both sections.

Figure 3.29 shows the final damage maps recovered for configurations E and EM at cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40. At cross-section no. 10 (see Figure 3.29a-b), significant armor blocks displacements occur only at the toe of the structure, whereas at cross-section no. 40 (see Figure 3.29c-d) also the top portion of the armor layer suffers relevant damage. This result highlights that discrepancies in existing geometry of the armor layer implies important differences in the structure response to wave action. As regards the modest dissimilarities between configurations E and EM at the same cross-section, they are likely due to the difficulty in exactly reproducing the irregular geometry of the existing armor layer.

For the sake of completeness, from Figure 3.30 to Figure 3.42, the damage maps calculated for all the tested configurations at cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40 are presented.

Figure 3.29 Final damage maps calculated for: (a) configuration E of cross-section no. 10; (b) configuration EM of cross-section no. 10; (c) configuration E of cross-section no. 40; (d) configuration EM of cross-section no. 40. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.30 Damage maps calculated for configuration E at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.31 Damage maps calculated for configuration EM at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.32 Damage maps calculated for configuration AS at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.33 Damage maps calculated for configuration AD at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.34 Damage maps calculated for configuration CM at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.35 Damage maps calculated for configuration CS at cross-section no. 10 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.36 Damage maps calculated for configuration AS at cross-section no. 21 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.37 Damage maps calculated for configuration E at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.38 Damage maps calculated for configuration EM at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.39 Damage maps calculated for configuration AS at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave III test; (b) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (c) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.40 Damage maps calculated for configuration AD at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.41 Damage maps calculated for configuration CM at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave I test; (b) end of wave I tests and end of wave III tests; (c) end of wave III tests and end of wave IV test; (d) end of wave IV tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

Figure 3.42 Damage maps calculated for configuration CS at cross-section no. 40 between: (a) no-damage condition and end of wave IV test; (b) end of wave VI tests and end of wave V tests. The x and y axes are respectively orthogonal and parallel to the wave attack, whereas Δz is the height difference between the final and initial armor layer meshes.

In conclusion, the analysis of the presented results leads to some general conclusions, valid for the upgrading solutions using the additional armor layers (i.e. AS, AD, CM and CS). First, the erosive processes mainly affect the submerged armor layer. Indeed, the emerged structure is subject to simple settlement at best, due to the unit local rotations. Secondly, as already stated, the adequacy of the toe berm is fundamental for the overall structure stability. Indeed, only the configuration which provides a proper support at the toe of the additional units through the regularization of the existing armor layer (i.e. CS) ensures the same stability performances regardless of the existing armor layer geometry.

Armor layer surface roughness

The 3D reconstructions of the armor layer surface derived from the application of the SfM technique have been used to perform a novel analysis of the armor layer surface modification due to increasing wave load, based on the characterization of the micro and macro-roughness. The elaboration of the experimental data has been completed for cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40, whereas it is in progress for the other three.

The armor layer macro-roughness represents the blocks laying surface and it is described here by the ratio between its maximum wave height HD and its mean wavelength λ_M , both evaluated referring to the ensemble average of the y -profiles of the surface (see Figure 3.6). Such a ratio represents the mean slope of the macroroughness, and hence it assumes smaller values if the surface tends to a smooth plane.

Figure 3.43 shows the variation of HD/λ_M at the end of each j -th sea state with respect to the zero-damage condition, as a function of the stability number (i.e. the ratio between the incident significant wave height H_s and the product between the relative buoyant density Δ and the median nominal diameter D_{n50} of the armor blocks). For most of the tested configurations, the greatest deviation from the zero-damage condition occurs during the initial shakedown (i.e. under wave I), which corresponds to stability numbers less than 2.30.

Table 3.XIX reports the rate of the variation of HD/λ_M with respect to the zerodamage condition during and after shakedown. During shakedown, configurations without additional armor layer (i.e. E and EM) show different behaviors due to the non-homogeneous geometrical characteristics of the existing structure. Indeed, section n. 10 presents rates of the variation of HD/λ_M one order of magnitude smaller than those of section n. 40, thus confirming that the first section is more stable. However, the settling of the structure minimizes the differences between the two sections, which show similar rates of the variation of HD/λ_M after shakedown.

Figure 3.43 Evolution of the ratio between the maximum wave height HD and the mean wavelength λ_M of the macro-roughness referred to the zero-damage condition as a function of the stability number $H_s / \Delta D_{n50}$: (a) configuration with the existing armor layer; (b) SS upgraded configurations; (c) NSS upgraded configurations. The reference slopes $\pm 2\%$ are reported for the initial shakedown. The gray areas indicate the range of stability number for which the initial shakedown occurs. Data refer to cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023a).

Table 3.XIX Rate of the variation of the ratio between the maximum wave height (HD) and the mean wavelength (λ_M) of the macro-roughness as a function of the stability number ($H_s/\Delta D_{n50}$) with respect to the zero-damage condition during and after the initial shakedown. Data refer to cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023a).

Armor layer	Configuration	Rate of $(HD/\lambda_M)_i - (HD/\lambda_M)_0$	
		Pre-shakedown	Post-shakedown
Existing	Section no. 10 - E	0.2%	-0.2%
	Section no. 10 - EM	-0.4%	-0.1%
	Section no. 40 - E	-3.0%	0.4%
	Section no. 40 - EM	-1.0%	0.1%
Additional SS	Section no. 10 - CS	-0.6%	-1.6%
	Section no. 40 - AS	-1.4%	-1.1%
	Section no. 40 - AD	-1.6%	-0.3%
	Section no. 40 - CM	-0.4%	-0.8%
	Section no. 40 - CS	0.5%	-6.7%
Additional NSS	Section no. 10 - AS	-2.5%	0.5%
	Section no. 10 - AD	-4.3%	0.3%
	Section no. 10 - CM	-4.3%	1.4%

The upgrading solutions which involve the construction of a proper support at the toe of the additional armor units (SS) suffered minor modifications of the armor layer macro-roughness during the initial shakedown, with rates of the variation of HD/λ_M between the zero-damage condition and the initial shakedown always smaller than 2% in absolute terms. Also, after the shakedown, such a threshold is not overcome, with the exception of configuration CS of section n. 40, whose armor layer macro-roughness seems significantly modified only after sea state corresponding to wave V. During shakedown, upgrading options with extra armor layer but without a proper support at the toe (NSS) present values of the rates of variation of HD/λ_M with respect to the zero-damage condition quite larger than 2% in absolute terms, highlighting the poor stability of such configurations. However, the settled structure appears more stable, with rates of variation of HD/λ_M with respect to the zero-damage condition similar to the ones measured for SS configurations.

The armor layer micro-roughness, which represents the surface porosity, is directly related to the relative distance between the blocks. The mean spectral wavelength of the micro-roughness (λ_m), normalized with respect to the median nominal diameter of the armor units (D_{n50}), was identified as a good proxy of such a surface feature. Figure 3.44 shows the variation of λ_m/D_{n50} at the end of each j -th sea state with respect to the zero-damage condition as a function of the damage parameter N_{od} (see equation (3.1)). Four different behaviors can be distinguished.

For structure configurations characterized by small values of the damage parameter N_{od} , small oscillations of the change of λ_m/D_{n50} with respect to the zero-damage condition occur, with $O(10^{-2})$. This means that the armor units are not significantly displaced, neither through local rotations, nor by translation, thus determining the existence of a static equilibrium. Configuration CS of section no. 40 shows the above-described behavior (see Figure 3.44b).

Figure 3.44 Evolution of the ratio between the spectral wavelength of the micro-roughness λ_m and the median nominal diameter of the armor units D_{n50} referred to the zero-damage condition as a function of the damage parameter N_{od} : (a) configuration with the existing armor layer; (b) SS upgraded configurations; (c) NSS upgraded configurations. The limit $N_{od} = 0.5$ is the reference damage level used for the identification of different damage mechanisms. Data refer to cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023a).

The second case corresponds to those configurations characterized by small values of the damage parameter N_{od} but significant oscillation of the variation of λ_m/D_{n50} with respect to the zero-damage condition, $O(10^{-1})$. In this case the armor units locally rotate, but maintaining their original mean position, thus determining the existence of a dynamic equilibrium. Results indicate that configurations E, EM and CS of section no. 10 and EM and CM of section no. 40 (see Figure 3.44a-b) experience a dynamic equilibrium.

In the third case, when the damage parameter N_{od} tends to the intermediate damage level (CIRIA et al., 2007), small oscillations of the variation of λ_m/D_{n50} with respect to the zero-damage condition, $O(10^{-2})$, are recorded. The damage occurs through a bulk sliding of the armor blocks, which does not cause the widening neither the narrowing of the spaces between the units. In the present tests, configuration CM of section n. 10 and E of section no. 40 (see Figure 3.44a and c) approaches the intermediate damage level (CIRIA et al., 2007) through a mass sliding.

The fourth behavior corresponds to those configurations characterized by values of the damage parameter N_{od} close to the failure level (CIRIA et al., 2007) and also by significant oscillations of the variation of λ_m/D_{n50} with respect to the zero-damage condition, $O(10^{-1})$. Such a case corresponds to differential block displacements, which involve a clear change of the armor layer porosity. The damage progression of configurations AD and AS of section no. 40 follows the above-described dynamics (see Figure 3.44b).

It is important to point out that the same configuration could experience more than one behavior during the damage process. For instance, during the initial shakedown configuration AD of section no. 10 (see Figure 3.44c) reaches the failure threshold without variation of λ_m/D_{n50} , i.e. with an overall sliding of the armor blocks. After the initial shakedown, the damage develops with a significantly changing λ_m/D_{n50} , which means that the armor units change their

relative position. The damage progression of configuration AS of section no. 10 follows the opposite process. Table 3.XX summarizes the outcomes of the analysis of the armor layer microroughness for each tested configuration.

Therefore, it seems that the variation of λ_m/D_{n50} with respect to the zero-damage condition may be a useful parameter for the investigation of the way in which the armor layer damage quantified by traditional parameters (e.g. N_{od}) physically develops during increasing wave loads. In addition, the proposed technique allows us the automatic identification of small displacements of the units, and hence a more accurate diagnosis of the initiation of damage.

Table 3.XX Summary of the armor layer damage dynamics derived from the analysis of the armor layer microroughness for each tested configuration. Phases 1 and 2 refer to the damage processes respectively during and after the initial shakedown. Data refer to cross-sections no. 10 and no. 40.

Phase 1 \ Phase 2	Static equilibrium	Dynamic equilibrium	Bulk displacement	Differential displacement
Static equilibrium	Section no. 40 - CS			
Dynamic equilibrium		Section n. 10 - E Section n. 10 - EM Section n. 10 - CS Section n. 40 - EM Section n. 40 - CM		
Bulk displacement			Section n. 10 - CM Section n. 40 - E	Section n. 10 - AD
Differential displacement			Section n. 10 - AS	Section n. 40 - AS Section n. 40 - AD

Wave overtopping

The mean wave overtopping discharge (q) has been measured during each test. Table 3.XXI, Table 3.XXII, Table 3.XXIII, Table 3.XXIV, Table 3.XXV, Table 3.XXVI, and Table 3.XXVII report the non-dimensional mean overtopping discharge per meter q^* ($= q/\sqrt{g H_s^3}$) calculated for each experiment as a function of the ratio R_c/H_s . It should be noted that in some cases it was not possible to record q due to malfunctioning of the measurement system.

Table 3.XXI Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 10, configurations E, EM and AS (ND= no data).

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	1.79	$2.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.09	$8.69 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.97	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.79	$1.32 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.03	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.96	$8.88 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	ND	ND	2.06	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.84	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$
II	1	ND	ND	1.85	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.63	$9.87 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.53	$2.76 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.80	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.64	$-2.42 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.59	$4.69 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.75	$1.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ND	ND
III	1	1.39	$8.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.56	$2.31 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.46	$6.84 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.38	$7.17 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.56	$2.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.54	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	ND	ND	1.55	$2.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.45	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-5}$
IV	1	1.24	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.45	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.29	$7.06 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.23	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.38	$4.09 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.27	$1.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.34	$3.47 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	1.10	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	1.14	$1.97 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	ND	ND	-	-	-	-
V	1	1.08	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.17	$4.19 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.12	$3.99 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.05	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.17	$4.82 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.13	$5.40 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.11	$8.43 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ND	ND	1.13	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	1 SLR	1.09	$3.19 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	1.01	$8.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	1.00	$9.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-	-

Table 3.XXII Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 10, configurations AD, CM and CS (ND= no data).

Wave ID	Test	AD		CM		CS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	ND	ND	1.91	$3.16 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-	.
	2	1.83	$3.67 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.89	$3.67 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.80	$8.05 \cdot 10^{-7}$
	3	1.82	$4.46 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.95	$4.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.79	$1.69 \cdot 10^{-6}$
II	1	ND	ND	1.70	$2.67 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.76	$3.61 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.66	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-6}$	ND	ND	1.74	$3.52 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.73	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.63	$3.72 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.74	$3.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
III	1	1.47	$1.80 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.48	$8.92 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.58	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.46	$1.84 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.42	$7.06 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.55	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.46	$7.10 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.47	$5.51 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.53	$4.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$
IV	1	1.37	$8.77 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.31	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.38	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	ND	ND	1.31	$2.20 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.36	$7.41 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.34	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.28	$2.78 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.38	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	1	1.12	$5.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.09	$8.04 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.15	$5.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.11	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.11	$9.47 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.14	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.13	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.11	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.15	$2.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3.XXIII Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 17, configuration AS (ND= no data).

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	1.76	$5.73 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.76	$3.30 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.79	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-6}$
II	1	1.65	$6.34 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.64	$2.44 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.54	$2.76 \cdot 10^{-6}$
III	1	1.44	$6.57 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.43	$2.39 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.47	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$
IV	1	1.39	$2.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.33	$1.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.36	$8.08 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	1.17	$4.47 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.12	$6.76 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.15	$4.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XXIV Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 21, configurations AS (ND= no data).

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	1.74	$4.87 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.77	$5.00 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.72	$3.10 \cdot 10^{-6}$
II	1	1.68	$6.26 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	ND	ND
	3	1.70	$5.31 \cdot 10^{-6}$
III	1	1.50	$9.31 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.43	$4.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.44	$8.01 \cdot 10^{-6}$
IV	1	1.26	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.25	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.24	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	1.05	$4.31 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.07	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	1.04	$3.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XXV Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 34, configurations AS.

Wave ID	Test	AS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	1.71	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.84	$1.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.68	$1.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$
II	1	1.72	$4.18 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.68	$3.17 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.64	$2.58 \cdot 10^{-5}$
III	1	1.34	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.33	$2.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.35	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$
IV	1	1.23	$4.62 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.25	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.30	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-
V	1	1.08	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.16	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.18	$1.34 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-

Table 3.XXVI Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 40, configurations E, EM and AS.

Wave ID	Test	E		EM		AS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	1.52	$4.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.78	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.31	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.62	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.73	$2.88 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.33	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.68	$2.57 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.77	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.32	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-6}$
II	1	1.61	$3.26 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.82	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.31	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.51	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.80	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.33	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	1.51	$2.92 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.83	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.31	$2.43 \cdot 10^{-6}$
III	1	1.23	$4.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.52	$4.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.31	$1.53 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.27	$2.60 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.43	$3.53 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.25	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	ND	ND	1.50	$6.43 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.27	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-6}$
IV	1	1.15	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.25	$7.88 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.49	$7.12 \cdot 10^{-7}$
	2	ND	ND	1.28	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.46	$9.65 \cdot 10^{-7}$
	3	1.16	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.24	$8.52 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.17	$5.66 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	1 SLR	1.06	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	1.06	$3.22 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	1.01	$4.19 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-
V	1	ND	ND	1.22	$6.99 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.14	$6.00 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	2	1.09	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.22	$7.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.13	$5.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	3	ND	ND	1.20	$7.63 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.06	$4.49 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	0.96	$4.25 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	0.97	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-

	3 SLR	0.95	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	-	-
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Table 3.XXVII Mean overtopping discharge and ratio R_c/H_s for each tested configuration of the upgraded Catania harbor breakwater: cross-section no. 40, configurations AD, CM and CS (ND= no data).

Wave ID	Test	AD		CM		CS	
		R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*	R_c/H_s	q^*
I	1	ND	ND	1.71	$7.49 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.82	$3.43 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.62	$5.99 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.69	$8.08 \cdot 10^{-7}$	1.80	$2.88 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.62	$5.43 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.66	$6.26 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.77	$3.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$
II	1	1.64	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.63	$6.31 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.80	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	ND	ND	1.73	$5.36 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.76	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.61	$7.25 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.74	$3.86 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.72	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-5}$
III	1	1.30	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.35	$2.41 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.40	$3.89 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	ND	ND	1.28	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.52	$6.12 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.31	$9.53 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.35	$2.21 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.45	$2.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$
IV	1	ND	ND	1.20	$7.34 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.31	$6.78 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.13	$3.47 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ND	ND	1.37	$6.22 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	3	1.14	$5.10 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.18	$7.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.34	$7.41 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	1 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
V	1	1.07	$3.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.13	$7.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.22	$9.44 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	2	1.08	$3.12 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ND	ND	1.22	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	1.05	$3.32 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ND	ND	1.24	$1.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	1 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3 SLR	-	-	-	-	-	-

The validation of the experimental data on mean overtopping discharge has been performed through the comparison with the following empirical relationship, which is valid for seaside slopes between 1:2 and 1:4/3 and wave attack orthogonal to the breakwater (EurOtop, 2018):

$$q^* = \frac{q}{\sqrt{g} H_s^3} = a_E \exp \left[- \left(b_E \frac{R_c}{H_s \gamma_f} \right)^{1.3} \right] \quad (3.11)$$

where q^* is the mean overtopping discharge per meter, q , normalized with respect to the square root of the product between the gravitational acceleration g and the cube of the incident significant wave height H_s ; a_E and b_E are the empirical parameters of the formula, respectively equal to 0.09 with a standard deviation of 0.0135 and 1.50 with a standard deviation of 0.1500; R_c is the maximum value between the crest level and the wave wall height referred to mean sea level, and γ_f is the roughness factor (0.50 for Antifer blocks, 0.47 for double layer of artificial cubes).

Figure 3.45 shows the comparison between the experimental q^* as a function of R_c/H_s and Eq. (3.11), distinguishing the upgrading options with simple heightening of the wave wall from the ones that introduce also an additional armor layer made up of Antifer units smaller than the existing cubes or cubes equal to the existing one. The measured q^* is in good agreement with

the prediction of the EurOtop (2018) formula for the configuration with the existing armor layer (see Figure 3.45a) with additional cubes equal to the existing ones (see Figure 3.45c). On the contrary, Figure 3.45b shows that the values of q^* found for the configurations with additional Antifer units smaller than the existing cubes are in general lower than the prediction of EurOtop (2018). Such a lack of agreement between experimental data and the formula proposed by EurOtop (2018) may be due to the unusual placement of smaller armor units over the existing ones, whose reciprocal interaction could produce additional dissipation processed and hence reduce overtopping discharges.

As regards the effects of climate change, Figure 3.46a, which shows the increase of the overtopping rate of configuration E caused by SLR (Δq_{SLR}), highlights that SLR induced a significant enhancement of the overtopping phenomenon. Indeed, the mean overtopping discharges of configuration E corresponding to waves III and IV (i.e. to return periods equal to 50 and 100 years) rise by a factor of 7 – 9 and 2 – 4 respectively. The hydraulic performances of section n. 40 are less affected by the effects of SLR than those of section n. 10. Such a result is due to the fact that section n. 40 is more offshore, i.e. in deeper water than section n.10 (see Figure 3.13), and hence subject to waves less influenced by mean sea level variations. However, considering the results relative to both sections, the upgrade of existing armor layer is needed to ensure hydraulic responses able to withstand the future intensification of the overtopping phenomenon.

Figure 3.45 shows that, as expected, configurations E and EM are subject to the higher overtopping rates. Indeed, such options consist only in the heightening of the wave wall. On the contrary, all the other solutions involve the improvement of the hydraulic performances thanks to the addition of an extra armor layer.

Figure 3.45 Comparison between the empirical formula suggested by EurOtop (2018) and the experimental data on dimensionless mean overtopping discharge (q^*), expressed as a function of R_c/H_s : (a) upgrading options with simple raising of the wave wall; (b) upgrading options with raising of the wave wall and additional Antifer units smaller than the existing cubes; (c) upgrading options with raising of the wave wall and additional cubic units equal to the existing ones. The dotted lines indicate the 95% confidence bounds of the EurOtop (2018) formula.

Figure 3.46 Experimental results on mean overtopping discharge: (a) increase of the 50 and 100 years return period (respectively wave III and wave IV) overtopping rate of configuration E caused by SLR (Δq_{SLR}); (b) averaged reduction of the 100 years return period (i.e. wave IV) mean overtopping discharge with respect to configuration E (Δq_{E-}) performed by configurations EM, AS, AD, CM and CS.

Figure 3.46b shows the calculated Δq_{E-} , which is the averaged decrease of the mean overtopping discharge to wave III and IV (i.e. return period equal to 50 and 100 years) operated by configurations EM, AS, AD, CM and CS with respect to configuration E. The heightening of the wall up to +9.50 m above MSL gives significantly different overtopping reductions, i.e. Δq_{E-} respectively equal to 63% and 10% for section n. 10 and 540. Such discrepancy leads to the conclusion that the heightening of the wave wall by only one meter for the reduction of the overtopping discharge is less efficient for the most offshore section n. 40, which is subject to higher waves. With reference to those configurations which improve option E only thanks to the addition of an extra armor layer (i.e. AS, AD and CM), Δq_{E-} between 75 – 85% and 45 – 95% is observed, for section n.10 and n.40 respectively. Finally, solution CS improves configuration E thanks to the heightening of the wall by one meter and the addition of extra armor blocks, giving Δq_{E-} equal to 88% and 30% for section n. 10 and n. 40 respectively.

The choice of the best upgrading solutions with the additional armor layer cannot be based on the analysis of the overtopping phenomena. Indeed, all the tested configurations with additional armor units (i.e. AS and AD; CM and CS) guarantee sufficiently high Δq_{E-} , i.e. not lower than 30% regardless of the type of employed blocks (i.e. Antifer units smaller than the existing cubes or cubic units equal to the existing ones) and of the considered cross section geometry and position. Consequently, the structural behavior of upgrading solutions should be considered as the main factor for the selection of the overall most performing ones. Therefore, for the case of the Catania harbor breakwater, the most appropriate configuration seems to be the one that is designed using additional 62 t cubes placed following a 1:2 slope over the regularized existing armor, with a quarry stone toe berm, a wave wall raised up to +9.50 m above MSL (i.e. configuration CS).

3.2.2 Numerical dataset acquired by UniCT

This section presents the numerical dataset on existing and upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters obtained by UniCT through the numerical model IH2VOF. A portion of the data was previously published by Stagnitti et al. (2023b), whereas the remaining data were obtained within the framework of the PROMETEO Project.

Description of the numerical model

The hydraulic behavior of damaged and upgraded rubble mound breakwater was investigated by using the two-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model IH2VOF (Lara et al., 2011a, b). IH2VOF solves the 2D RANS equations, based on the decomposition of the

instantaneous velocity and pressure fields into their mean and turbulent components (Lara et al., 2011a, b). Under this assumption, the RANS equations can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (3.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + g_i + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{\tau}_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \overline{u'_i u'_j}}{\partial x_j} \quad (3.13)$$

where $u_i = \bar{u}_i + u'_i$ and $p = \bar{p} + p'$ are respectively the Reynolds decomposed velocity and pressure fields, ρ is the density of the fluid, g_i is the i -th component of the gravitational acceleration and $\bar{\tau}_{ij}$ is the mean viscous stress tensor. The mean flow characteristics for turbulent conditions are calculated by solving the $k - \varepsilon$ model, in which the coefficients proposed by Lin (1998) and Rodi (1993) are employed.

The flow inside the porous media is modeled by means of the VARANS equations, which are obtained by applying the intrinsic volume average to the RANS equations and combined with the Forchheimer's relationship (Liu et al., 1999):

$$\frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (3.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle \langle \bar{u}_j \rangle}{\partial x_j} = & -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{p} \rangle}{\partial x_i} + g_i + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{\tau}_{ij} \rangle}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \langle \overline{u'_i u'_j} \rangle}{\partial x_j} - \\ & \left[\frac{\alpha_F v (1-n)^2}{n^2 D_{n50}^2} \right] \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle + \frac{\beta_F (1-n)}{n D_{n50}} \sqrt{\langle \bar{u}_1 \rangle^2 + \langle \bar{u}_2 \rangle^2} \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle + c_F \frac{1-n}{n} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial t} \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

where v is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid, D_{n50} and n are respectively the median nominal diameter and the porosity of the porous media, α_F and β_F are two empirical coefficients associated with the linear and nonlinear porous drag force respectively and c_F is the empirical parameter of the added mass coefficient, equal to 0.34. The coefficients α_F and β_F depend on several parameters, linked to both flow and structure characteristics. Since an accurate description of such dependencies is still not available for oscillatory flows, the best-fit values for α_F and β_F should be evaluated by comparing experimental data and numerical results (Losada et al., 2008).

The RANS, VARANS and $k - \varepsilon$ equations are all solved using the finite differences two-steps projection method (Chorin, 1968, 1969). The computational domain is discretized in rectangular cells, whose dimension can be uniform or different for each sub-region of the numerical channel. The movement of free surface is tracked by a VOF method. In addition, the insertion of solid boundaries of arbitrary shape in the computational domain can be performed through a partial cell treatment (Lara et al., 2011b).

Still water is the model initial condition for the mean flow in the whole domain, although specific form for the free surface displacements or mean velocity field can be introduced. As regard turbulence, nonzero initial values are generated using a chosen seed. At solid walls no slip or

free slip boundary conditions can be used, whereas at the free surface the stress, pressure and gradients of turbulent energy (k) and dissipation (ε) are set equal to zero. Moreover, the open boundary condition can be employed to allow two-way flow, by defining free pressure and velocity. As regards the wave generation, three procedures are included in the model, i.e. internal wavemaker, static wave paddle (i.e. Dirichlet boundary condition) and dynamic wave paddle (i.e. moving boundary condition). Finally, wave absorption boundary conditions are available, which allow to run longer simulations, avoiding most of the effects of reflected waves inside the numerical flume. In particular, the active wave absorption can be applied to both the Dirichlet and the moving boundary conditions, whereas a sponge layer can be placed on the opposite side of the flume for passive absorption.

Dataset on wave overtopping of rubble-mound breakwaters by Stagnitti et al. (2023b)

Numerical model setup and simulations

Two-dimensional simulations were carried out inside a numerical wave channel, whose height and length were fixed considering the dimension of the structure to be tested, which is about 1.60 m wide and 0.40 m high, and also the hydrodynamic conditions to simulate. Sea state W4 (see Table 3.XXVIII) was used as reference for the preliminary definition of the total length of the channel and of the numerical grid. In particular, the length of the numerical domain was set equal to the structure length plus one deep-water wavelength ($L_0 = gT_p^2/2\pi$), i.e. 4.50 m, which was preliminary demonstrated to ensure the development of the wave motion with limited numerical dissipation and computational costs. The height of the domain was fixed equal to 0.65 m (i.e. the height of the structure plus 0.25 m), in order to avoid the influence of the top boundary on the wave overtopping phenomena.

Figure 3.47 shows a sketch of the numerical wave flume, the reference system, and the position of the free surface elevation and velocity gauges: (i) gauge no. 1 was placed one meter after the origin of the domain, in order to monitor waves close to generation area; (ii) gauges no. 2, 3, 4 and 5 were located following the same arrangement of the lab tests for the evaluation of the reflection coefficient according to the four gauge method proposed by Faraci et al. (2015); (iii) gauge no. 6 was positioned at the toe of the structure; (iv) gauge no. 7 was placed in the correspondence of the wave wall, in order to measure the overtopping waves. The Dirichlet boundary condition was employed to generate irregular wave series using JONSWAP spectra. Moreover, active and passive wave absorption was applied to reduce wave reflection inside the flume.

The grid used to discretize the numerical domain was made of uniform rectangular cells having $\Delta x = 0.020$ m and $\Delta y = 0.010$ m. These dimensions ensure the aspect ratio (i.e. $\Delta x/\Delta y$) equal to 2, as well as at least 10 cells per wave height along the vertical direction, respectively. The domain contains a total of 226 and 66 cells along the x and y directions, respectively. The time step is dynamically adjusted during the simulations depending on the Courant number, Δt ranging between 0.02 s to 0.06 s. The numerical output data of the wave and velocity gauges is re-sampled at 30 Hz by linear interpolation. Using a processor Intel Xeon Silver 4214 2.20 GHz, about 250 waves were reproduced every thirty minutes.

Table 3.XXVIII Characteristics of the experimental incident wave motion used to calibrate the numerical model. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Sea state ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	N_w [no. of waves]	No. of simulations
W1	0.075	1.18	0.270	1500	3
W2	0.071	1.24	0.270	1500	3
W3	0.093	1.27	0.270	1500	3
W4	0.100	1.27	0.270	1500	3
W5	0.109	1.43	0.270	1500	3

About 80 simulations were run to calibrate the porosity parameters of equation (3.15) for each layer of the rubble-mound structure, using as benchmark the experimental results on wave reflection and overtopping described in section 3.2.1 with reference to configurations E and CS of cross-section no. 40 of the Catania harbor breakwater. The five experimental wave conditions summarized in Table 3.XXVIII, which corresponds to the input experimental conditions reported in

Table 3.VII, were reproduced. Parameters α_F and c_F of equation (3.15) were fixed respectively equal to 200 and 0.34, according to Lara et al. (2008). Instead, the values of n and β_F were deduced from the comparison between preliminary numerical k_r and q^* and the corresponding experimental values, as described by Stagnitti et al. (2023b). Table 3.XXIX summarizes the values of the porosity parameters of each layer of the rubble-mound structure.

The calibrated numerical model was employed to further extend the wave overtopping experimental database described in section 3.2.1, and to perform an in-depth investigation on the hydraulic response of damage and upgraded structures. Table 3.XXX reports the reference sea states used for the definition of the input hydrodynamic conditions, in terms of significant wave height, peak wave period, water depth and number of waves, which corresponds to $\xi_{m-1,0}$ ranging between 2.16 and 3.15. All the sea states reported in Table 3.XXX were reproduced, also considering variations of the water depth and of the peak wave period equal to ± 0.020 m and ± 0.20 s, respectively. For each input sea state, six realizations have been generated, to analyze the effects on overtopping phenomena due to: wave-wave interaction; influence of wave sequence; the ratio between the maximum and the significant wave height of the wave height of the series (H_{max}/H_s). Table 3.XXXI summarizes the performed simulations, in terms of input sea state, tested structure and number of realizations with different seedings for the random wave generations. A total of 300 simulations were performed, which allowed the analysis of the wave overtopping phenomena for both the existing and upgraded structures.

Figure 3.47 Sketch of the numerical domain and location of the free surface and velocity gauges. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Table 3.XXIX Characteristics of the porous layers of the tested structures. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Layer	D_{n50} [m]	n [-]	α_F [-]	β_F [-]	c_F [-]
Core	0.009	0.32	200	1.20	0.34
Filter	0.017	0.35	200	2.00	0.34
Existing armor layer	0.059	0.30	200	1.50	0.34
Additional armor layer	0.059	0.25	200	5.00	0.34
Toe berm	0.017	0.35	200	3.00	0.34

Table 3.XXX Reference sea states used for the definition of the input hydrodynamics of the numerical simulations. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Sea state ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	h [m]	N_w [n. of waves]
NW1	0.075	1.18	0.270	1500
NW2	0.071	1.24	0.270	1500
NW3	0.093	1.27	0.270	1500
NW4	0.100	1.27	0.270	1500
NW5	0.109	1.43	0.270	1500
NW6	0.095	1.30	0.270	1500
NW7	0.105	1.30	0.270	1500
NW8	0.120	1.30	0.270	1500

Table 3.XXXI Summary of the input hydrodynamics of the performed simulations. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Sea state	Configuration	N. of realizations
NW1-5	E	6
NW1-5 with $h + 0.020$ m	E	6
NW1-5 with $h + 0.020$ m	E	6
NW1-5 with $T_p + 0.020$ m	E	6
NW1-5 with $T_p + 0.020$ m	E	6
NW4-8	CS	6
NW4-8 with $h + 0.020$ m	CS	6
NW4-8 with $h + 0.020$ m	CS	6
NW4-8 with $T_p + 0.020$ m	CS	6
NW4-8 with $T_p + 0.020$ m	CS	6

Analysis of the numerical results

Besides the mean wave overtopping discharge, which was measured also during the experimental campaign, the probability of wave overtopping (P_o) was evaluated. Moreover, parameters describing the individual wave overtopping volumes distribution, such as the maximum overtopping volume (V_{max}), were calculated for each simulated sea state. The outputs of the numerical simulations are summarized from Table 3.XXXII to Table 3.XXXVII.

Table 3.XXXII Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration E (part I).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW1	1	0.07	1.16	2.66	1.58	0.59	0.24	$1.83 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.07	1.08	2.62	1.57	0.60	0.23	$2.89 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.21 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.07	1.13	2.68	1.63	0.61	0.22	$2.29 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.07	1.16	2.69	1.66	0.62	0.24	$3.39 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.07	1.23	2.64	1.59	0.60	0.23	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	1.15	2.66	1.62	0.61	0.22	$4.42 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
NW2	1	0.06	1.29	2.9	1.78	0.61	0.26	$2.90 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.26 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	2	0.07	1.25	2.83	1.7	0.60	0.25	$1.32 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	3	0.07	1.25	2.78	1.61	0.58	0.25	$2.82 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.22 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.07	1.35	2.79	1.62	0.58	0.25	$1.86 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.06	1.2	2.86	1.78	0.62	0.25	$1.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	1.2	2.82	1.66	0.59	0.24	$1.47 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.27 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW3	1	0.08	1.25	2.58	1.37	0.53	0.26	$3.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.68 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.88 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.26	2.53	1.31	0.52	0.25	$3.14 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.16	2.55	1.34	0.53	0.25	$3.79 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.39 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.19	2.54	1.35	0.53	0.25	$3.99 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.91 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.23	2.51	1.32	0.53	0.25	$3.65 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.28	2.55	1.30	0.51	0.26	$3.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.20 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.84 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW4	1	0.09	1.20	2.49	1.26	0.51	0.25	$5.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.73 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.33	2.52	1.25	0.50	0.26	$5.20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.65 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.64 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.28	2.5	1.27	0.51	0.26	$4.61 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.33	1.15	0.49	0.25	$5.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.48 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.25	2.42	1.21	0.50	0.26	$5.84 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.16 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.17	2.42	1.24	0.51	0.26	$4.24 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.65 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.88 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW5	1	0.09	1.31	2.65	1.22	0.46	0.31	$2.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.23 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.34	2.56	1.16	0.45	0.29	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.12 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	3	0.11	1.46	2.49	1.08	0.43	0.3	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.88 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.01 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.46	2.59	1.19	0.46	0.3	$2.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$8.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.51	1.12	0.45	0.29	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.30 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.62	1.17	0.45	0.31	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW1 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.07	1.24	2.68	1.31	0.49	0.24	$2.97 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.01 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.07	1.08	2.61	1.29	0.49	0.22	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.07	1.13	2.67	1.35	0.50	0.21	$3.31 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.74 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.07	1.16	2.69	1.37	0.51	0.23	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.07	1.23	2.65	1.31	0.49	0.22	$3.09 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.50 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.07	1.15	2.67	1.35	0.50	0.21	$3.17 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.11 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW2 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.06	1.29	2.91	1.47	0.51	0.25	$4.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.51 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.07	1.25	2.82	1.41	0.50	0.24	$2.66 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.07	1.25	2.79	1.33	0.48	0.24	$3.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.68 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.07	1.27	2.81	1.35	0.48	0.24	$4.24 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.88 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.06	1.20	2.86	1.47	0.51	0.24	$3.37 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.51 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.07	1.20	2.83	1.37	0.48	0.24	$2.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.83 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW3 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.08	1.31	2.6	1.14	0.44	0.26	$2.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.32 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.38 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.26	2.53	1.07	0.42	0.25	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.16	2.55	1.11	0.43	0.25	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.57 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.19	2.55	1.11	0.43	0.26	$2.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.82 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.15 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.23	2.5	1.08	0.43	0.26	$2.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.09 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.28	2.55	1.07	0.42	0.26	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.76 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	2	0.09	1.33	2.51	1.02	0.41	0.26	$3.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$9.54 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.28	2.5	1.05	0.42	0.25	$2.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$7.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.XXXIII Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration E (part II).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW4 $h+0.02$ m	3	0.09	1.28	2.5	1.05	0.42	0.25	$2.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$7.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.33	0.94	0.40	0.25	$2.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	5	0.10	1.25	2.43	0.99	0.41	0.26	$3.05 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.64 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.17	2.42	1.01	0.42	0.26	$2.85 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-2}$
NW5 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.31	2.65	1.00	0.38	0.32	$6.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.06 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	2	0.10	1.32	2.53	0.94	0.37	0.30	$5.84 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.03 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	3	0.11	1.46	2.51	0.89	0.35	0.31	$5.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.07 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	4	0.10	1.46	2.6	0.98	0.38	0.31	$6.72 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.52	0.92	0.37	0.30	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.96 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.61	0.96	0.37	0.33	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.88 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-2}$
NW1 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.07	1.16	2.68	1.87	0.7	0.22	1.87	0.00	0.00
	2	0.07	1.08	2.63	1.87	0.71	0.21	1.87	$6.04 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.07 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.07	1.13	2.69	1.92	0.71	0.2	1.92	0.00	0.00
	4	0.07	1.16	2.69	1.95	0.72	0.21	1.95	0.00	0.00
	5	0.07	1.34	2.67	1.89	0.71	0.21	1.89	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	1.15	2.67	1.92	0.72	0.2	1.92	0.00	0.00
NW2 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.06	1.29	2.91	2.1	0.72	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.07	1.25	2.82	2.0	0.71	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.07	1.25	2.77	1.89	0.68	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.07	1.35	2.81	1.92	0.68	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.06	1.2	2.86	2.10	0.73	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	1.2	2.81	1.95	0.69	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW3 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.08	1.31	2.62	1.64	0.63	0.24	$9.44 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.26	2.54	1.54	0.61	0.23	$9.11 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.08	1.16	2.57	1.60	0.62	0.23	$6.39 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	4	0.08	1.19	2.57	1.60	0.62	0.23	$4.48 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.23	2.51	1.56	0.62	0.23	$9.14 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.28	2.56	1.54	0.60	0.24	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.14 \cdot 10^{-4}$
NW4 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.2	2.51	1.51	0.60	0.23	$2.47 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.33	2.54	1.49	0.59	0.23	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.66 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.09	1.28	2.51	1.51	0.60	0.24	$1.10 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.49 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.35	1.37	0.58	0.23	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.25	2.44	1.44	0.59	0.24	$1.82 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.45 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.29 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	6	0.09	1.17	2.42	1.48	0.61	0.24	$3.14 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
NW5 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.31	2.66	1.44	0.54	0.29	$1.84 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.32	2.55	1.37	0.54	0.27	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.33 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.46	2.49	1.28	0.51	0.28	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.51 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.46	2.59	1.41	0.54	0.28	$2.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.52	1.33	0.53	0.26	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.64	1.40	0.53	0.30	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.49 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.26 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW1 $T_p+0.2$ s	1	0.07	1.26	2.93	1.62	0.55	0.29	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.76 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.08	1.34	2.86	1.53	0.53	0.29	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.07	1.41	3.03	1.60	0.53	0.31	$1.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.08	1.34	2.82	1.42	0.50	0.30	$7.83 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.09 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.07	1.30	2.93	1.60	0.54	0.29	$5.49 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.72 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.07	1.50	2.93	1.58	0.54	0.28	$1.08 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.33 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW2 $T_p+0.2$ s	1	0.07	1.4	3.13	1.65	0.53	0.33	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.95 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.07	1.45	3.07	1.61	0.52	0.30	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.07	1.43	3.1	1.61	0.52	0.32	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.07	1.40	3.15	1.72	0.55	0.32	$4.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.81 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.XXXIV Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration E (part III).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW2 $T_p+0.2s$	5	0.07	1.49	3.14	1.63	0.52	0.31	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.99 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.07	1.38	3.06	1.55	0.51	0.32	$6.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.83 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW3 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.09	1.40	2.79	1.33	0.48	0.32	$7.73 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.11 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.40	2.80	1.29	0.46	0.32	$9.19 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.45	2.80	1.30	0.46	0.31	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.49	2.69	1.24	0.46	0.32	$8.15 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.39 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.05 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.47	2.75	1.27	0.46	0.32	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.99 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.91 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.45	2.75	1.27	0.46	0.31	$9.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.23 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW4 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.09	1.52	2.79	1.30	0.47	0.32	$1.49 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.39 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.34	2.59	1.17	0.45	0.30	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.36 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.81 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.43	2.58	1.15	0.45	0.3	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.66 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.16 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.45	2.7	1.21	0.45	0.31	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.10	1.47	2.62	1.16	0.44	0.32	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.42 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.5	2.73	1.21	0.44	0.31	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.89 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW5 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.10	1.61	2.87	1.18	0.41	0.35	$3.55 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.53 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	2	0.10	1.57	2.8	1.15	0.41	0.34	$3.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.39 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	3	0.10	1.59	2.78	1.12	0.40	0.34	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	4	0.10	1.67	2.79	1.10	0.40	0.36	$3.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.67 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.45 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	5	0.11	1.69	2.76	1.06	0.38	0.36	$3.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	6	0.11	1.57	2.78	1.08	0.39	0.35	$3.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-2}$
NW1 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.07	1.00	2.34	1.69	0.72	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.07	0.97	2.3	1.67	0.72	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.07	1.00	2.35	1.74	0.74	0.21	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	4	0.07	0.93	2.33	1.67	0.72	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.07	1.02	2.31	1.67	0.72	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	0.96	2.32	1.69	0.73	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW2 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.07	1.10	2.46	1.68	0.68	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.06	0.96	2.48	1.80	0.73	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.07	1.00	2.42	1.68	0.69	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.06	1.04	2.48	1.77	0.72	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.07	1.05	2.46	1.76	0.72	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.07	1.03	2.45	1.68	0.69	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW3 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.09	1.08	2.26	1.33	0.59	0.20	$4.89 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	2	0.08	1.06	2.30	1.41	0.61	0.20	$7.85 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	3	0.08	1.05	2.35	1.47	0.63	0.21	$2.63 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.09	1.09	2.26	1.34	0.59	0.19	$7.34 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.10	2.27	1.34	0.59	0.20	$1.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.65 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	6	0.09	1.03	2.24	1.32	0.59	0.19	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.61 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-4}$
NW4 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.09	1.09	2.19	1.24	0.57	0.20	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.68 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	2	0.09	0.99	2.26	1.35	0.60	0.21	$2.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.48 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.09	1.09	2.22	1.29	0.58	0.20	$3.69 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.28 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.09	1.13	2.23	1.28	0.58	0.19	$2.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.59 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	5	0.09	1.02	2.24	1.33	0.59	0.20	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.02	2.22	1.31	0.59	0.21	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.67 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$
NW5 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.10	1.22	2.29	1.14	0.50	0.23	$5.74 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.48 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.10	2.36	1.16	0.49	0.24	$6.30 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.83 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.80 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.15	2.37	1.18	0.50	0.25	$5.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.90 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.25	2.40	1.19	0.50	0.24	$5.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.63 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.81 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.19	2.33	1.13	0.49	0.23	$5.37 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.63 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.39 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.30	2.40	1.22	0.51	0.24	$4.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.94 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.XXXV Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration CS (part I).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW7	1	0.09	1.26	2.50	1.44	0.58	0.28	$2.64 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.38 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.28	2.52	1.45	0.58	0.29	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.09	1.28	2.52	1.45	0.58	0.29	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.34	1.3	0.55	0.28	$3.68 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.25	2.44	1.37	0.56	0.28	$8.52 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.48 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	6	0.09	1.23	2.44	1.41	0.58	0.29	$2.51 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.45 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.81 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW5	1	0.09	1.31	2.67	1.37	0.51	0.32	$2.79 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.32	2.56	1.31	0.51	0.31	$2.26 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.08 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.46	2.5	1.22	0.49	0.31	$2.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.48 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.46	2.6	1.35	0.52	0.31	$3.09 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.66 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.53	1.27	0.50	0.30	$2.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.62	1.32	0.50	0.33	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW6	1	0.09	1.26	2.56	1.46	0.57	0.28	$3.19 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.30	2.53	1.43	0.56	0.29	$1.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.55 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.09	1.32	2.54	1.43	0.56	0.28	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.99 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.31	2.50	1.37	0.55	0.29	$5.69 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.40	2.55	1.41	0.55	0.30	$1.04 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.61 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.08	1.28	2.63	1.52	0.58	0.29	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
NW7	1	0.09	1.36	2.47	1.37	0.55	0.29	$7.44 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.66 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.26	2.52	1.40	0.56	0.29	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.26	2.46	1.32	0.53	0.29	$5.56 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.21	2.49	1.37	0.55	0.30	$8.62 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.68 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.82 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	5	0.10	1.31	2.44	1.33	0.55	0.29	$7.93 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.32	2.46	1.33	0.54	0.28	$2.91 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW8	1	0.11	1.26	2.33	1.19	0.51	0.27	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.40	2.38	1.27	0.53	0.28	$1.97 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.24	2.33	1.22	0.52	0.28	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.64 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.91 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.35	2.39	1.25	0.52	0.28	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.37 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.21	2.37	1.23	0.52	0.27	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.11	1.30	2.33	1.18	0.50	0.28	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.42 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW4 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.20	2.50	1.21	0.48	0.27	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.33	2.52	1.19	0.47	0.29	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.77 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.52 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.28	2.51	1.22	0.48	0.28	$2.21 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.04 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.55 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.34	1.09	0.47	0.28	$2.57 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.25	2.44	1.15	0.47	0.28	$3.12 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.23	2.43	1.18	0.49	0.29	$2.97 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-2}$
NW5 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.44	2.67	1.15	0.43	0.33	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.49 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.32	2.56	1.10	0.43	0.31	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.46	2.5	1.02	0.41	0.31	$1.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.03 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.46	2.6	1.13	0.44	0.32	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.53	1.06	0.42	0.30	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.06 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.62	1.11	0.42	0.33	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.96 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW6 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.26	2.57	1.23	0.48	0.28	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.58 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.22 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.3	2.53	1.20	0.47	0.29	$2.45 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.85 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.32	2.55	1.20	0.47	0.28	$3.10 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.26 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.31	2.49	1.15	0.46	0.29	$3.19 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.4	2.56	1.19	0.46	0.30	$2.70 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.75 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.08	1.28	2.64	1.29	0.49	0.29	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.26	2.53	1.18	0.47	0.29	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.51 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.26	2.46	1.11	0.45	0.29	$5.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.77 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.XXXVI Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration CS (part II).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW7 $h+0.02$ m	3	0.10	1.26	2.46	1.11	0.45	0.29	$5.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.77 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.21	2.49	1.15	0.46	0.3	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.61 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.25 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.31	2.43	1.11	0.46	0.29	$6.42 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.55 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.32	2.46	1.11	0.45	0.28	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW8 $h+0.02$ m	1	0.11	1.3	2.32	0.99	0.43	0.27	$8.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.30 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	2	0.10	1.4	2.36	1.06	0.45	0.28	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.31 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.93 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.24	2.32	1.01	0.44	0.28	$9.72 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.73 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.35	2.38	1.04	0.44	0.28	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.90 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	5	0.11	1.21	2.34	1.03	0.44	0.27	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.26 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.11	1.3	2.31	0.98	0.42	0.28	$9.21 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.24 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.85 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW4 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.26	2.52	1.68	0.67	0.27	$9.47 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.33	2.55	1.67	0.65	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.09	1.28	2.53	1.68	0.67	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.10	1.21	2.35	1.51	0.64	0.27	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.82 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	5	0.09	1.25	2.44	1.6	0.66	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.23	2.44	1.65	0.68	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW5 with h -0.02 m	1	0.09	1.31	2.67	1.60	0.60	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.10	1.32	2.57	1.53	0.59	0.30	$2.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.46	2.51	1.42	0.57	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.09	1.46	2.60	1.57	0.61	0.31	$4.57 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.36	2.53	1.48	0.59	0.29	$3.01 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.40	2.62	1.55	0.59	0.32	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
NW6 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.26	2.57	1.70	0.66	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.30	2.54	1.65	0.65	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.09	1.32	2.55	1.67	0.65	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.09	1.31	2.5	1.59	0.64	0.28	$6.66 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.40	2.54	1.64	0.64	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.08	1.28	2.64	1.78	0.67	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW7 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.09	1.36	2.48	1.6	0.64	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.26	2.53	1.64	0.65	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.10	1.26	2.47	1.54	0.62	0.28	$2.86 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.11 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.21	2.5	1.59	0.64	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.10	1.31	2.44	1.56	0.64	0.29	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.32	2.46	1.55	0.63	0.28	$5.37 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.00	0.00
NW8 $h-0.02$ m	1	0.11	1.31	2.35	1.39	0.59	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.10	1.4	2.4	1.49	0.62	0.27	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.79 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.10	1.19	2.36	1.44	0.61	0.28	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	4	0.10	1.35	2.41	1.47	0.61	0.27	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.70 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.21	2.4	1.45	0.61	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.11	1.3	2.36	1.39	0.59	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW4 $T_p+0.2$ s	1	0.09	1.52	2.79	1.46	0.63	0.33	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.95 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.34	2.6	1.32	0.67	0.32	$2.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.09 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.37 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.43	2.59	1.3	0.65	0.31	$8.25 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.45	2.71	1.36	0.64	0.32	$2.53 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.76 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.47	2.62	1.30	0.66	0.33	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.68 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.5	2.73	1.36	0.65	0.33	$2.68 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.99 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW5 $T_p+0.2$ s	1	0.10	1.61	2.88	1.34	0.55	0.35	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.23 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.57	2.81	1.29	0.55	0.34	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.02 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.15 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.59	2.78	1.26	0.55	0.33	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.10 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.67	2.79	1.25	0.56	0.34	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Table 3.XXXVII Summary of the output of the numerical simulations presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b): cross-section no. 40, configuration CS (part III).

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/H_s \xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	P_0 [-]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
NW5 $T_p+0.2s$	5	0.11	1.69	2.79	1.20	0.54	0.35	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.47 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.12 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	6	0.11	1.57	2.78	1.22	0.57	0.35	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.32 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$
NW6 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.09	1.53	2.84	1.48	0.64	0.32	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.49 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.09	1.47	2.83	1.44	0.67	0.34	$2.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.09	1.44	2.8	1.46	0.66	0.33	$1.87 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.39 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.54 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.09	1.42	2.87	1.49	0.66	0.33	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.93 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.09	1.41	2.72	1.37	0.64	0.34	$1.80 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.57	2.84	1.42	0.65	0.35	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW7 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.10	1.40	2.67	1.28	0.61	0.33	$4.17 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.10 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.44	2.64	1.30	0.61	0.33	$4.27 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.41 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.10	1.45	2.74	1.33	0.65	0.35	$3.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.64 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.10 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.53	2.57	1.26	0.63	0.32	$4.17 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.40	2.63	1.29	0.61	0.33	$4.51 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.91 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.91 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.53	2.76	1.41	0.63	0.34	$4.59 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.90 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW8 $T_p+0.2s$	1	0.11	1.53	2.50	1.17	0.58	0.33	$9.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.20 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.11	1.57	2.56	1.19	0.59	0.32	$8.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.83 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	3	0.11	1.60	2.60	1.22	0.61	0.33	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.54 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.16 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	4	0.11	1.55	2.61	1.16	0.58	0.33	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.04 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$
	5	0.11	1.55	2.52	1.19	0.60	0.33	$7.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.82 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.10	1.44	2.60	1.27	0.58	0.33	$7.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.19 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NW4 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.09	1.08	2.22	1.40	0.48	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.08	1.11	2.28	1.53	0.47	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.09	1.07	2.25	1.46	0.48	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.09	1.07	2.26	1.44	0.47	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.08	2.28	1.51	0.47	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.07	2.28	1.48	0.49	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW5 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.10	1.22	2.33	1.29	0.43	0.26	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	2	0.10	1.10	2.39	1.31	0.43	0.27	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	3	0.10	1.22	2.41	1.34	0.41	0.28	$4.99 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.39 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	4	0.10	1.25	2.43	1.35	0.44	0.28	$3.12 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.19	2.35	1.27	0.42	0.26	$1.93 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	6	0.09	1.30	2.43	1.39	0.42	0.28	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.79 \cdot 10^{-4}$
NW6 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.08	1.15	2.37	1.52	0.48	0.26	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.08	1.04	2.34	1.56	0.47	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.08	1.08	2.38	1.56	0.47	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.08	1.14	2.36	1.56	0.46	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.10	2.35	1.51	0.46	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.08	2.30	1.49	0.49	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
NW7 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.10	1.16	2.22	1.35	0.47	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.09	1.08	2.31	1.42	0.47	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.09	1.16	2.30	1.49	0.45	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.09	1.05	2.30	1.45	0.46	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00
	5	0.09	1.08	2.25	1.38	0.46	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	6	0.09	1.09	2.28	1.43	0.45	0.23	$5.81 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.00	0.00
NW8 $T_p-0.2s$	1	0.10	1.08	2.16	1.26	0.43	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.10	1.15	2.19	1.29	0.45	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3	0.10	1.08	2.21	1.35	0.44	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4	0.10	1.08	2.21	1.28	0.44	0.24	$8.65 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.93 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	5	0.10	1.05	2.25	1.35	0.44	0.23	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.00	0.00
	6	0.10	1.18	2.21	1.29	0.42	0.24	$6.01 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.00	0.00

The numerical non-dimensional mean wave overtopping discharge q^* ($= q/\sqrt{g H_s^3}$) measured for the existing and upgraded structures were compared with the predictions of the following existing formulas for conventional rubble-mound breakwaters, after verifying that their range of application was consistent with our dataset: (i) the formula proposed by Smolka et al. (2009) for cube- and Cubipod-armored breakwaters; (ii) the formulas developed by Jafari and Etemad-Shahidi (2012) and Etemad-Shahidi and Jafari (2014) using the CLASH dataset (Steendam et al., 2005); (iii) the formula that Molines and Medina (2016) derived from the CLASH Neural Network data (van Gent et al., 2007); (iv) Eq. (5) proposed by EurOtop (2018); (v) the formula proposed by Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2022), which was calibrated on the EurOtop (2018) and Koosheh et al. (2022) databases. The scatter plots in Figure 3.48a–e represent such comparisons. In order to quantify the differences between measured and predicted values, the following statistical error indicators were also calculated (see Table 3.XXXVIII): (i) the normalized bias *NBI* of the logarithm of q^* , which gives indications about the average component of the error and assumes a value close to zero for good simulations; (ii) the correlation coefficient *cor* representing the scatter component of the error, which is smaller when *cor* is closer to one; (iii) the symmetrically normalized root mean square error *HH* (Hanna and Heinold, 1985) of the logarithm of q^* , which combines information about the average and scatter components of the error, with no bias toward simulations that underestimate the average.

Existing prediction formulas considered in Figure 3.48a–d produce an overestimation of numerical q^* lower than 10^{-4} , by more than one order of magnitude when the latter is lower than 10^{-5} . Figure 3.48e shows predictions that overestimate most of the numerical data, i.e. all values of numerical q^* smaller than 7×10^{-4} , by more than one order of magnitude when the latter is smaller than 4×10^{-5} . The above-discussed discrepancies between predictions and observations are probably influenced by the significant uncertainty which characterizes the lowest mean wave overtopping discharges, as well as by the expected worse performance of state-of-the-art formulas for q^* lower than the zero-overtopping limit of the experimental tests. From a practical point of view, the poor correspondence between predicted and observed q^* lower than the zero-overtopping limit is a minor issue, since the most intense wave overtopping phenomena are of major interest for engineering practices.

Figure 3.48a–d reveal that for observed q^* higher than 10^{-4} , the considered prediction formulas tend to underestimate the numerical data, up to one order of magnitude. This is likely to be linked to the non-conventional geometry and layering of the tested breakwater configurations. In particular, the irregular shape of the existing armor layer may induce unexpected increase of the wave steepness along the structure slope, thus causing wave breaking for the highest waves, but enabling some of the lowest ones to go beyond the crown wall. The formula proposed by Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2022) gives good predictions only for observed q^* higher than 7×10^{-4} . Table 3.XXXVIII reports the values of *NBI*, *cor* and *HH* calculated with reference to the whole available dataset, including also q^* lower than 10^{-5} (i.e. the zero-overtopping limit). It should be noted that the exclusion of values of q^* lower than 10^{-5} would not produce significant variations of the calculated statistical indicators, since they represent only 11% and 12% of the entire dataset for the existing and upgraded structures, respectively. Therefore, even though considering only q^* higher than 10^{-5} may be sufficient for engineering practices, the prediction model performances were assessed considering the entire available dataset to provide a comprehensive evaluation useful also for research purposes. Table 3.XXXVIII shows that the

values of NBI , cor and HH are quite similar for all the considered prediction formulas. The normalized bias ranges between -0.06 and 0.04 for the formulas employed in Figure 3.48a–d, thus indicating a contained average component of the prediction error. This is in accordance with the shape of the data point clouds, of which the first and second halves are placed over and under the bisector, respectively, thus minimizing the average prediction error. Instead, the formula considered in Figure 3.48f produces a more significant averaged overestimation of the observed data. The correlation coefficient is always higher than 0.69 , thus indicating the existence of a strong positive relationship between observed and predicted values. Finally, the symmetrically normalized root mean square error ranges between 0.16 and 0.28 .

Figure 3.48 Comparison between the numerical data on non-dimensional mean wave overtopping discharge and the predictions of the formulas proposed by: (a) Smolka et al. (2009); (b) Jafari and Etemad-Shahidi (2012) and Etemad-Shahidi and Jafari (2014); (c) Molines and Medina (2016); (d) EurOtop (2018); (e) Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2022); (f) Eq. (7). Dashed lines indicate 10 times under/overestimation of the numerical q^* , whereas the dotted line represents the perfect prediction. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Table 3.XXXVIII Statistical indicators of the correspondence between predictions and numerical q^* measured for the E and CS configurations at cross-section no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Formulation	NBI		cor		HH	
	Conf. E	Conf. CS	Conf. E	Conf. CS	Conf. E	Conf. CS
Smolka et al. (2009)	-0.03	0.04	0.92	0.76	0.17	0.18
Jafari and Etemad-Shahidi (2012) and Etemad-Shahidi and Jafari (2014)	-0.05	0.02	0.86	0.80	0.20	0.18
Molines and Medina (2016)	-0.03	-0.04	0.91	0.73	0.17	0.16
EurOtop (2018)	-0.06	0.03	0.89	0.69	0.16	0.16
Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2022)	0.18	0.16	0.89	0.89	0.28	0.24
Equation (3.16)	-0.06	-0.03	0.97	0.90	0.14	0.12

Since none of the tested existing formulas provides an accurate estimate of q^* over the whole investigated range of hydrodynamic conditions, the numerical data on mean wave overtopping discharge were employed for the definition of two site-specific formulas, for the existing and upgraded structures respectively, according to the following format:

$$q^* = \frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = a_q \cdot \exp \left[- \left(b_q \frac{R_c}{H_s \xi_{m-1,0}} \right)^{c_q} \right] \quad (3.16)$$

where c_q was calculated as the optimal value for the entire dataset, and a_q and b_q were estimated using the least squares linear regression method. It should be noted that the presence of $\xi_{m-1,0}$, which was used by all the above-mentioned existing formulas with the exception of the one proposed by EurOtop (2018), allows the inclusion of possible breaking phenomena which may develop over the structure slope. Table 3.XXXIX reports the optimal c_q , the estimate and the standard deviation of a_q and b_q and the corresponding R^2 , calculated for both the existing and upgraded structures. Figure 3.49 graphically shows the fitted formulations, which are valid for $10^{-7} < q^* < 10^{-2}$ and $0.30 < R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0}) < 0.80$. The numerical results for each of the reproduced sea states are represented in terms of mean q^* and $R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$ evaluated with reference to the six realizations with different seeding, being the vertical and horizontal error bars representative of the corresponding standard deviation. When the lower error bar is absent, it has a negative value, which does not have a physical meaning and cannot be plotted in log-scale. Such a condition occurs when null q^* are recorded for some of the six realizations of a certain sea state.

Figure 3.48f shows that the numerical non-dimensional mean overtopping discharge is quite well predicted by the site-specific formulas, also when the lowest and highest q^* are considered. Indeed, the data point cloud is very close to the bisector for the whole range of numerical q^* , though with a more pronounced scatter level for q^* lower than 10^{-5} due to the highest uncertainty of the numerical simulation results (see Section 5). As already stated, the lowest reliability of the predictions for q^* lower than 10^{-5} is of little interest for engineering practices. Table 3.XXXVIII shows that the negative NBI is quite contained, thus indicating a slight tendency of the site-specific formulas to underestimate the observed data on average. The very strong correlation between the numerical and predicted q^* is demonstrated by *cor* equal to or greater than 0.90. Finally, values of *HH* calculated for the predictions of equation (3.16) are lower than the ones found using state-of-the-art formulas.

Table 3.XXXIX Coefficients and coefficient of determination of the site-specific equations which describe the relationship between q^* and $R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Configuration	c_q	a_q		b_q		R^2
		Estimate	σ	Estimate	σ	
E	3.8	0.023	0.005	2.930	0.088	0.94
CS	3.8	0.015	0.006	2.933	0.112	0.78

Figure 3.49 Site-specific prediction formula fitted to the numerical data on non-dimensional mean wave overtopping discharge as a function of $R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$: (a) configuration E; (b) configuration CS. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

It seems useful to recall the simplified version of equation (3.16) presented by Stagnitti et al. (2022), which is a calibrated version of the EurOtop (2018) formula (see Eq. (3.11)):

$$q^* = \frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = a_{q2} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(b_{q2} \frac{R_c}{H_s \gamma_f} \right)^{1.3} \right] \tag{3.17}$$

where γ_f is the roughness factor (equal to 0.47 for double layer of artificial cubes), and a_E and b_E are empirical parameters equal to 0.30 ($\sigma = 0.14$) and 1.50 ($\sigma = 0.01$) for configuration E, and to 0.06 ($\sigma = 0.05$) and 1.50 ($\sigma = 0.15$) for configuration CS.

Besides the mean wave overtopping discharge, the probability of wave overtopping was calculated for both the E and CS configurations. The obtained results were compared to the predictions of state-of-the-art formulas developed for conventional rubble-mound breakwaters, whose range of applicability is consistent with our dataset. Two formulas which express P_o as a function of the non-dimensional mean wave overtopping discharge $Q^* = q / (gH_s T_m)$ developed by Besley (1999) and Mares-Nasarre et al. (2020) were considered. Moreover, the following more sophisticated formulation expressing P_o as a function of the sea state characteristics and breakwater geometry was employed (EurOtop, 2018):

$$P_o = \exp \left[- \left(\sqrt{-\ln 0.02} \frac{R_c}{R_{u,2\%}} \right)^2 \right] \tag{3.18}$$

where $R_{u,2\%}$ is the wave run-up level corresponding to the 2%-value of the hypnotized Rayleigh distribution, calculated using the following empirical formula for the case of orthogonal wave attack and neglecting the effects of the toe berm:

$$\frac{R_{u,2\%}}{H_s} = 1.65 \cdot \gamma_f \cdot \xi_{m-1,0} \quad (3.19)$$

where γ_f is the roughness factor equal to 0.47 for double layer of artificial cubes. Following a similar approach to the one employed for the analysis of q^* , Figure 3.50a–c shows the graphical comparison between the observed and predicted probability of overtopping of the existing and upgraded configurations, whereas Table 3.XL reports the corresponding NBI , cor and HH of P_o .

State-of-the-art formulas considered in Figure 3.50a–c clearly overestimate the observed probability of wave overtopping. In particular, Figure 3.50a–b shows predictions higher than the observed probability of wave overtopping by more than one order of magnitude when the latter is lower than 10^{-3} and 2×10^{-2} , respectively. Instead, the existing formula employed in Figure 3.50c provides estimates of P_o higher than the observed values by no more than one order of magnitude. The highest scatter level of the data point clouds found for observed P_o lower than 4×10^{-3} is coherent with the uncertainty typical of measurements of overtopping produced by low-energy sea states. Table 3.XL shows that the positive NBI ranges between 1.77 and 13.44, thus confirming the tendency of state-of-the-art formulas to return predictions of P_o higher than the observed ones. The correlation among predicted and observed values is very strong, with cor in the range $0.84 \div 0.97$. Finally, HH assumes values between 0.95 and 3.07.

Figure 3.50 Comparison between the numerical data on probability of wave overtopping and the predictions of the formulas proposed by: (a) Besley (1999); (b) EurOtop (2018); (c) Mares-Nasarre et al. (2020); (d) Eq. (10). Dashed lines indicate 10 times under/overestimation of the numerical P_o , whereas the dotted line represents the perfect prediction. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Table 3.XL Statistical indicators of the correspondence between predictions and numerical P_o measured for the E and CS configurations at cross-section no. 40. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Formulation	NBI		cor		HH	
	Conf. E	Conf. CS	Conf. E	Conf. CS	Conf. E	Conf. CS
Besley (1999)	1.77	3.57	0.97	0.97	0.95	1.54
EurOtop (2018)	3.90	13.44	0.88	0.84	1.44	3.07
Mares-Nasarre et al. (2020)	1.98	4.66	0.93	0.96	1.01	1.85
Equation (3.20)(3.16)	0.16	0.10	0.95	0.90	0.3.	0.38

The peculiar geometry and layering of the tested rubble-mound structures are likely to contribute to the deviation of the observed probability of wave overtopping from the predictions of existing formulas. In particular, breaking phenomena along the irregular slope of the existing armor layer and the increased porosity of the structure with additional blocks may induce the reduction of the number of overtopped waves with respect to state-of-the-art predictions. Such a reduction does not necessarily correspond to values of q^* lower than the expected ones, because the mean wave overtopping discharge is influenced not only by the number of overtopped waves, but also by their energy content. In any case, concerning the prediction formulation proposed by EurOtop (2018), a certain overestimation of the measured number of overtopping waves is expected, because equations (3.18) and (3.19) refer to the run-up level on a straight rock armored slope. Indeed, as explained by Schüttrumpf et al. (2018), wave overtopping discharge is not measured in the correspondence of the run-up level, but some onshore distance away, in this case behind the crown wall.

A more reliable description of the probability of wave overtopping for a certain structure type can be obtained by adapting traditional formulations to specific experimental data. To this aim, Eqs. (3.18) and (3.19) can be combined and rewritten as:

$$P_o = \exp \left[- \left(c_{Po} \frac{R_c}{H_s \xi_{m-1,0}} \right)^2 \right] \tag{ 3.20 }$$

where c_{Po} is an empirical coefficient that includes the peculiarities of the considered structure. For instance, Victor et al. (2012) proposed a relationship for the calculation of c_{Po} as a function of the slope angle, specific for smooth slopes and neglecting the effect of $T_{m-1,0}$ included in Eq. (3.20). Likewise, Iuppa et al. (2019) defined a formula for the calculation of c_{Po} specific for OBREC systems with a 2:3 seaside slope, not considering the influence of $\xi_{m-1,0}$ on wave overtopping phenomena. In the work of Stagnitti et al. (2023b), two site-specific formulas were defined, by fitting the coefficient c_{Po} of Eq. (3.20) to our data. The proposed formulation for the existing and upgraded cube-armored breakwaters includes the effects of the wave steepness, which is expressed by $\xi_{m-1,0}$. Moreover, the empirical coefficient c_{Po} allows to take into account the geometrical irregularities of the existing armor slope, which are likely to induce the rise of the wave steepness and wave breaking of the highest waves, as well as the unusually large thickness of the porous media composed by the layers of the upgraded breakwater, which is likely to cause significant wave energy dissipation. Table 3.XLI reports the estimated c_{Po} and its standard deviation, together with the R^2 of the fitting performed through the least squares method. Moreover, Figure 3.51 shows the numerical dataset and the fitted curves with the corresponding 95% confidence bounds. According to the procedure employed for the

visualization of the mean wave overtopping discharge data, the mean value and the standard deviation of P_o were calculated for each simulated sea state, considering six realizations.

Figure 3.50d shows that the site-specific formulas provide a good estimate of the observed P_o when the latter is higher than 10^{-2} . The highest scatter level which characterizes the data point cloud for observed P_o lower than 10^{-2} is again due to the significant level of uncertainty which affects the measurement of the less intense wave overtopping events. In any case, the overestimation of the numerical P_o is never higher than one order of magnitude. Table 3.XL reveals that the fitted Eq. (3.20) produces predictions with NBI and HH much lower than the considered state-of-the-art formulas. Moreover, the correlation between observed and estimated P_o is always strong, being cor equal to 0.95 and 0.90 for the case of existing and upgraded structures, respectively.

The last analysis regards the individual wave overtopping volumes. In particular, the calculation of the probability density function of the individual wave overtopping volumes for each simulated sea state was performed, considering both the existing and the upgraded structure. The distribution of individual wave overtopping volumes is generally well-described by the two-parameter Weibull distribution (EurOtop, 2018):

$$P_{V_i}(V) = P[V_i > V] = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{V}{a_V}\right)^{b_V}\right] \quad (3.21)$$

where $P_{V_i}(V)$ is the probability that the generic individual volume V_i is greater than the reference value V , and a_V and b_V are the scale and shape parameter of the distribution, respectively.

Table 3.XLI Coefficients and coefficient of determination of the site-specific equations which describe the relationship between P_o and $R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

Configuration	C_{P_o}		R^2
	Estimate	σ	
E	3.604	0.221	0.88
CS	4.140	0.227	0.76

Figure 3.51 Site-specific prediction formula fitted to the numerical data on probability of wave overtopping expressed as function of $R_c / (H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$: (a) configuration E; (b) configuration CS. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

In the work of Stagnitti et al. (2023b), the Weibull distribution was adapted to the sample of individual volumes of each simulation using the maximum likelihood estimation method, and its goodness of fit was verified through the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test at the 5% significance level. Following the work of Bruce et al. (2009), the adaptation of the Weibull distribution was not performed for simulations giving less than 15 overtopping events, which are characterized by q^* is lower than 4×10^{-5} . The calculated shape and scale parameters of the Weibull distributions were compared to the predictions of state-of-the-art formulas. In particular, the shape parameter for conventional rubble-mound structures can be evaluated as a function of the ratio $q / (gH_s T_{m-1,0})$, using the following empirical formula (Zanuttigh et al., 2014) as suggested by EurOtop (2018):

$$b_V = 0.85 + 1500 \cdot \left(\frac{q}{gH_s T_{m-1,0}} \right)^{1.3} \tag{3.22}$$

Figure 3.52 compares the estimates of b_V computed for configurations E and CS using Eq. (3.22). In order to link each b_V to the corresponding probability of wave overtopping, a color scale is employed. The scatter of the data decreases for increasing P_o or $q/(gH_s T_{m-1,0})$. Such a result agrees with the fact that for small wave overtopping events the measurement dispersion of is higher. The calculated values of b_V , which correspond to $q/(gH_s T_{m-1,0})$ ranging between 1×10^{-5} and 5×10^{-4} , seem to be significantly underestimated by Eq. (3.22). However, our dataset is similar to the highest scattered part of the CLASH rubble-mound dataset (Steendam et al., 2005) used by Zanuttigh et al. (2014) for the calibration of Eq. (3.22). In particular, the region characterized by P_o lower than 0.05 and b_V greater than 1.40 is not included into the empirical model. Also, the values of b_V with P_o higher than 0.05, which were found for configuration E, are almost overlapping the clash rubble-mound dataset. The same holds for the couples $P_o - b_V$ with P_o lower than 0.05 and b_V lower than 1.40. The similarity between the shape parameters evaluated for configurations E and CS and the ones calculated for the clash rubble-mound dataset is in accordance with the findings of Bruce et al. (2009) and Zanuttigh et al. (2014), who verified that b_V is not significantly influenced by the armor layer surface roughness, the structure porosity and the number of layers of armor blocks (i.e. one or two layers) for the range of $q/(gH_s T_{m-1,0})$ considered by Stagnitti et al. (2023b). New site-specific formulas to estimate b_V were not defined because of the too high scattered nature of the dataset.

Figure 3.52 Comparison between the values of the shape parameter of the Weibull distributions fitted to the numerical data expressed as a function of $q/(gH_s T_{m-1,0})$ and the predictions of Zanuttigh et al. (2014). Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

The scale parameter of the Weibull distribution can be estimated using the following relationship (EurOtop, 2018):

$$a_V = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{b_V}\right)} \cdot \frac{qT_m}{P_o} \quad (3.23)$$

where Γ is the gamma function. In the present work, q , T_m , P_o are the output of the numerical simulations. The shape parameter b_V should be calculated using Eq. (3.22). However, as already discussed, such a formula is not sufficiently reliable for the range of $q/(gH_s T_{m-1,0})$ considered here. Therefore, the estimated b_V were employed, to verify the adequacy of Eq. (13) in predicting the correspondent a_V . Figure 3.53a–b shows the scatter plot for the comparison between the numerical and the predicted scale parameter, using a color scale to relate each data point to the corresponding measured P_o . Moreover, the statistical error indicators NBI , cor and HH were calculated to quantify the differences between measured and predicted values.

The obtained results show that Eq. (3.23) produces a quite good prediction of the observed a_V , being cor greater than 0.90 and HH not higher than 0.21, for both the tested configurations. However, the employed formulation tends to slightly overestimate the numerical a_V , as demonstrated by the position of the data point clouds with respect to the bisector, and also by the positive NBI equal to 0.10 and 0.23 for the existing and upgraded structures, respectively.

If the Weibull distribution of individual wave overtopping volumes is known, the expected maximum V_{max} can be calculated using the following formula (EurOtop, 2018):

$$V_{max} = a_V \cdot [\ln(N_o)]^{1/b_V} \quad (3.24)$$

Figure 3.53c–d show the comparison between the observed and predicted V_{max} , using again the scatter plot with color scale to relate each data point to the corresponding P_o . The statistical error indicators NBI , cor and HH were also calculated. The prediction formula tends to slightly underestimate the measured maximum wave overtopping volumes. Such a results is confirmed by the values of NBI , which is equal to -0.13 and -0.14 for the existing and upgraded structures, respectively. However, the correlation coefficient is close to 0.90 and the parameter HH is about 0.20 for both the tested configurations. Therefore, despite of the considered non-conventional configurations, Eq. (3.24) is able to provide a quite good prediction of the maximum wave overtopping volume produced during a single event. Such a result confirms that the traditional formulation for the statistical characterization of the individual wave overtopping volumes, which is based on the use of the Weibull distribution, seems adequate also for damaged or upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters when P_o ranges between 5.6×10^{-4} and 2.1×10^{-1} .

Figure 3.53 Comparison between the fitted and estimated distributions of individual wave overtopping volumes according to EurOtop (2018): scale parameter of the Weibull distribution for (a) configuration E and (b) configuration CS; maximum wave overtopping volume for (c) configuration E and (d) configuration CS. Source: Stagnitti et al. (2023b).

New dataset on wave overtopping of rubble-mound breakwaters

Numerical model setup and simulations

The new numerical dataset on wave overtopping regards two new upgrading configurations of cross-section no. 40 of the Catania Harbor breakwater. The PD configuration, which is showed in Figure 3.54a, consists on the addition of extra armor units that have the same weight as the existing ones, i.e. 62 tons, and follow a 2:1 slope. The armor and crest freeboards are +9.80 m and +9.50 m above mean sea level (MSL), respectively. A toe berm made up by 7-ton quarry stones is placed at the toe of the additional armor layer, with a submergence of -8.00 m above MSL. In the PE configuration, which is illustrated in Figure 3.54b, the additional 62 tons parallelepipeds are placed exclusively on the submerged portion of structure, forming an S-shaped cross-section. The armor and crest freeboards are +5.00 m and +10.00 m above mean sea level (MSL), respectively. With respect to the PD configuration, the berm at the toe of the extra armor units is smaller and its submergence is -10.50 m above MSL. Three target intermediate water hydrodynamic conditions were considered, namely HC01, HC02 and HC03, which are characterized in terms of target significant wave height (H_s^t), peak wave period (T_p^t), increase of mean sea level (Δh), and number of waves. As indicated in Table 3.XLII, each hydrodynamic condition was generated two times, with a different seeding for wave random generation.

Table 3.XLII Target hydrodynamic conditions tested (prototype scale) during the experimental and numerical tests on structure configurations PD and PE.

Hydrodynamic condition	Wave seeding	H_s^t [m]	T_p^t [s]	Δh [m]	No. of waves
HCO1	S1 and S2	5.00	10.00	0.50	1500
HCO2	S1 and S2	6.00	11.00	0.58	1500
HCO3	S1 and S2	7.00	11.60	0.66	1500

The model was run at prototype scale as described in Figure 3.55. The numerical channel is 350.00 m long and 45.50 m high. The length of the numerical flume is such that it contains at least one wavelength in front of the tested structure, under the considered wave conditions. Instead, the height of the domain is such that a freeboard equal to 17.50 m between the crest of the structure and the top boundary is ensured for the development of the overtopping processes.

Stress, pressure and gradients of turbulent energy and dissipation were set equal to zero at the free surface. Inflow/outflow and continuative outflow boundary conditions were employed at the initial and final solid walls of the numerical channel, respectively. Finally, waves were generated at the initial solid wall of the numerical flume by a static wave paddle (i.e. Dirichlet boundary condition) with active absorption, whereas a sponge layer was placed on the opposite side of the domain. In particular, series of approximately 1500 waves was generated using JONSWAP-type spectra with a peak enhancement factor γ of 3.3, as recommended by Boccotti (2004) for the Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 3.54 Sketches of the cross-sections of the upgrading solutions for the Catania harbor breakwater: (a) detailed project (PD configuration); (b) executive project (PE configuration). Sizes are provided in meters at prototype scale.

Figure 3.55 Sketch of the wave flume employed for the numerical tests, with the location of the studied structure, the wave gauges (WG), and the overtopping measurement system (sizes are provided at prototype scale in meters). R_c is the structure crest freeboard and h is the water depth at the toe of the structure, which is equal to $19.0 \text{ m} + \Delta h$.

Six wave gauges with sampling frequency of 30 Hz were placed along the numerical channel, according to the pattern shown in Figure 3.55: i) signals recorded by wave gauges WG01, WG04, WG05, and WG06 were used to monitor the wave propagation along the channel; ii) signals recorded by wave gauges WG02 and WG03 were employed for the characterization of the incident wave motion through the two gauges method (Goda and Suzuki, 1976). An additional gauge with a sampling frequency of 30 Hz was installed at the wave wall to measure the flow thickness and velocity over it. These measurements allow for the calculation of both individual and mean wave overtopping volumes.

The choice of the computational grid and the porosity parameters was based on a comparison between the results of preliminary calibration simulations and the experimental data collected during the campaign described by Stagnitti et al. (2020, 2023a). Calibrating the porosity parameters using experimental data rather than relying solely on values suggested in the literature, which is always advisable, is especially important when dealing with non-conventional structures such as those shown in Figure 3.54. During this preliminary analysis, three non-uniform grids and ten different combinations of porosity parameters were tested. The cell size in the non-uniform grids was gradually varied in both vertical and horizontal directions to achieve higher resolution in the region where overtopping processes occur. Regarding the porosity parameters, α_F and c_F were set to 200 and 0.34 respectively, following the recommendations of Lara et al. (2008), while different combinations of n and β_F were explored.

The comparison between the simulation results and the available experimental wave reflection coefficients and mean overtopping discharges (Stagnitti et al., 2020, 2023a) showed that the optimal combination of cell size and porosity parameters, in terms of both correspondence between numerical and experimental results and computational time, varied depending on the energy content of the incoming wave motion. For R_c/H_s lower than 1.4, the cell horizontal and vertical sizes are in the range $1.00 \div .20 \text{ m}$ and $0.50 \div 0.78 \text{ m}$, for a total of 291 and 66 cells along the horizontal and vertical directions. Instead, for the less energetic sea states with R_c/H_s greater or equal to 1.4, a finer grid is required to properly simulate the lower wave heights. In this case, the grid cells have horizontal and vertical sizes in the range $0.70 \div 1.85 \text{ m}$ and $0.30 \div 0.82 \text{ m}$, for a total of 349 and 105 cells along the horizontal and vertical directions. In the refinement region, both grids ensure the aspect ratio (i.e. $\Delta x/\Delta y$) equal to 2, as well as at least $14 \div 20$ cells per wave height along the vertical direction. The porosity parameters n and β_F assumed the values reported in Table 3.XLIII. The computational time for reproducing about

1500 waves by using a processor Intel Xeon Silver 4214 2.20 GHz was 10 hours when R_c/H_s is lower than 1.4, otherwise 15 hours.

Table 3.XLIII Characteristics of the porous layers of the tested structures. Despite of the value of R_c/H_s , α_F and c_F of each porous layer are set equal to 200 and 0.34, respectively.

Porous layer	Porosity parameter	R_c/H_s	
		<1.4	≥ 1.4
Core ($D_{n50}=0.72$ m)	n	0.32	0.32
	β_F	1.20	1.20
Filter layer ($D_{n50}=1.22$ m)	n	0.35	0.35
	β_F	2.00	2.00
Existing armor layer ($D_{n50}=3.00$ m)	n	0.50	0.35
	β_F	0.50	1.00
Additional armor layer ($D_{n50}=3.00$ m)	n	0.25	0.20
	β_F	0.60	7.00
Toe berm ($D_{n50}=1.22$ m)	n	0.35	0.35
	β_F	3.00	3.00

Analysis of the numerical results

Besides the mean wave overtopping discharge, which was measured also during the experimental campaign, the number of wave overtopping events (N_o) was evaluated. Moreover, parameters describing the individual wave overtopping volumes distribution, such as the maximum overtopping volume (V_{max}), were calculated for each simulated sea state. The outputs of the numerical simulations are summarized in Table 3.XLIV and

Table 3.XLVTable 3.XLV.

The performed analysis focused on the response of the structure in terms of mean wave overtopping. Figure 3.56 shows the comparison between the numerical dimensionless mean wave overtopping discharge (q^*) expressed as a function of the dimensionless structure freeboard (R_c/H_s) and the prediction provided by the EurOtop Manual (2018) with its 95th percentile confidence bounds. It is observed that the numerical data follow fairly well the EurOtop Manual (2018) curve, which therefore can be used to describe the response in terms of q^* of the upgraded configurations PD and PE.

Table 3.XLIV Summary of the output of the new numerical simulations: cross-section no. 40, configuration PD.

Sea state ID	Rea l. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/(H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	N_o [no. of events]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
HC01	1	5.22	10.38	2.63	1.69	0.64	0.34	8.58×10^{-6}	2	2.62
	2	5.13	9.90	2.61	1.70	0.65	0.33	0.00	0	0.00
HC02	1	6.16	10.76	2.58	1.48	0.57	0.32	3.10×10^{-6}	1	2.11
	2	6.12	10.45	2.55	1.49	0.59	0.32	0.00	0	0.00
HC03	1	7.30	11.52	2.47	1.32	0.53	0.32	1.86×10^{-4}	17	19.79
	2	7.13	12.19	2.52	1.37	0.54	0.33	3.21×10^{-4}	24	24.96

Table 3.XLV Summary of the output of the new numerical simulations: cross-section no. 40, configuration PE.

Sea state ID	Real. ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	$\xi_{m-1,0}$ [-]	R_c/H_s [-]	$R_c/(H_s \xi_{m-1,0})$ [-]	k_r [-]	q^* [-]	N_o [no. of events]	V_{max} [m ³ /m]
HC01	1	5.19	10.38	2.63	1.76	0.67	0.28	7.21×10^{-7}	2	0.28
	2	5.11	9.90	2.61	1.77	0.68	0.28	1.05×10^{-6}	3	0.40
HC02	1	6.14	10.76	2.57	1.52	0.59	0.24	1.30×10^{-5}	9	1.59
	2	6.14	10.45	2.55	1.52	0.60	0.24	4.50×10^{-6}	5	1.32
HC03	1	7.41	11.52	2.45	1.31	0.53	0.23	1.42×10^{-4}	31	13.62
	2	7.17	12.19	2.52	1.34	0.53	0.23	2.61×10^{-4}	43	22.21

Figure 3.56 Comparison between the numerical dimensionless mean wave overtopping discharge expressed as a function of the dimensionless structure freeboard and the prediction provided by the EurOtop Manual (2018) with its 95th percentile confidence bounds.

3.2.3 Experimental dataset on rubble-mound breakwaters acquired by UniSalento

This section presents the experimental dataset on new rubble-mound breakwaters in depth-limited water conditions acquired by UniSalento. A portion of the data was previously published by Marino et al. (2023), Scaravaglione et al. (2024) and Scaravaglione et al. (2025a,b), whereas the remaining data were obtained within the framework of the PROMETEO Project.

Physical model

The experimental campaign was carried out in the wave flume at the European Maritime and Environmental Research Laboratory (EUMER) of the University of Salento (Lecce, Italy) (Figure 3.57). The wave flume is 45 m long, 2 m high, and 1.4 m wide, equipped with a piston-type wave generator able to generate both regular and second-order irregular waves characterised by target spectra shape (e.g., PM, JONSWAP, TMA, double). The wave generator is equipped with an Active Reflection Compensation system and a mild coarse and rocky spending beach (~1V:10H) is placed at the end of the flume to reduce as much as possible the re-reflection of the flume wall.

Figure 3.57 Wave tank of the EUMER of the University of Salento used for the experimental campaign. b) Flume control room.

A 2D physical model of a rubble mound breakwater (Figure 3.58) was built with the toe placed 29.10 m from the wave generator at the end of a 14.30 m long concrete foreshore ($m=1V:30H$). The foreshore was connected to a flat bottom by means of a short 1.1 m long transitional slope ($\sim 1V:5H$) ensuring sufficient depth at the wave generator. To control and fix exactly the water depth a point gauge is generally set at the end of the flume which allows a very accurate lecture (uncertainty of about 0.1 mm).

During the experimental investigation, wave conditions along the flume were measured through 8 resistive wave gauges (WG_i) with a sampling frequency equal to 40 Hz. Due to the inherent limitations of reflection analysis in depth-limited conditions, all tests were conducted with and without the structure to estimate the incident wave bulk parameters at the toe of the breakwater. Indeed, two different layouts for wave gauges were used: (i) for tests with the breakwater in the flume, and (ii) for wave calibration without the breakwater. The wave gauges positions for both layouts are detailed in Table 3.XLVI, providing the absolute distance from the wavemaker (Figure 3.58). The incident wave signals for irregular waves were obtained from the calibration tests without the structure in place. This approach was chosen because most methods for separating incident and reflected waves, particularly in the presence of sloping foreshores and nonlinear waves (Lykke Andersen and Eldrup, 2024), fail to capture the true wave behaviour. In fact, uncertainties in determining the incident wave parameters stem from the nonlinear nature of waves, which, in shallow water, transform into breaking rollers. The measured free surface elevation from the calibration tests was used to calculate the incident wave parameters, rather than relying on wave separation methods assuming the good performance of the active absorption system. To verify the performance of the absorption system, the measured wave spectra in deep water (WG_1) were compared against the target spectra provided by the wave generation system and with the incident spectra obtained at the WG_{2-4} array with the model in place (layout (i)), showing reasonable agreement. The primary drawback of this approach is the introduction of errors caused by wave reflection from the passive absorber during calibration tests. To account for the small but existing reflection induced by the dissipative beach, the inshore bulk reflection coefficient, K_R , was computed for all tests without breakwater in the flume ($0.08 \leq K_R \leq 0.32$), using the method of Mansard and Funke (1980), as modified by Zelt and Skjelbreia (1992), with a four-gauge-array among WG_{3-7} based on the optimal spacing for the given water and wave conditions. Since the total waves was measured at a distance of at least one wavelength from the dissipative beach, it was assumed

that the incident and reflected waves were uncorrelated, allowing for the calculation of the incident wave height, as suggested by Goda (2000), using the formula $H_{m0,i} = H_{m0}/(1+K_R)^{1/2}$.

Figure 3.58 Cross-section of the physical model and wave gauge (WG_i) locations with (layout (i)) and without (layout (ii)) the breakwater in the flume.

Table 3.XLVI Wave gauge absolute distance (m) from the wave generator.

Layout	WG ₁	WG ₂	WG ₃	WG ₄	WG ₅	WG ₆	WG ₇	WG ₈
(i)	0.66	11.8	12.6	13.2	21.2	28.20	28.65	-
(ii)	0.66	24.26	27.16	27.88	28.35	28.65	28.85	31.00

The structure was a conventional non-overtopped rubble mound breakwater without a toe berm. A small wooden slat, approximately 5 mm thick, was fixed seaward on the seabed near the toe, just in front of the bottom row armour rocks. The breakwater was 0.9 m high with a 0.2 m wide crest. The dimensionless crest freeboard ($R_c/H_{m0,t}$) above the still water level (SWL) was in the range of $1.99 \leq R_c/H_{m0,t} \leq 21.79$, ensuring the avoidance of overtopping conditions. The breakwater was protected by a double armour layer of rocks, randomly placed, with a front/rear slope of $\alpha=1V:2H$. The armour layers consisted of natural rocks provided by a local quarry. The placement of rocks can be considered bulk-random, and their shape can be assumed as equant and fresh, according to the definition given by Latham et al. (1988). The thickness of the armour and filter layers were determined as $2D_{n50}$ and $0.5D_{n50}$, respectively.

Four breakwater configurations (BW_i) and four water levels (WL_i) were tested across five different test series (Ti), denoted as T1 (BW₁ and WL₁, $h=0.40$ m), T2 (BW₂ and WL₂, $h=0.20$ m), T3 (BW₃ and WL₃, $h=0.10$ m), T4 (BW₄ and WL₃, $h=0.10$ m), and T5 (BW₄ and WL₄, $h=0.05$ m) (Figure 3.59). Notably, the structure with the highest water depth (T1) was the only configuration with an underlayer composed by stones approximately half the size of those in the armour layer, whereas the other structures consisted of an amour layer atop the core material. Figure 3.60 Rock sieving curves of the rock material used in the experiments. and Table 3.XLVII report, respectively, the sieving curves and the main characteristics of the rocks for each configuration, along with the notional permeability factor (P) calculated as proposed by Eldrup et al. (2019). Results show that the structure configuration BW₄ (Figure 3.59d,e) closely resembles a homogeneous structure ($P=0.55$), whereas the cross-sections with the lowest P -values (BW₁ and BW₂ in Figure 3.59a,b) are characterised by P -values close to 0.40, in line with the outcomes reported in van der Meer (1988). Table 3.XLVII also reports the $D_{n50,core}/D_{n50}$ ratio, the grading uniformity coefficient (D_{85}/D_{15}), the length-to-thickness ratio (LT), and the blockiness coefficient (BLC) used to assess the grading and the rough angular shape of rock in the armour layers for BW₁, BW₂ and BW₃, following the procedures outlined in the Rock Manual

(CIRIA/CUR/CETMEF, 2007). For the BW₄ configuration, the small dimensions of the stones did not permit conducting the same grading and shape characterisation as performed for the other configurations. These parameters were obtained by averaging the values from 20 samples randomly taken from the grain population, as shown in Figure 3.61, where the standard deviation (std) for each sample population was also calculated. The density of the stones was $\rho_r=2576 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and the porosity of the core (n) was assumed equal to 0.40 (Rock Manual, 2007). In the present study, the Reynolds number was calculated for both the armour layer (R_{eA}) and inside the porous core (R_{ep}) to assess the flow regime inside the structure and the potential occurrence of scale effects (Scaravaglione et al., 2024). In intermediate and shallow water R_{eA} exceeds 3×10^4 , and hence, no scale effects are expected. In shallower conditions (i.e., T3, T4 and T5), R_{eA} results $0.75 \times 10^4 \leq R_{eA} \leq 2 \times 10^4$, indicating that some scale effects could be present. Specifically, for T4 and T5, R_{eA} is slightly lower than 1×10^4 , and the test data can be considered slightly conservative, meaning that the corresponding damage to the prototype structure may be slightly less than those observed in the model tests (Hudson, 1975).

Figure 3.59 Layouts of the tested rubble mound breakwaters.

Figure 3.60 Rock sieving curves of the rock material used in the experiments.

Table 3.XLVII Main characteristics of rocks.

Breakwater configuration	BW ₁	BW ₂	BW ₃	BW ₄
D_{n50} [m]	0.046	0.034	0.024	0.0138
$D_{n50,underlayer}$ [m]	0.024	-	-	-
$D_{n50,core}$ [m]	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
$D_{n50,core}/D_{n50}$ [-]	0.21	0.29	0.41	0.71
D_{85}/D_{15} – armour [-]	1.26	1.27	1.20	1.28
LT – armour [-]	1.35	1.41	1.46	-
BLC – armour [%]	47.79	36.28	38.18	-
P -values [-]	0.37	0.40	0.47	0.55

Figure 3.61 Shape characterisation for armour layers used in the T1, T2 and T3 test series: length-to-thickness ratio (on the left) and blockiness coefficient (on the right).

Instruments

Wave measurements

The free-surface elevation along the wave flume was measured using eight resistive-type wave gauges. Each wave gauge operates by measuring the electrical resistance of the water column between two parallel metallic rods. The measured resistance is proportional to the immersion depth of the probes. Each wave gauge was connected to an acquisition card (AC), housed within a dedicated control box capable of accommodating up to eight acquisition channels (Figure 3.62). The electrical resistance is converted into an output voltage according to the relation: $\Delta V = R \cdot I$, where R is the electrical resistance of the probe wires dependent on their length and cross-sectional area and i is the electrical current. The output voltage signal is linearly related to the water surface elevation and is converted into metric units through a calibration relationship expressed as: $\eta = V_0 + kV$, where η is the free-surface elevation expressed in meters, V is the measured voltage, V_0 is the voltage offset, and k is the calibration coefficient. The full-scale operating range of each wave gauge was ± 10 V. Following standard laboratory procedures, all wave gauges were cleaned and calibrated daily prior to the commencement of the experimental tests. This procedure was necessary to minimize potential measurement inaccuracies caused by environmental factors such as water temperature variations, mineral deposits (e.g., limestone), and probe aging, which may affect the signal response over time. The calibration was considered

valid when the linear regression fitted through three reference points yielded a coefficient of determination R^2 close to unity. An example of a calibration output is presented in Figure 3.62.

Moreover, one wave gauge (WG_8) was employed to measure wave run-up during tests with structure in place, while it was used to record wave elevation over the flat bed during the wave calibration phase. As previously mentioned, wave run-up measurements were collected for almost all experimental tests, although portions of some signals were truncated due to exceeding the measurement range. The longest available wave gauge was installed on the sloping section to ensure the detection of at least $\pm 3H_{m0}$ relative to the still water level (SWL). To prevent unwanted movements and ensure measurement stability, a wooden support structure was rigidly fixed to the flume wall. The probe was positioned at a minimum distance of 0.15 m from the wall in order to minimize side-wall effects (Figure 3.63). For the tests conducted at the two largest water depths at the toe of the slope (0.40 m and 0.20 m), standard wave gauges were employed. Conversely, for the shallower water depths (0.10 m and 0.05 m at the toe of the slope), shorter wave gauges were used to ensure adequate measurement resolution and signal quality.

Figure 3.62 a),b): Wave gauges acquisition card; c): Calibration lines from each wave probe.

Figure 3.63 Run-up wave gauge.

Pressure measurements

In this experimental campaign, wave-induced pore pressures have been acquired for some tests. Pressure sensors were employed to measure the dynamic pressure induced by wave-driven flow within the rubble mound breakwater during the experimental campaign. Prior to installation, all pressure sensors were protected with a wire mesh casing (Figure 3.64) to prevent damage and clogging while ensuring an undisturbed transmission of pressure fluctuations. The sensors were accurately positioned at predefined locations inside the structure in order to create a three-dimensional pressure measurement grid, covering both vertical and horizontal planes. This configuration allowed for the reconstruction of the internal pressure and flow fields within the breakwater. In particular, by placing pressure sensors at the interface between the core and the underlayer, it was possible to investigate the attenuation of dynamic wave-induced pressures across different grading layers, both along the vertical and cross-shore directions (Figure 3.65).

Pressure measurements were conducted exclusively for test series T1, as for the remaining configurations the pressure sensors would not have been fully submerged. In total, seven tests with irregular wave conditions were performed for the T1 configuration. In addition, a dedicated series of 13 tests with regular waves (50 waves) was carried out for the same configuration. During these tests, the water depth at the toe of the slope was varied in order to investigate intermediate and shallow water conditions. For each tested water level, a static pressure measurement was acquired prior to wave generation. These measurements were used as a reference to assess the hydrostatic pressure distribution and to better control the degree of damping within the breakwater structure. All pressure signals were acquired with a sampling frequency of 1000 Hz, ensuring sufficient temporal resolution to accurately capture the rapid pressure fluctuations induced by wave action.

Figure 3.64 Pressure sensors and set-up of the sensors inside the structure.

Figure 3.65 Cross-shore view of the placements of the pressure sensors inside the rubble mound breakwater in relation to the T1 test series (top) and front and side views of the tested breakwater (bottom).

Video recording

Three video cameras were employed for continuous video recording and image acquisition throughout the entire experimental campaign. Two cameras were positioned in front of the breakwater, while a third camera was installed to provide a side-view perspective of the structure (Figure 3.66). This multi-camera configuration allowed for the simultaneous monitoring of different physical processes. In particular, the front-view cameras were used to support image-based analysis of wave run-up, whereas the side-view camera enabled the observation and qualitative assessment of the temporal evolution of armour layer damage and rock slope deformation during each test. The combined use of multiple viewing angles ensured

adequate spatial coverage of the breakwater and improved the reliability of the post-processing analyses by reducing potential occlusions and perspective-related uncertainties.

Figure 3.66 Placement of the video cameras.

Damage assessment

Laser profiler measurements

Damage measurements were performed using a high-density laser profiler provided by HR Wallingford. A total of ten transversal transects were surveyed across the flume width, with a spacing of 0.10 m between adjacent profiles. To minimize laboratory boundary effects, clearances of 0.20 m and 0.30 m were maintained from the left and right side walls of the wave flume, respectively. A local reference coordinate system was defined with its origin located at the lower corner of the structure ($x=0$, $y=0$, $z=0$). The x -axis represents the longitudinal direction, positive towards the seaward side of the structure; the y -axis corresponds to the transversal direction, positive in the wave propagation direction; and the z -axis denotes the vertical direction, positive upwards (Figure 3.67a). The laser profiler provides a measurement resolution of ± 0.5 mm in both the y and z directions, with the same positional accuracy ensured by the traverse support system. This level of accuracy is consistent with previous applications of the technique in laboratory studies (Atkinson and Baldock, 2016; Marino et al., 2023).

The damage analysis followed procedures similar to those proposed by van der Meer (1988) and van Gent et al. (2003), in order to ensure consistency and comparability with existing laboratory datasets. For each test, bed profiles were acquired both before and after wave loading, referred to as the mean initial (reference) profile and the final profile, respectively. For most tests, damage was assessed after 1000 incident waves. In cases where failure was not observed after 1000 waves, the test was extended to a total of 3000 waves (1000 + 2000) without reconstructing the armour layer. Figure 3.67b shows an example of reference and post-test profiles for test T1, expressed in terms of the mean vertical elevation z , averaged over the measured transversal transects and referenced to the local coordinate system. The eroded area (A_e) and accreted area (A_a) were computed as the integral of the negative and positive portions, respectively, of the spatial variation of the mean slope elevation change (Δz), including minor displacements. The dimensionless damage level S was then estimated as: $S=A_e/D_{n50}^2$.

The laser profiler consists of a vertically controlled positioning device driven by an electric motor and mechanical transmission system. A laser distance sensor, housed in a waterproof casing, is mounted at the lower end of the profiling rod. The vertical position of the probe is recorded by encoders installed on the motor shafts, allowing the accurate reconstruction of the slope elevation. The probe has a vertical measurement range of 600 mm and provides continuous output over the full profile length. This technique is widely adopted in hydraulic laboratories due to its high accuracy, on the order of tenths of a millimetre, good spatial resolution (comparable to the probe tip diameter, typically a few millimetres), and its ability to accurately track steep and irregular profiles. Longitudinal profiling is achieved through the horizontal translation of the

vertical profiling unit, typically mounted on a carriage system guided by rails or beams, with either motorized or manual displacement. In addition, prior to each test configuration, the armour slope was painted with alternating coloured stripes of approximately $3D_{n50}$ width. This procedure facilitated the visual tracking of stone displacements during wave loading. Photographs of the breakwater were taken before and after each test to support a qualitative assessment of damage evolution. Where applicable, the number of displaced stones (N_{od}) within a reference width of D_{n50} was also recorded, providing an additional indicator of the damage level. Table 3.XLVIII Measured damage level ranges for each test series summarizes the range of damage values measured for each test series during the experimental campaign.

Figure 3.67 Picture of the breakwater before and after 1000 waves of the test T1 and the analysis performed on MATLAB about the calculation of the eroded area. b) Reference coordinate system and 10 transsects across the flume width. c) Example of reference (red solid line) and final (black solid line) averaged profiles measured for the test T1 after 1000 waves (Top right). Spatial evolution of slope elevation changes (dz) with respect to the initial slope (Bottom right): erosion area (red) and accretion area (grey).

Table 3.XLVIII Measured damage level ranges for each test series.

	T1	T2	T3-T4	T5
Slope damage: S [-]	1.8-20	1.5-11.05	1.2-18.4	1-8.21

Photogrammetry

In coastal engineering, and particularly in studies addressing wave–structure interaction, the application of photogrammetry for quantitative damage assessment is still relatively limited. In the present study, photogrammetry was employed as a complementary tool to traditional profiling techniques, allowing for the three-dimensional reconstruction of the breakwater

geometry before and after selected tests. By overlapping the reconstructed 3D models (using Metashape), it was possible to obtain spatial deviation maps highlighting areas of erosion and accretion and to extract representative mean profiles of the structure. Figure 3.68 illustrates an example of the photogrammetric analysis for test series T1, showing: (a) the damaged breakwater configuration at the end of the test; (b) a deviation map obtained by comparing the pre- and post-test 3D models. Further details and results are reported in Marino et al. (2023).

Figure 3.68 a) The damaged structure at the end of test T1 06. b) A deviation map obtained overlapping the 3D models of the structure before and after the test.

Test program

A total of 33 laboratory tests were conducted to investigate the hydraulic stability of steep rock-armoured rubble mound breakwaters under nonstationary wave conditions. The experimental tests were organised into distinct configurations, each subdivided into two test series characterised by progressively increasing wave height and wave period at the wave generator. Within each series, the target offshore spectral wave steepness ($s_{m-1,0,0}$) was kept constant and set equal to 0.024 and 0.048, respectively, in order to reproduce storm-like, nonstationary wave conditions. After the completion of each individual test, the breakwater structure was fully rebuilt prior to the subsequent test to ensure repeatability and independence of results. For each test, a minimum of 1000 incident waves was generated to investigate the initiation and progression of armour layer damage. Irregular wave conditions were reproduced using a JONSWAP spectrum with a peak enhancement factor $\gamma=3.3$. For selected tests, where no significant damage was observed after the initial 1000 waves, the wave loading was extended up to 3000 waves (1000 + 2000) to further assess damage development. Conversely, tests were terminated before reaching 1000 waves when the underlayer (for configuration T1) or the core layer (for configurations T2, T3, T4, and T5) became visibly exposed to wave action. In such cases, the reduced test duration (t_r) was adopted to correlate the measured damage level with the exact number of incident waves, calculated as: $N_w=t_r/T_m$, where T_m is the mean wave period in the time domain. Under shallow water conditions, the mean wave period measured near the toe of the breakwater may vary significantly, directly affecting the estimation of N_w . Therefore, for consistency, the deep-water mean wave period ($T_{m,0}$) was used in the calculation of the number of incident waves. Prior to each test series, the rubble mound breakwater was subjected to a shake-down procedure consisting of low-energy wave loading, aimed at compacting the armour units and allowing the structure to reach a stable initial condition (Hughes, 1993).

The experimental program covered a wide range of hydrodynamic conditions, including intermediate, shallow, very shallow, and extremely shallow water depths, both with and without

wave breaking on the foreshore. The tests encompassed different breaking regimes, including surging and plunging breakers. The experimental campaign provided new stability data in very shallow and extremely shallow water conditions ($h_r = H_{m0,o}/h > 1.5$), a regime that remains poorly documented in existing literature. Specifically, out of the 33 tests performed, 7 tests were conducted under intermediate water depth conditions ($h=0.40$ m), 10 tests under shallow conditions ($h=0.20$ m), 10 tests under very shallow conditions ($h=0.10$ m), and 6 tests under extremely shallow water conditions ($h=0.05$ m). In addition, for configuration BW₁, a supplementary set of 13 tests with regular waves was performed, each consisting of 50 incident waves, to investigate the influence of different levels of wave shallowness (Scaravaglione et al., 2024).

Table 3.XLIX summarises the main characteristics of the experimental program, including the number of tests for each breakwater configuration (N), the water depth at the toe of the structure (h), the relative water depth (h_r), and the measured offshore spectral wave steepness ($S_{m-1,0,o}$).

Table 3.XLIX Main characteristics of the performed tests.

Test ID	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Regular
Breakwater configuration	BW ₁	BW ₂	BW ₃	BW ₄	BW ₄	BW ₁
Water level	WL ₁	WL ₂	WL ₃	WL ₃	WL ₄	WL ₁ – WL _{reg}
N [-]	7	10	6	4	6	13
h [m]	0.40	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.40 - 0.30
h_r [-]	0.42-0.75	0.71-1.40	1.49-2.54	1.49-2.03	2.98-4.94	0.5 - 1
$S_{m-1,0,o}$ [-]	0.024-0.051	0.025-0.047	0.024-0.046	0.024-0.046	0.024-0.046	0.019 – 0.07

Wave analysis

Wave analysis was performed using the time series of incident waves measured in front of the breakwater toe, recorded during preliminary tests conducted without the structure installed in the flume. This approach ensured that the analysed wave conditions were not influenced by reflection, transmission, or dissipation processes induced by the presence of the structure. Table 3.L summarizes the dimensionless wave parameters derived from the analysis and the range covered by the full experimental dataset. Figure 3.69 presents the measured offshore spectral wave steepness $s_{m-1,0,o} = H_{m0,o}/L_{m-1,0,o}$, the relative wave height ($H_{m0,t}/H_{m0,o}$), the ratio $H_{2\%,t}/H_{s,t}$ and the relative wave period ($T_{m-1,0,t}/T_{m-1,0,o}$) all plotted as functions of the relative depth (h_r) computed at the toe of the breakwater.

Table 3.L Wave characteristics for each test series.

Main parameters	T1 (WL ₁)	T2 (WL ₂)	T3-T4 (WL ₃)	T5 (WL ₄)	Total
$H_{m0,o}/h$	0.42 – 0.75	0.71 – 1.40	1.49 – 2.54	2.98 – 4.94	0.42 – 4.94
$H_{2\%,t}/H_{s,t}$	1.20 – 1.37	1.20 -1.31	1.29 – 1.32	1.31 – 1.43	1.20 – 1.43
$H_{m0,t}/H_{s,t}$	0.90 – 0.99	0.89 – 0.98	0.96 – 1.04	1.00 – 1.11	0.89 – 1.11
$T_{p,o}/T_{m-1,0,o}$	1.05 – 1.12	1.02 -1.09	1.00 – 1.09	1.01 – 1.13	1.00 – 1.13
$H_{m0,t}/H_{m0,o}$	0.83 – 1.03	0.57 – 0.96	0.57 – 0.96	0.21 - 0.28	0.21 – 1.03
$T_{m-1,0,t}/T_{m-1,0,o}$	1.00 – 1.11	1.09 – 1.36	1.53 – 2.30	2.42 – 3.40	1.00 – 3.40

Figure 3.69 Wave characteristics as a function of the relative depth.

Previous experimental datasets by van Gent et al. (2003) mainly cover shallow and very shallow foreshore conditions but do not include low steepness waves, whereas the dataset by Eldrup and Andersen (2019) extends the range to smaller steepness values, down to $s_{m-1,0,o}=0.01$. As shown in Figure 3.69a, the present experimental data cover realistic wind-wave conditions, with $0.02 < s_{m-1,0,o} < 0.05$, a range commonly adopted in engineering design. Figure 3.69b shows that, under relatively intermediate water depth conditions, limited wave shoaling occurs prior to reaching the breakwater toe, with $H_{m0,t}/H_{m0,o}$ slightly exceeding unity for two sea states. As the relative depth decreases, wave breaking becomes progressively dominant. In extremely shallow water, wave heights decay significantly, reaching values as low as 20% of the offshore spectral wave height. Tests involving low-steepness waves exhibit pronounced nonlinear shoaling in intermediate water depths, whereas higher-steepness waves tend to break earlier along the foreshore. Figure 3.69c illustrates the evolution of the ratio $H_{2\%,t}/H_{s,t}$ with relative depth. In deep water conditions, where wave breaking is absent, wave heights are approximately Rayleigh distributed, and the ratio approaches 1.40. As waves shoal and propagate towards shallower depths, nonlinear effects amplify individual wave heights, leading to deviations from the Rayleigh distribution. Once waves enter the surf zone, the stochastic breaking process significantly alters the wave height distribution. The ratio $H_{2\%,t}/H_{s,t}$ decreases from 1.40 to approximately 1.20 in shallow water ($h_r > 0.75$), before increasing again and stabilising around 1.30 in very shallow conditions. In extremely shallow water ($h_r > 3$), the ratio increases once more, approaching values close to 1.40. This behaviour is consistent with the findings reported by Goda (2010, 2012), who observed a reversion towards Rayleigh-type statistics as waves approach the shoreline. The variation of the relative spectral wave period ($T_{m-1,0,t}/T_{m-1,0,o}$) with relative depth is shown in Figure 3.69d. Infragravity (IG) waves generated within the flume significantly influence wave parameters, particularly $T_{m-1,0,t}$. As waves propagate along the foreshore, the spectral wave period at the toe increases markedly, reaching values up to four times the deep-water period under extremely shallow conditions. This increase is attributed to wave breaking and energy dissipation at peak and higher harmonic frequencies, combined with a progressive transfer of energy towards lower frequencies (Hofland et al., 2017).

Figure 3.70 reports the ratio $H_{s,t}/H_{m0,t}$ plotted against the nonlinearity parameter for all tests, corresponding to the two target deep wave steepness values. Goda (2010) described the nonlinearity parameter as $\Pi_0 = \frac{H_{m0,o}}{L_{m,o}} \coth\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L_{m,o}}\right)^3$, where $L_{m,o}$ is the local wavelength calculated with T_m . For $\Pi_0 \leq 0.2$, data show that the ratio $H_{s,t}/H_{m0,t}$ is approximately 1, but a clear difference is observed in the range $0.2 < \Pi_0 < 1$, where $H_{s,t}/H_{m0,t}$ increases, reflecting the expected mean behaviour for low steepness waves according to Goda (2010). For $\Pi_0 \geq 1$, the ratio decreases to around 0.9. In relatively shallow water wave nonlinearity increases with an increase in wave height. As waves approach the shore, they undergo nonlinear shoaling, resulting in wave profiles with high and sharp crests and low and flat troughs. This nonlinearity effect becomes most pronounced around the outer edge of the surf zone. Within the surf zone, waves begin to break, and nonlinearities are gradually lessened, in accordance with wave steepness. Specifically, low steepness waves experience significant nonlinear shoaling before breaking, whereas high steepness waves break earlier.

Figure 3.70 Wave height ratio as a function of the nonlinearity parameter.

Figure 3.71 provides further insights into the energy spectral spreading during wave propagation in shallow water by showing the ratio $m^{IG}_{0,t}/m^{TOT}_{0,t}$ at varying relative depth, where $m^{IG}_{0,t}$ represents the infragravity (IG) wave energy component, and $m^{TOT}_{0,t}$ represents the total wave energy, both evaluated at the structure toe. The inset plot shows an example of the density spectrum for a test in very shallow water (T4), evaluated at the toe, highlighting the dominant peak frequencies. As water depth decreases, wave breaking begins, causing dissipation of energy at the peak and higher harmonic frequencies, while energy at lower frequencies continues to increase. Due to the very long wavelengths of these low-frequency waves, they do not break, and the substantial energy present at these lower frequencies explains the observation of large wave periods in shallow water. The spectrum clearly indicates significant energy in the infragravity frequency band in very shallow water. Results, indeed, demonstrate that, in the deep water, the infragravity waves minimally contribute to the total wave energy, but this contribution becomes progressively more significant as the water depth decreases. The most noticeable increase in the ratio occurs in extremely shallow water, where $m^{IG}_{0,t}/m^{TOT}_{0,t}$ values are the highest and the energy of IG components reach also the 60% of the total wave energy.

Figure 3.71 Ratio $m^{IG}_{0,t}/m^{TOT}_{0,t}$ as a function of the relative depth. The inset plot reports an example of the energy density spectrum for T4, at the wave gauge WG_6 .

In Figure 3.72 the spectral wave steepness computed at the toe of the structure is reported as a function of the relative depth (h_r). It was computed using $H_{m0,t}$ and $L_{m-1,0,t}$ where $L_{m-1,0,t}$ was calculated using the deep water wavelength formula, with the spectral wave period at the toe ($T_{m-1,0,t}$). Since the spectral shape changes significantly in extremely shallow water the wave steepness becomes very low. The increased energy at lower frequencies results in an exceptionally large spectral wave period. However, it is important to emphasize that the total wave steepness is dominated by the energy at the lower frequencies making it less representative of the wave field and the steepness of the short waves. As expected, the wave steepness ratio ($s_{m-1,0,o}/s_{m-1,0,t}$) increases from intermediate to extremely shallow water conditions. However, it should be noted that in such conditions, waves break over a wide surf zone on the foreshore and not directly on the structure slope.

Figure 3.72 Influence of the relative depth on $s_{m-1,0,o}/s_{m-1,0,t}$ for different shallowness conditions.

Pressure analysis

Hereafter, the term pressure refers exclusively to the dynamic component p' of the total pressure, expressed as: $p=p_0+p'$, where p_0 denotes the hydrostatic pressure. The signals acquired by the pressure sensors were pre-processed through standard procedures, including signal denoising, filtering, and removal of the static water level component, and subsequently analysed in both the time and frequency domains. As a preliminary step, the pressure signals were filtered using three different techniques: the Savitzky–Golay filter, the Morlet wavelet transform, and a zero-phase digital filter. The performance of the different filters was evaluated in terms of Root

Mean Square Error (RMSE). Since the zero-phase digital filter provided the lowest RMSE, it was selected and applied to both pressure and free-surface elevation signals. The filtering was performed within a frequency bandwidth defined by a minimum frequency $f_{\min}=0.03$ Hz and a maximum frequency $f_{\max}=3f_p$, where f_p is the peak frequency of the wave energy spectrum. The filtered signals were then used to investigate the temporal and spatial variability of the dynamic pore pressure within the breakwater.

For regular wave tests, the mean pressure height P_m was estimated in the time domain using a zero up-crossing analysis. For irregular wave tests, in addition to P_m , a spectral pressure height P_{m0} was computed from the pressure variance spectrum as: $P_{m0}(x)=4\sqrt{m_0}$, where m_0 is the zeroth-order spectral moment. Figure 3.73a presents an example of the temporal evolution of the dynamic pressure $p'(t)$, measured over a 20 s time window by the pore pressure transducers located at the same vertical level (Pt₁₋₂₋₃₋₇₋₈) during an irregular wave test. The corresponding free-surface elevation $\eta(t)$, measured at the breakwater toe by wave gauge WG₇, is also shown. Figure 3.73b displays the total wave energy spectra recorded offshore (WG₁), on the foreshore (WG₅), and at the breakwater toe (WG₇). Figure 3.73c illustrates the corresponding wave-induced pressure spectra measured within the breakwater core for the same test.

All test cases exhibit pronounced nonlinear wave transformations along the foreshore, including shoaling and breaking processes, as evidenced by the bimodal and flattened spectral shapes and the increasingly peaked free-surface elevation time series observed at the breakwater toe. In addition, a slight phase lag ($\tau\approx 1$ s) between the incident waves at the structure toe and the resulting pore pressure response was consistently observed (Figure 3.73a). This phase lag can be attributed to the combined effects of flow infiltration through the porous medium, the relatively low permeability of the core, and wave reflection at the structure (Brancasi et al., 2022). Under depth-limited conditions, low-frequency motions play a dominant role in controlling the hydrodynamics within the surf zone. These motions are closely linked to incident wave groups, whereby the energy associated with long-wave components increases as waves propagate shoreward, while the energy of short-wave components is progressively dissipated due to breaking. This complex reorganisation of wave energy significantly influences the pressure field inside the breakwater, particularly in shallow and very shallow water conditions. Further insights and results of the experimental campaign are reported in Scaravaglione et al. (2024).

Figure 3.73 Irregular test: $H_{o,m0} = 0.25$ m, $T_{o,p} = 2.00$ s. (a) Temporal variation of the water free surface elevation $\eta(t)$ computed at the structure toe and temporal variation of the pressure $p'(t)$. (b) Wave spectra. (c) Pressure spectra.

Damage analysis

The relationship between the damage level S and the stability number N_s , computed at the toe of the breakwater, is commonly described by a power-law relationship: $S = a(N_s)^b$, where a and b are regression coefficients determined through a nonlinear least-squares fitting of the experimental data. The exponent b governs the shape of the damage curve and is widely recognized as the key parameter for comparing damage trends derived from different experimental datasets. As highlighted by van der Meer (2021), a meaningful comparison among damage results from independent laboratory studies is only possible when the exponents of the fitted damage curves are comparable. Accordingly, in the present study, the same methodology originally proposed by van der Meer (1988) was replicated to derive the exponent of the damage fitting curve from the newly acquired experimental data. Overall, the fitted exponent b was found to lie within the range: $4.09 \leq b \leq 5.07$, corresponding to damage curve shapes varying $S \propto N_s^4$ and $S \propto N_s^5$. These values are consistent with those reported in previous studies, where an exponent close to $b=5$ is commonly adopted. In the analysis, only damage values within the range $1 \leq S \leq 15$ were considered, as larger values fall outside the range of practical relevance.

Figure 3.74 presents the experimental damage curves plotted against the stability number for both target offshore wave steepness values, together with the reference fifth-power regression line (dotted curve) for each breakwater configuration (BW_i). As expected, damage increases monotonically with increasing stability number for all configurations. No systematic differences were observed between the two target wave steepness values, indicating that, within the investigated range, wave steepness does not significantly alter the overall shape of the damage curves. For the BW_4 configuration, tested at two different water levels (WL_3 and WL_4), distinct

were observed despite the identical structural configuration. This behaviour is likely associated with differences in wave transformation processes under varying water depth conditions. Since wave steepness does not follow a unique stability relationship in deep water, it is reasonable to expect that such discrepancies become even more pronounced in shallow and very shallow water conditions.

Figure 3.74 Slope armour damage S against the stability number $N_s = H_{m0,t} / \Delta D_{n50}$.

The following subsection presents the analyses on the influence of shallow water conditions on the stability of a rock-armoured steep breakwater. This is achieved by evaluating the accuracy of the formulae developed by van Gent et al. (2003) (VG) against newly acquired experimental data. First, the accuracy of the original formula is assessed relative to this new data. Then, the formula is recalibrated to account for shallow water conditions, with the data categorised by water levels and new regression coefficients calculated. Modified version of the VG formula is also explored to fit the new experimental data and are specifically valid for the range of application investigated here, incorporating the incident wave steepness to better capture the effects of shallow water. Further insights and results are reported in Scaravaglione et al. (2025a,b).

Comparison with van Gent et al. (2003) stability formula valid in shallow water

Figure 3.75 reports the observed dimensionless damage according to the VG expression, with the experimental data aggregated into 4 groups based on the investigated water levels: intermediate (red squares, $h=0.40$ m), shallow (blue squares, $h=0.20$ m), very shallow (green and magenta squares, $h=0.10$ m), and extremely shallow (black squares, $h=0.05$ m) water. The theoretical curve (blue line, with $c_{VG}=1.75$) is also plotted. With respect to the theoretical regression line, a good prediction of damage is observed for very shallow water (tests T3 and T4) in both breakwater configurations (BW₃ and BW₄) at the same water level, regardless of the permeability. However, an overestimation of the predicted damage for intermediate/shallow water (tests T1 and T2), and an underestimation of damage for extremely shallow water (test T5) are observed. Therefore, for each water level, the formula was refitted to derive a new

regression coefficient c_{VG} , to better fit the experimental data. In these analyses, the time-domain significant wave height (H_s) is replaced with the significant spectral one (H_{m0}) to minimise the influence of spectral shape and wave nonlinearity effects compared to low exceedance time domain wave heights (e.g., H_s or $H_{2\%}$). Moreover, frequency-based parameters (H_{m0} and $T_{m-1,0}$) are commonly used in practical design and typically derived from numerical wave models, making them readily available without relying on empirical relations, unlike time domain parameters that necessitate detailed knowledge of the wave height distribution. Results show that data in intermediate ($h=0.40$ m) and shallow ($h=0.20$ m) water exhibit similar behaviour (red dotted line, $c_{VG}=2.3$) and can be clustered, whereas data in extremely shallow water ($h=0.05$ m) are well represented by van Gent et al. (2003) stability equation if a regression coefficient c_{VG} equal to 1.5 is used (black dotted line).

Figure 3.75 Refitting of the van Gent et al. (2003) formula with the new data.

From these results, the primary conclusion is that data corresponding to different water levels at the toe of the structure do not converge into a single formula and exhibit high uncertainty when $c_{VG}=1.75$ is applied uniformly for all data. Therefore, van Gent et al. (2003) equation can be adjusted to account for the effects of shallow water conditions. Figure 3.76 shows that the recalibrated van Gent formula exhibits a better agreement with the experimental data if different water levels are considered separately. In this context, the influence of the spectral wave period becomes evident. Based on these findings, a new formula is developed to fit the new experimental dataset and provide better insights into the effects of shallow water. Van Gent et al. (2003) stability equation was modified by adding the influence of the spectral wave steepness (wave period) as a function of H_{m0} . All incident wave parameters were computed at the toe of the structure and $s_{m-1,0}$ was calculated using the deep water wavelength formula, considering the incident wave parameters. Results are reported in Figure 3.76 and demonstrate that the new modified formula (Eq. 3.25), provides a better prediction of the observed damage

for the new dataset if a regression coefficient $c_{VG,new}$ equal to 3.3 is used, across the different shallowness conditions investigated in the present study.

$$\frac{H_{m0}}{\Delta D_{n50}} = c_{VG,new} \sqrt{\cot \alpha} \left(1 + \frac{D_{n50,core}}{D_{n50}} \right) s_{m-1,0}^{0.1} \left(\frac{S}{\sqrt{N_w}} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (3.25)$$

Figure 3.76 Modified van Gent et al. (2003) stability formula with the new data.

3.2.4 Numerical dataset acquired by UniSalento

This section presents the numerical datasets developed by UniSalento, based on the experimental tests previously described in Section 3.2.1. The simulations were performed using the OpenFOAM framework, coupled with the IHFOAM wave solver, to reproduce wave–structure interaction processes observed in the laboratory. Specifically, test series T1, comprising 7 irregular wave tests (BW_1, WL_1), and test series T_{reg} , including 13 regular wave tests (BW_1, WL_1-WL_{reg}), were reproduced within the CFD model. The primary objective of these numerical simulations is to calibrate and validate the CFD framework against the experimental measurements, with particular reference to free-surface elevation, and dynamic pressure signals. By systematically comparing numerical and experimental results, the numerical dataset aims to assess the capability of the OpenFOAM–IHFOAM model to accurately reproduce near-structure hydrodynamics and internal pressure response within rubble-mound breakwaters. This validation effort represents a fundamental step towards advancing the use of high-fidelity CFD tools for the investigation of wave–structure interaction phenomena, especially under depth-limited water conditions and complex loading conditions.

Description of the numerical model

The response of rubble-mound breakwaters to wave-induced loads was investigated using the IHFOAM numerical suite (Higuera et al., 2013), integrated into the open-source OpenFOAM

platform (ESI-Group, 2021). This framework is specifically developed for coastal and offshore engineering applications and incorporates advanced boundary conditions for wave and current generation and absorption, as well as dedicated solvers for porous media. The numerical approach enables the solution of both three-dimensional Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) Eqs. (3.26, 3.27) and Volume-Averaged Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (VARANS) Eqs. (3.28, 3.29), with the RANS formulation applied in the main fluid domain and the VARANS formulation adopted within the porous media domain. Finite Volume Method (FVM) is employed to discretize the governing partial differential equations in both space and time, thereby transforming them into a system of algebraic equations suitable for numerical solutions. The governing equations are expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (3.26)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + g_i + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{\tau}_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial (\overline{u'_i u'_j})}{\partial x_j} \quad (3.27)$$

where $u_i = \bar{u}_i + u'_i$ and $p = \bar{p} + p'$ are respectively the Reynolds decomposed velocity and pressure fields, ρ is the density of the fluid, g_i is the i -th component of the gravitational acceleration and $\bar{\tau}_{ij}$ is the mean viscous stress tensor. The RANS are coupled with Volume of Fluid (VoF) method to track the evolution of water free surface.

The flow inside the porous media is modeled by means of the VARANS equations, which are obtained by applying the intrinsic volume average to the RANS equations and combined with the Forchheimer's relationship (Liu et al., 1999):

$$\frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (3.28)$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle \langle \bar{u}_j \rangle}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{p} \rangle}{\partial x_i} + g_i + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{\tau}_{ij} \rangle}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \langle \overline{u'_i u'_j} \rangle}{\partial x_j} - \quad (3.29)$$

$$\left[\frac{\alpha_F v (1-n)^2}{n^2 D_{n50}^2} \right] \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle + \frac{\beta_F (1-n)}{n D_{n50}} \sqrt{\langle \bar{u}_1 \rangle^2 + \langle \bar{u}_2 \rangle^2} \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle + c_F \frac{1-n}{n} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial t}$$

where v is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid, D_{n50} and n are respectively the median nominal diameter and the porosity of the porous media, α_F and β_F are two empirical coefficients which take in to account frictional forces induced by Darcy-type flow and turbulent flow (Van Gent 1995), respectively. The coefficient c_F represents the added-mass effect. The best-fit values for α_F and β_F should be evaluated by comparing experimental data and numerical results (Losada et al., 2008).

The stabilized k - ω SST turbulence model was adopted in the simulations to limit turbulence overproduction (Larsen and Fuhrman, 2018). Initial conditions were kept constant across all numerical simulations and correspond to still water, with the initial velocity set to $u = 0$. Wave generation was performed using the native IHFOAM wave-generation library, adopting a single paddle wavemaker. Lateral boundaries were treated with slip/zeroGradient-type conditions to

enforce a quasi-two-dimensional configuration, consistent with typical experimental wave flume setups. Wave absorption boundary conditions are then applied. Specifically, the active wave absorption is set to the generation section (Schaffer and Klopman, 2000) while shallow water absorb condition is set at the outlet boundary.

Numerical model setup and simulations

The numerical framework is based on the accurate reproduction of the wave flume geometry and the experimental conditions described in Section 3.2.1, with calibration performed through comparison against experimental data obtained in the same position of wave gauges and pressure transducers. The 2D simulations were carried out within a numerical wave flume with a total length of 35 m along x axis and a height of 4 m along z axis. The dimension along y direction is considered negligible. These values were selected to adequately take in to account the air-water interaction effects and to minimize undesired air induced turbulence associated with the proximity of the domain boundaries in the vertical direction. The tested structure was placed according to the coordinate system and layout adopted in the reference experimental study.

Numerical model flume calibration: free surface elevation

A preliminary sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify the optimal spatial and time discretization. To this end, several mesh resolutions were tested to assess the level of agreement with the experimental laboratory data but following the guidelines provided by Jacobsen et al. (2012), a uniform mesh was employed to achieve a consistent resolution of the free surface dynamics and to maintain numerical stability of the VoF formulation. The optimal time discretization was determined based on the Courant number, for which numerical stability was ensured for values below 0.2. A Courant number of 0.18 was therefore selected as a compromise between numerical accuracy and computational efficiency. All the calibration tests were performed using test T1_02_1000 as experimental reference.

Figure 3.77 illustrates the results of the mesh sensitivity analysis, in which the starting calibration parameter for the selection of the cell size was the significant wave height H_m , for regular wave tests and H_{m0} for irregular wave conditions. It can be observed that the most accurate results are obtained using the finest mesh, characterized by the smallest cell size. This finding is consistent with previous validation studies, which recommend to select the spatial resolution as a fraction of the wave height, typically around $H/10$ for regular waves and $H_{m0}/10$ for irregular ones, to ensure an appropriate resolution of the free surface dynamics and wave kinematics (Chen et al., 2021, Irias Mata and Van Gent 2023). To ensure physical reliability while maintaining a reasonable balance with computational cost, it is good practice to apply the finest spatial discretization only in the proximity of the free surface, where accurate wave propagation is critical, while allowing coarser resolution in regions of lower relevance. Accordingly, a mesh configuration with a base cell size of $H_{m0}/5$ was adopted, with local refinement to $H_{m0}/10$ at the air–water interface. This strategy was found to preserve the same level of accuracy while reducing the overall computational time by approximately 30%.

Figure 3.77 Mesh sensitivity analysis.

An additional calibration analysis was carried out to consider bottom-friction effects induced by the wave flume bed. In OpenFOAM, these effects can be represented through turbulence wall functions. In this context, the calibration parameter was the Nikuradse roughness coefficient K_s , which characterizes the effective physical roughness of the bed material and controls the near-wall velocity profile. Both the classical smooth wall formulation, corresponding to $K_s = 0$ and several rough wall configurations with higher values of K_s were tested to assess the sensitivity of the numerical results to bed roughness effects.

Figure 3.78 presents the results obtained for the different values of K_s tested. The simulation performed with $K_s = 40 \times 10^{-6}$ shows the closest agreement with the experimental measurements. This value is therefore adopted for all next simulations.

Figure 3.78 Sensitivity analysis of the Nikuradse roughness parameter.

Calibrated the previous numerical parameters, the reliability of the numerical wave flume is assessed. All 7 irregular test cases listed in Table 3.II are reproduced without the structure and the numerical results are systematically compared with the corresponding experimental data. Wave spectra are computed for the qualitative (Figure 3.79) and quantitative results (Table 3.III) presented below.

Table 3.LI Characteristics of the experimental wave tests motion used to calibrate the numerical model.

Sea state ID	H_{m0} [m]	T_p [s]	h_{off} [m]	h_{toe} [m]	N_w [n. of waves]	duration [s]
T1_02_1000	0.25	2.83	1.16	0.4	1000	2622
T1_03_1000	0.2	2.53	1.16	0.4	1000	2350
T1_04_1000	0.3	2.19	1.16	0.4	1000	2042
T1_05_1000	0.25	2.00	1.16	0.4	1000	1868
T1_06_1000	0.2	1.79	1.16	0.4	1000	1676
T1_07_1000	0.16	1.60	1.16	0.4	1000	1505
T1_08_1000	0.16	2.26	1.16	0.4	1000	2107

T1_02_1000

T1_03_1000

Figure 3.79 Wave spectra of Experimental data (red) and Numerical simulations (blue).

Table 3.LII Exp. and num. spectral parameters in terms of percentage difference %err (if %err > 0, Exp > Num).

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	H_{m0} % err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	T_p % err [-]
1	0.2473	0.2570	3.92	2.7699	2.8248	1.98
2	0.2428	0.2493	2.66	2.7746	2.8494	2.70
3	0.2337	0.2453	4.96	2.8151	2.8643	1.75
4	0.2391	0.2461	2.96	2.8007	2.8568	2.01
5	0.2380	0.2451	2.97	2.7911	2.8444	1.91
6	0.2321	0.2417	4.14	2.7840	2.8469	2.26
7	0.2261	0.2393	5.85	2.7864	2.8519	2.35
8	0.2075	0.2255	8.67	2.8248	2.8794	1.93

T1_02_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	H_{m0} % err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	T_p % err [-]
1	0.2111	0.2135	1.17	2.5033	2.5323	1.16
2	0.2137	0.2093	-2.06	2.5033	2.5680	2.59
3	0.2065	0.2098	1.59	2.5323	2.5863	2.13
4	0.2134	0.2112	-1.02	2.5560	2.6068	1.99
5	0.2151	0.2094	-2.68	2.5461	2.6006	2.14
6	0.2127	0.2086	-1.94	2.5343	2.5924	2.29
7	0.2081	0.2078	-0.14	2.5343	2.5883	2.13
8	0.1937	0.2017	4.17	2.5781	2.6256	1.84

T1_03_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	$H_{m0}\%$ err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	$T_p\%$ err [-]
1	0.2976	0.3013	1.26	2.1264	2.1601	1.58
2	0.2718	0.2780	2.26	2.1319	2.2428	5.20
3	0.2476	0.2695	8.82	2.1586	2.2521	4.33
4	0.2474	0.2665	7.73	2.1933	2.2096	0.74
5	0.2490	0.2626	5.46	2.2111	2.2186	0.34
6	0.2467	0.2590	4.98	2.2096	2.3109	4.58
7	0.2422	0.2575	6.33	2.2066	2.3174	5.02
8	0.2104	0.2315	10.02	2.2261	2.3456	5.37

T1_04_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	$H_{m0}\%$ err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	$T_p\%$ err [-]
1	0.2538	0.2613	2.96	1.9321	1.9622	1.56
2	0.2417	0.2350	-2.78	1.9389	2.0190	4.13
3	0.2279	0.2300	0.92	1.9622	2.0252	3.21
4	0.2252	0.2274	0.97	1.9716	2.0570	4.33
5	0.2264	0.2291	1.15	1.9740	2.0328	2.98
6	0.2265	0.2270	0.21	1.9752	2.0265	2.60
7	0.2239	0.2249	0.44	1.9775	2.0290	2.60
8	0.1981	0.2084	5.21	1.9956	2.0493	2.69

T1_05_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	$H_{m0}\%$ err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	$T_p\%$ err [-]
1	0.2155	0.2173	0.81	1.7751	1.7847	0.54
2	0.2007	0.1930	-3.83	1.7789	1.7916	0.71
3	0.1943	0.1937	-0.3	1.8368	1.8174	-1.05
4	0.1912	0.1916	0.20	1.7799	1.7995	1.10
5	0.1911	0.1908	-0.15	1.7551	1.8316	4.36
6	0.1941	0.1919	-1.15	1.8597	1.8347	-1.34
7	0.1940	0.1922	-0.93	1.8576	1.8276	-1.62
8	0.1838	0.1886	2.57	1.8215	1.8124	-0.50

T1_06_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	$H_{m0}\%$ err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	$T_p\%$ err [-]
1	0.1688	0.1703	0.90	1.5515	1.5938	2.72
2	0.1565	0.1428	-8.72	1.5861	1.6158	1.87
3	0.1536	0.1430	-6.89	1.5876	1.6110	1.47
4	0.1511	0.1421	-5.92	1.5604	1.6417	5.21
5	0.1526	0.1421	-6.84	1.6400	1.6286	-0.70
6	0.1527	0.1434	-6.10	1.6000	1.6190	1.19
7	0.1519	0.1411	-7.11	1.5739	1.6206	2.97
8	0.1454	0.1410	-3.03	1.6433	1.6516	0.50

T1_07_1000

Wave Gauge	H_{m0} exp [m]	H_{m0} num [m]	H_{m0} % err [-]	T_p exp [s]	T_p num [s]	T_p % err [-]
1	0.1679	0.1706	1.63	2.1845	2.2201	1.63
2	0.1669	0.1674	0.31	2.2306	2.2835	2.37
3	0.1649	0.1697	2.94	2.2096	2.2851	3.42
4	0.1667	0.1695	1.69	2.2261	2.2787	2.36
5	0.1695	0.1696	0.05	2.2490	2.3060	2.53
6	0.1712	0.1712	0.00	2.2459	2.3158	3.11
7	0.1695	0.1710	0.86	2.2352	2.3158	3.6
8	0.1609	0.1685	4.71	2.2428	2.3339	4.06

T1_08_1000

Despite some discrepancies primarily associated with the wave-absorption boundary conditions, which may not be fully suitable across all water-depth regimes, the validation of the waves in the numerical wave tank can be considered successful.

Numerical model flume calibration: internal pressure

The regular test T1_REG_001C (BW₁ and WL₁) was selected as reference case for calibration of Darcy-Forchheimer parameters for the three different layers. The coefficients β_F and c_F are assumed 0 in the core, a condition that reproduces laminar flow behavior, typically observed at model scale (Campos et al., 2020, Celli et al., 2021). Table 3.LIII summarizes the configuration of the porosity parameters implemented in the simulations of each layer of the rubble-mound structure.

Table 3.LIII Calibration Test with regular sea state.

Sea state ID	H_{m0} [m]	T_p [s]	h_{off} [m]	h_{toe} [m]	N_w [n. of waves]	duration [s]
1	0.2	2.00	1.16	0.4	50	150

Table 3.LIV Porous layers parameters tested in the calibration phase.

Configuration	Armour			Filter			Core		
	α_F	β_F	c_F	α_F	β_F	c_F	α_F	β_F	c_F
1 (Celli et al., 2021)	1000	3	0.34	1000	3	0.34	200	0	0
2	1000	1	0.34	1000	2	0.34	500	0	0
3	1000	1	0.34	1000	2	0.34	700	0	0
4	1000	2	0.34	1000	1	0.34	500	0	0
5	1000	0.5	0.34	1000	0.5	0.34	500	0	0

The results at the eight pressure transducers placed within the structure are reported. In this phase, the qualitative results of the best setup (Configuration 2) are presented in Figure 3.80, while quantitative assessment in terms of mean pressure values for every configuration is provided in Table 3.LV.

Figure 3.80 Pressure evolution in mwc: Experimental (red) and Numerical (blue).

Table 3.LV Exp. and num.l parameters in terms of percentage difference %err (if %err > 0, Exp > Num) for the tested configurations.

Pressure transducer	P_m exp [m]	P_m num [m]	P_m % err [-]	T exp [s]	T num [s]	T % err [-]
1	0.0828	0.0603	-27.234	2.0000	2.0013	0.065
2	0.0461	0.0269	-41.62	1.9982	2.0038	0.280
3	0.0225	0.0185	-18.103	1.9694	2.0038	1.748
4	0.0731	0.0444	-39.293	1.9996	2.0047	0.255
5	0.0367	0.0286	-22.058	2.0035	2.0038	0.015
6	0.0457	0.0264	-42.12	2.0039	2.0047	0.036
7	0.0075	0.0095	27.723	1.9629	2.0030	2.040
8	0.0008	0.0042	411.045	0.3990	2.0038	0.941

Configuration 1

Pressure transducer	P_m exp [m]	P_m num [m]	P_m % err [-]	T exp [s]	T num [s]	T % err [-]
1	0.0828	0.0736	-11.135	2.0000	2.0009	0.043
2	0.0461	0.0399	-13.378	1.9982	2.0042	0.301
3	0.0225	0.0236	4.565	1.9694	2.0025	1.683
4	0.0731	0.0597	-18.327	1.9996	2.0051	0.277
5	0.0367	0.0441	19.994	2.0035	2.0042	0.036
6	0.0457	0.0491	7.451	2.0039	2.0047	0.036
7	0.0075	0.0066	-11.681	1.9629	1.9966	1.713
8	0.0008	0.0009	7.793	0.3990	1.9961	0.945

Configuration 2

Pressure transducer	P_m exp [m]	P_m num [m]	P_m % err [-]	T exp [s]	T num [s]	T % err [-]
1	0.0828	0.0778	-6.12	2.0000	2.0013	0.065
2	0.0461	0.0410	-11.048	1.9982	2.0042	0.301
3	0.0225	0.0227	0.834	1.9694	2.0025	1.683
4	0.0731	0.0629	-14.005	1.9996	2.0055	0.298
5	0.0367	0.0456	24.176	2.0035	2.0047	0.058
6	0.0457	0.0518	13.568	2.0039	2.0047	0.036
7	0.0075	0.0046	-37.941	1.9629	1.9965	1.710
8	0.0008	0.0004	-54.843	0.3990	2.1085	0.887

Configuration 3

Pressure transducer	P_m exp [m]	P_m num [m]	P_m % err [-]	T exp [s]	T num [s]	T % err [-]
1	0.0828	0.0706	-14.851	2.0000	2.0005	0.024
2	0.0461	0.0346	-23.881	1.9982	2.0042	0.094
3	0.0225	0.0205	-9.171	1.9694	2.0028	1.887
4	0.0731	0.0551	-24.874	1.9996	2.0057	0.331
5	0.0367	0.0378	2.914	2.0035	2.0042	0.047
6	0.0457	0.0417	-8.645	2.0039	2.0052	0.071
7	0.0075	0.0061	-18.41	1.9629	1.9962	1.835
8	0.0008	0.0008	-3.26	0.3990	1.9966	0.942

Configuration 4

Pressure transducer	P_m exp [m]	P_m num [m]	P_m % err [-]	T exp [s]	T num [s]	T % err [-]
1	0.0828	0.0800	-3.406	2.0000	2.0017	0.086
2	0.0461	0.0495	7.386	1.9982	2.0047	0.323
3	0.0225	0.0335	48.479	1.9694	2.0030	1.705
4	0.0731	0.0703	-3.794	1.9996	2.0055	0.298
5	0.0367	0.0554	50.782	2.0035	2.0042	0.036
6	0.0457	0.0615	34.700	2.0039	2.0047	0.036
7	0.0075	0.0085	13.854	1.9629	1.9970	1.735
8	0.0008	0.0011	38.021	0.3990	1.9978	0.961

Configuration 5

The analysis of the results demonstrates that the calibration of the Forchheimer coefficients would benefit from further investigation. While the current numerical predictions show a generally good level of agreement with experimental data, some discrepancies are still observed. A more extensive sensitivity analysis of these coefficients is therefore considered necessary to reduce these differences. This step is particularly important to ensure a reliable and physically consistent representation of the internal pressure distribution within the breakwater.

3.3 Failure mechanisms of vertical breakwaters

3.3.1 Reliability of Goda's formula for quasi-static wave forces

Experiments

In the late 1980's and early 1990s, 2D laboratory experiments on small scale models of vertical breakwaters were carried out at the Danish Hydraulic Institute (DK) and Delft Hydraulics (NL). Later two cases were added from CEDEX-CEPYC, Spain, and ENEL-CRIS, Italy. This data base was reanalysed by van der Meer et al. (1994) to assess the reliability of Goda's formulae in the perspective of a probabilistic calculation (level II and level III).

A total of eleven cases has been re-analyzed with respect to wave forces and moments on vertical structures. Details on caisson geometry, foreshore slopes, wave conditions and horizontal forces were stored in a database as presented in Juhl and van der Meer (1992). The analysis of horizontal forces is also described in van der Meer et al. (1992). Vertical forces and overturning moments were treated later by Bruining (1994).

Van der Meer et al. (1994) considered three categories of structures, namely vertical superstructure, inclined superstructure, and curved superstructure. In Figure 3.81, an example of each of these three categories is shown.

Figure 3.81 Different superstructures used in the analysis.

The significant and maximum wave heights in front of the vertical structure were calculated by formulae developed by Goda (2010). Only total wave forces measured by means of strain gauge are considered; this means that local wave impacts are not treated, as they cannot be measured by this measuring technique. Therefore, results discussed below concern solely pulsating (quasi-static) loads.

Generated random sea states lasted 1000-3000 waves. Based on the recordings, the horizontal and vertical forces and horizontal and vertical overturning moments at the heel of the caisson were tabulated, with exceedance frequencies of 0.1%, 0.4%, 1%, 2% and 5% respectively. 134 experiments were used for horizontal forces and moments, 31 tests were selected for the uplift forces and moments, which were treated in the same way as the horizontal forces.

Results

In Figures 3.83 and 3.84 the measured horizontal forces, $F_{0.4\%}$, are compared with the horizontal forces calculated by Goda's formula, F_{Goda} . Due to the various structure geometries, foreshore slopes, wave characteristics, etc., a significant scatter in the measured wave forces was found. Note that for inclined and recurved superstructures, the Goda force has been calculated considering only the vertical part of the breakwater. This is because of the delay of load peak on the crown.

Figure 3.82 Calculated $F_{0.4\%}$ horizontal force vs. Goda's formula. Breakwaters with vertical superstructures.

Figure 3.83 Calculated $F_{0.4\%}$ horizontal force vs. Goda's formula for breakwaters with inclined and curved superstructures. The calculated Goda force ignores the presence of superstructures.

Based on the available data, for each component of wave forcing, the ratio:

$$r = \frac{F_{Goda}}{F_{0.4\%}} \quad (3.30)$$

was treated as a log-normal distributed random variable, whose average and standard deviation is reported in Table 3.LVI. Note that reported values refer to the variable r itself and not to its logarithmic transform.

Table 3.LVII. Average and Standard Deviation of r

Wave loading Component	Symbol	Average	Standard Deviation
Horizontal force	r_{Fh}	0.83	0.25
Horizontal moment at the heel	r_{Mh}	0.75	0.40
Vertical Force	r_{Fv}	0.71	0.25
Vertical Moment at the heel	r_{Mv}	0.67	0.37

In all cases the average of r is smaller than one, indicating overprediction by the Goda formulae. The most important conclusion, though, is that the standard deviations are large, with variation coefficients, σ/μ in the order of 30-50%. Thus, it can be concluded that the Goda method gives only a rough estimation of the forces and moments.

As a further analysis, the various percentiles of wave loadings (0.1%, 0.4%, 1%, 2% and 5%) were fitted with a two parameter Weibull distribution, leading to the following equation describing the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of extreme forces:

$$Prob(f_r \leq F_r) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(2.35 \cdot \frac{F_r}{F_{r,0.4\%}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.31)$$

where the subscript r refers to any of the wave loading components in Table 3.LVI. Therefore, by combining Eqs. (3.30) and (3.31) one obtains:

$$Prob(f_r \leq F_r) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{2.35}{r} \cdot \frac{F_r}{F_{r,Goda}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.32)$$

which includes both the inherent randomness of wave forces (due to wave randomness) and the uncertainties related to the Goda's model (via the variable r).

3.3.2 Impact Wave Loadings- The EU database from the PROVERBS project

Introduction

Under the Research Project "PROVERBS" ('PRObabilistic design tools for VERTical BreakwaterS'), included in the European Programme "Marine Advanced Science and Technology" (MAST III), a wide ensemble of hydraulic model tests was carried out to investigate the role of impact wave loadings in the failure of vertical and vertically composite breakwaters (Figure 3.84).

Figure 3.84 Vertically composite breakwater's geometric variables.

In his comprehensive work of 1994, Oumeraci gave an account of reasons leading to those failures pointing out that, although the failure mechanisms are related to different aspects, closely interconnected, of hydrodynamic, geotechnical, morphological and structural nature, wave breaking represents the most frequent damage source even in cases where depth – induced breaking is not expected (Figure 3.85). He also indicated that the high irregularity and short-crestedness of real sea states strongly affect the breaking mechanism, so that it appears very difficult to avoid totally impact loads occurrence due to waves breaking, even in deep water.

Figure 3.85 Breaking waves on vertical breakwater.

Experimental work

The PROVERBS data base encompasses both 2D and 3D hydraulic model tests conducted with both regular and random waves at various geometric scales.

Bidimensional model tests were performed:

- in 1993 at the *Franzius Institut of the University of Hannover* in the mid-size wave flume “*Wellenkanal Shneiderberg*” (WKS93);
- in 1993, 1994 and 1997 at Hannover in the large wave flume “*GrossWellenKanal*” of the Coastal Research Center (GWK93/94; CER197);
- in 1994 at *HR Wallingford* in the “*Deep Random Wave Flume*” (HR94);
- in 1997 at the *University of Edinburgh* (UE97) in a small scale flume;

- in 1997 at the *University of Naples Federico II* (UN97) in a small scale flume.

These tests are described in more detail, respectively, Kortenhaus and Oumeraci (1998), Allsop et al. (1996), Vicinanza (1997), Bruce and Vicinanza (1998), Vicinanza (1998).

Tridimensional experiments were conducted in 1995 in the UK national *Coastal Research Facility, CRF, at HR Wallingford* (HR95) and are illustrated in Allsop and Calabrese (1999).

In the experiments three different bed slopes were employed:

- 1:75 and 1:50 indicative of shallow sand beach slope (CERI97, HR94, GWK93/94 and WKS93);
- 1:20 indicative of steeper sand beaches (HR95, UE97 and UN97).

Description of model tests

Bidimensional tests at the University of Hannover (WKS93)

Small scale model tests were performed at the Franzius-Institut, University of Hannover, Germany, in a mid-size wave flume (*WellenKanal Schneiderberg*) of 110 m length, 2.2 m width and 2.0 m depth. A sand filled caisson 0.91 m high was based over a rubble mound foundation 0.41 m high and with a seaward front slope of 1:2. No further geometry was investigated. Both regular and irregular waves were generated. Irregular waves were characterized at the calibration by deep water steepness $s_{m,0} = 0.01 - 0.11$ and by wave heights $H_{s,0} = 0.10 - 0.35$ m. Each test was run for at least 100 waves. Water depths of 0.90 m up to 1.20 m in the flume were used. To measure the characteristics of the waves, a set of wave gauges were used, while wave loads were measured by a set of 16 pressure transducers distributed over the bottom (n.5) and the front face of the caisson (n.11). Video camera recordings of wave shapes at the structure were taken.

Bidimensional large scale model tests at Hannover (GWK93/94; CERI97)

Large scale model tests were conducted in 1993, 1994 and 1997 in the Large Wave Flume of Hannover (*GrossWellenKanal*) of the Coastal Research Center (FZK, a joint institution of the University of Hannover and the Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany).

Tests performed in 1993/1994 refer to a caisson 2.76 m high, based on a rubble mound foundation 1.020 m high with a front slope of 1:1.5. Both regular and irregular waves (TMA spectra) were generated. Irregular waves were characterised at the calibration by deep water steepness $s_{m,0} = 0.005 - 0.016$ and by wave heights $H_{s,0} = 0.30 - 1.10$ m. Each test was run for at least 100 waves. Water depths of 3.70 m up to 4.30 m were used.

Model tests conducted in 1997 refer to a joint research project between Port and Harbour Research Institute, Japan, and Leichtweiss-Institute, Germany, to investigate the hydraulic performance of an innovative structure based on the concept of a high mound composite breakwater. It consists of a very high rubble foundation, in the model 1.75 m high with a front slope of 1:3, and of a superstructure smaller than the standard vertical wall, formed by a permeable front wall and an impermeable back wall. Both regular and irregular waves (PM spectra) were generated. Irregular waves were characterised at the calibration by deep water steepness $s_{m,0} = 0.01 - 0.03$ and by wave periods $T_p = 3.6$ s, 5.0 s and 7.0 s. Each test was run for at least 200 waves. Water depths of 2.05 m up to 2.875 m were used.

To measure the characteristics of the waves and the loads, a set of wave gauges and pressure cells distributed over the structures were used. Video camera recordings of wave shapes at the structure were taken.

Bidimensional tests at HR Wallingford (HR94)

Experiments were carried out in the “Deep Random Wave Flume”. It is 52 m long and 1.20 m wide at the point where measurements were taken. The vertical structure was built with a stiff plywood box 0.69 m high. The model was designed to be tested at up to 5 water levels (each 0.09 m apart in the model starting from 0.34 m). All 5 water levels were used during the tests, but not for all structures. As well as a simple vertical wall, 10 structures with different mound geometry were tested in the study. The main geometric features of the test structures are summarized in Table 3.LVII.

Table 3.LVIII. Breakwater’s characteristics for HR94 experiments

Structure’s code number	$cot\alpha$	h_b [m]	B_b [m]
0	vertical	-	-
1	2	0.187	0.250
2	2	0.367	0.250
3	2	0.367	0.250
4	3	0.367	0.250
5	1.5	0.367	0.250
6	2	0.367	0.375
7	2	0.367	0.500
8	2	0.457	0.250
9	2	0.367	0.250
10	2	0.457	0.250

Mean JONSWAP spectra were generated for all the tests. Wave conditions were characterized by three nominal deep water steepnesses $s_{m,0} = 0.02, 0.04$ and 0.06 and by nominal significant wave height $H_{s,0} = 0.10 - 0.25$ m. Each test was run for at least 500 waves. To measure the characteristic of the waves, a set of resistance probes were sampled at 20 Hz. Wave loads were measured by a set of 8 pressure transducers in the front face of the caisson. Video camera recordings of wave shapes in front of the structure were taken.

Bidimensional tests at the University of Edinburgh (UE97)

Experiments were executed in a laboratory flume 20 m long and 0.40 m wide. Tests refer to a caisson 0.316 m high based on a rubble mound foundation 0.16 m high with a front slope of 1:2 and berm width of 0.36 m. Water depths of 0.25 m and 0.31 m were used. Mean JONSWAP spectra were generated for all the tests. Wave conditions were characterized by nominal deep water steepness $s_{m,0} = 0.04 - 0.08$ and by nominal significant wave heights $H_{s,0} = 0.056 - 0.121$ m. Each test comprised approximately 1000 waves and was run at least twice to allow PIV measurements. Pressure on the front face of the caisson were measured by a set of 7 pressure transducers.

Bidimensional tests at the University of Naples (UN97)

All experiments were conducted in a wave flume 26 m long and 0.5 m wide. The caisson was formed as a cube in plexiglass 0.50 m wide and 0.50 m high. The vertical structure was built with two different mound geometries 0.10 m high, with front slope 1:2 and berm width of 0.20 m and 0.36 m respectively. The water depth in front of the structure was constant and equal to 0.21 m. Mean JONSWAP spectra were generated for all the tests. Wave conditions were characterised by nominal deep-water steepness $s_{m,0} = 0.04 - 0.08$ and by nominal significant wave heights $H_{s,0} = 0.06 - 0.10$ m. Each test was run for at least 1000 waves. To measure the characteristics of the waves, a set of resistance probes was sampled at 20 Hz. Wave loads were recorded by 5 pressure transducers installed on the front face of the caisson. Pressure data were acquired simultaneously at a rate of 1000 Hz. Video camera recordings of wave shapes in front of the structure were taken.

Tridimensional tests at the HR Wallingford (HR95)

Tridimensional tests were performed in the UK national Coastal Research Facility (CRF) at HR Wallingford by a team of Italian and English researchers. The CRF wave basin measures 52 m by 27 m, and is equipped with 72 multi-axis piston paddles to give oblique long crested or short crested waves. The model was designed to be tested at water levels 0.77 m and 0.68 m above the basin floor, giving depths at the structure toe of 0.52 m and 0.43 m respectively. The measurement caisson, built of a marine plywood box constructed on rubble foundation, was 1.20 m long and fitted with eighteen pressure transducers in three vertical rows. As well as simple vertical wall, 3 structures with different mound geometry were utilized characterized by front slope 1:2, berm width 0.250m and berm height of 0.187 m, 0.287 m, 0.337 m respectively.

Mean JONSWAP spectra were generated for all the tests. Wave conditions were characterised by three nominal deep - water conditions $s_{m,0} = 0.02, 0.04$ and 0.06 and by nominal significant wave heights $H_{s,0} = 0.10 - 0.25$ m. Tests on each structure were run for at least 500 waves and were conducted in three phases:

- long crested waves with angle of attack $\beta = 0^\circ$
- long crested oblique waves with $\beta = 15^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 45°
- short crested waves with mean wave direction $\beta_0 = 0^\circ$ and with directional dispersion index $n = 2$ or $n = 6$ which values are generally appropriate to describe wind waves ranging from disorganized to more organized sea state conditions.

The directional spreading function adopted is expressed by a cosine power form:

$$D_n(\beta; \beta_0) = A_n \cos^n(\beta - \beta_0) \quad \text{for } |\beta - \beta_0| \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (3.33)$$

where A_n is a normalizing factor.

Wave profile at the wall and loading cases

The combined analysis of video-camera recordings and pressures records made it possible to distinguish at the wall in addition to the classic shape of a standing wave, the following main breaking conditions, similar to Oumeraci et al. (1993) and Hattori et al. (1994):

1. *Upward-deflected breakers*, characterized by the rapid rise of the wave surface along the wall just before the wave crest overturns and hits the wall (Figure 3.86). This rapid

rise constitutes the main reason for the delay in the development of breaking on the wall.

2. *Breaking waves with almost vertical front* surface at the moment of impact bring about impulsive pressures with very high magnitude and short duration (Figure 3.87).
3. *Plunging breaker with small or large cushion of air*. In this case a well-developed jet of water is projected from the crest of the wave at high velocity. If the wave front curls before hitting the wall, a small air pocket will be trapped in the vicinity of the impinging region of the wave crest (Figure 3.88). The thin air pocket generates high impact pressures with very short duration and pressure oscillation with high frequency. With increasing distance between the wave breaking position and the wall a large amount of air will be trapped between the wave and the wall which results in a decrease in the peak pressure magnitude.
4. *Broken waves*. This wave condition is observed when the onset of breaking starts so early that the breaker collapse occurs before reaching the wall (Figure 3.89). Typically, the foam-covered bore front first strikes the wall and is then compressed by the following impacting water mass. This impact is considerably damped by the preceding foamy mass.

Figure 3.86 Sequence of video frames and pressure signal at s.w.l. for an upward deflected breaker.

Figure 3.87 Video frames and pressure signal at s.w.l. for a plunging breaker.

Figure 3.88 Sequence of video frames and pressure signal at s.w.l. for a well-developed plunging breaker.

Figure 3.89 Sequence of video frames and pressure signal at s.w.l. for a broken wave.

Breaking waves with flat fronts and plunging breakers cause *impulsive wave loadings (impact)* with high pressure close to swl (2 to more than 10 times the incident wave height, Figure 3.90) and pressure rise times at the swl less than 0.01 the mean wave period of the sea-state, T_m (Figure 3.91). On the other hand, quasi-standing waves have pressure rise times in the order of $0.1 T_m$ and cause pulsating quasi static peaks; finally, *Upward deflected and Broken waves* cause intermediate (0.01-0.1) rise times and loading magnitudes slightly larger than quasi standing waves (*Slightly breaking loadings*). In Figure 3.90, pulsating loadings and slightly breaking loadings are labelled as “non-impact waves”.

Figure 3.90 Example of comparison between Impact and Non Impact wave pressure at swl.

Figure 3.91 Example of distribution of wave pressure rise-time, t_r , at the swl. Rise times are made non-dimensional by the mean wave period in the sea state, T_m .

3.3.3 Predicting the percentage of impact waves in a sea-state

Under “PROVERBS”, a parameter decision map has been developed to provide easy guidance to identifying the possible loading cases of waves attacking the front face of a simple vertical or composite breakwater starting from dimensionless parameters based on structure geometry, water depth and wave conditions in the nearfield (Oumeraci et al., 1999). However, in the “*Parameter Map*”, the wave impact occurrence is treated as a dichotomic event (YES/NO) and its probability remains unknown.

To overcome this limitation, Calabrese (1998, 1999) has proposed a breaking criterion, which provides an upper limit to the percentage of impulsive loading events in a sea-state. The development of the breaking criterion relies on previous theoretical work by Oumeraci et al. (1993) and extensive 2D random wave experiments, mostly collected in Vicinanza (1997). The Calabrese’s approach was lately refined in Calabrese and Buccino (2000) and then applied to a wider data base, including 3D experiments.

The calculation method can be summarized as follows.

First, a limiting wave height for wave breaking occurrence at a vertical or vertically composite breakwater is computed according to the formula (see Figure 3.84):

$$H_{bc} = 0.1025 \cdot L_p \cdot \tanh\left(2\pi \cdot k_b \cdot \frac{h_s}{L_p}\right) \quad (3.34)$$

where L_p is the local peak wavelength at the toe of the breakwater. The correction factor k_b :

$$k_b = 0.0076 \cdot \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d}\right)^2 - 0.1402 \cdot \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d}\right) + 1 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \frac{B_{eq}}{d} \leq 10 \quad (3.35)$$

accounts for the effects of the mound berm. In Eq. (3.35), the “equivalent berm width”, B_{eq} , is given by (Figure 3.84):

$$B_{eq} = B_b + \frac{h_b}{2 \cdot \tan\alpha} \quad (3.36)$$

Therefore, an increase in berm dimensions (width and/or height) reflects in a reduction of the limiting wave height, favouring the occurrence of breaking waves at the wall.

Secondly, a further limiting wave height (H_{bro}) is calculated, which predicts the occurrence of broken waves. H_{bro} represents the individual wave that breaks at a distance from the structure equal to 5 times its height. Therefore, the predictive equation is:

$$H_{bro} = 0.1025 \cdot L_p \cdot \tanh\left[\frac{2\pi \cdot k_b}{L_p} \cdot (h' + 5 \cdot H_{bro} \cdot \tan\alpha')\right] \quad (3.37)$$

Eq. (3.37) should be solved iteratively. First, one supposes that H_{bro} breaks on the foreshore; thus, k_b is set equal to 1, $h' = h_s$ and $\tan\alpha'$ corresponds to the bottom angle. Once H_{bro} has been calculated, it is necessary to verify that:

$$5 \cdot H_{bro} > B_{eq} \quad (3.38)$$

If the above criterion is not met, the calculation restarts with k_b computed according to Eq. (3.35), $h' = d$ and $\tan\alpha'$ equal to the berm slope.

However, for breakwaters placed in intermediate depth, where no breaking occurs in the absence of the structure, the following regression formula can be used:

$$H_{bro} = \left[0.013 \cdot \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d}\right)^2 + 0.04 \cdot \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d}\right) + 0.74 \right] \cdot H_{bc} \quad (3.39)$$

Once H_{bc} and H_{bro} have been achieved, the percentage of impacting waves is calculated as:

$$P_i = \exp \left[-2 \cdot \left(\frac{H_{bc}}{H_{si}}\right)^2 \right] \quad (3.40)$$

if:

$$\frac{H_{si}}{H_{bro}} \leq 0.6 \quad (3.41)$$

and:

$$P_i = \exp \left[-2 \cdot \left(\frac{H_{bc}}{H_{si}}\right)^2 \right] - 0.58 \cdot \exp \left[-1.93 \cdot \left(\frac{H_{bc}}{H_{si}}\right)^2 \right] \quad (3.42)$$

otherwise.

It is worth noticing that in the previous equations H_{si} is the significant wave height of the incident sea-state, calculated at the toe of the structure in the absence of the wall. Therefore, the method here discussed accounts for the effect of wave reflection implicitly.

Figures 3.93 and 3.94 show the comparison with 2D and 3D tests respectively. The agreement is overall reasonable. The scatter between calculated ($P_{i,calc}$) and observed ($P_{i,meas}$) values can be considered normal distributed with average 0 and standard deviation 0.0241. Hence, the confidence interval of P_{calc} with coefficient 0.9 can be fixed as ± 0.0387 . It should be noted, however, that under oblique wave attack, as expected, the proposed model over-estimates the occurrence of impacts.

Figure 3.92 Observed vs Computed impact percentage for 2d tests.

Figure 3.93 Observed vs Computed impact percentage for 3d tests.

3.3.4 Horizontal Forces on a caisson of finite length

Based on the occurrence of both quasi-static and impact events in a sea state, the exceedance probability of a horizontal force magnitude, F , in a sea-state can be calculated as follows:

$$Prob(f > F) = P_i \cdot Prob(f > F|Impact) + (1 - P_i) \cdot Prob(f > F|pulsating) \quad (3.43)$$

where:

- P_i is the fraction of waves producing impulsive loadings;
- $Prob(f > F|Impact)$ indicates the exceedance probability conditional to impact occurrence;

- $Prob(f > F|pulsating)$ indicates the exceedance probability conditional to pulsating (quasi-static) events.

The Calabrese and Buccino’s method discussed in the preceding section provides reasonable estimates of P_i , although some overprediction may occur in case of oblique waves. As shown in Figure 3.94, the predictive equations predict reasonably the proportion of impacts up to a wave angle of 15°. Otherwise, a tendency to overestimate the frequency appears for 30°.

Figure 3.94 Calabrese and Buccino’s method for oblique wave attacks. Dotted lines represent 90% probability bands.

As far as wave forces are concerned, it should be noticed that in directional seas the non-contemporaneity of the peak-pressures occurrence along the caisson, due to the obliquity, short-crestedness or impact of the incoming waves, may generate a significant reduction of the wave loads for unit of length of structure. As consequence the forces probability distribution function on a caisson of length, L_c , should be re-written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Prob(f_{Lc} > F) = P_i \cdot \int_F^\infty \rho(f_i) \cdot Prob\left(C_{Fi} > \frac{F}{f_i}\right) df_i + (1 - P_i) \\
 \cdot \int_F^\infty \rho(f_p) \cdot Prob\left(C_{Fp} > \frac{F}{f_p}\right) df_p
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.44}$$

in which:

- ρ indicates probability density
- f_{lc} is the wave load per unit of caisson length acting on a structure extending L_c ;
- f_i and f_p are, respectively, the impact and pulsating forces acting on an infinitely short caisson;
- C_{Fi} and C_{Fp} are stochastic variables describing the spatial distribution of the wave induced hydrodynamic forces.

For quasi-static (pulsating) forces, van der Meer et al. (1994) proposed a two parameter Weibull distribution based on the Goda's formula, as described previously in this chapter. As van der Meer et al analysed data from loading cells, their results incorporate in effect the coefficient C_{Fp} .

However, a deterministic approach to calculate C_{Fp} has been originally proposed by Battjes (1982), later simplified by Burcharth and Liu (1997). In its simplified form, the reduction factor for wave obliquity of long crested waves can be calculated as:

$$C_{Fp-long\ crest} = \left| \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi \cdot L_c}{L_p} \cdot \sin\beta\right)}{\frac{\pi \cdot L_c}{L_p} \cdot \sin\beta} \right| \quad (3.45)$$

where:

- L_p is the peak wavelength at the toe of the structure;
- β is the wave angle.

On the other hand, the reduction factor due to short crestedness equals:

$$C_{Fp-short\ crest} = \left[\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \left| \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi \cdot L_c}{L_p} \cdot \sin\beta\right)}{\frac{\pi \cdot L_c}{L_p} \cdot \sin\beta} \right|^2 \cdot D(f_p, \beta) d\beta \right]^{1/2} \quad (3.46)$$

in which f_p is the peak frequency of the spectrum and $D(f_p, \beta)$ is the directional spreading distribution at f_p .

Eqs. (3.45) and (3.46) are valid in principle only for simple vertical breakwaters.

Based on the 3D experiments at the CRF wave basin described previously, Allsop and Calabrese (1998) and Calabrese et al. (2000) attempted to verify the reliability of the Battjes method for vertically composite breakwaters also. Moreover, the authors proposed:

- a method to calculate the probability density distribution of elementary impact forces f_i ;
- an empirical approach to calculate C_{Fi} .

In the CRF 3D experiments, a measurement caisson built of a marine plywood box was fitted with eighteen pressure transducers in three vertical rows (Figure 3.95). An interpolation method was used to derive (fictional) pressure and forces on an imaginary column "a" between columns 1 and 2.

Figure 3.95 Test caisson and pressure transducers.

To investigate the variability of the extreme horizontal forces along the caisson, the maximum wave forces on each column ("1", "a", "2", "3") were found for each event. In any test of 500 waves there would therefore be expected to be approximately 500 maximum force value for each column. These individual column forces were considered as representative of wave loads f acting on an infinitesimal segment of the wall. To simulate the effect of increasing caisson length, average wave forces were calculated for each event for each combination of columns ("2+3"; "1+a+2"; "a+2+3"; "1+a+2+3") giving a series of wave loads, f_{L_c} , for each caisson length, L_c .

The maximum wave forces for each column and each event were ranked in order of magnitude. The forces above the 1/250 non-exceedance level were averaged for each column and each combination of columns to give values of $f_{L_c-1/250}$. Where more than one combination was used to represent a given caisson length the average of the value of was used. To approximate the extreme wave force on an infinitely short length of caisson, the average of the different values of $F_{h1/250}$ over the three columns was calculated. The extreme force over each caisson length L_c was divided by the extreme force over an infinitely short length to demonstrate the variation of the force with increasing caisson length:

$$(C_F)_{1/250} = \frac{f_{L_c-1/250}}{f_{1/250}} \tag{3.47}$$

For experiments with no impact events, the Battjes-Burcharth method was found to predict the experimental data rather well for vertically composite structures also. The ratio between measured and predicted reduction factor ranged 0.9-1.0. Indeed, the ratio:

$$c_p = \frac{(C_{Fp})_{1/250}}{C_{Fp-B}} \tag{3.48}$$

where C_{Fp-B} denotes the predictions of the Battjes-Burcharth method, can be treated as a log-normal random variable with mean (of ln) equal to 0.045 and standard deviation (of ln) equal to 0.03.

To infer the probability density function of impact forces on an infinitely short caisson strip, $\rho(f_i)$, Calabrese et al. (2000) collected all the events (from the three columns) with pressure rise-time at the swl less than 0.01 the mean period in the sea state ($t_r/T_m < 0.01$). The force data were found to be log-normal distributed, as previously argued by several authors (e.g., Vicinanza, 1997).

Denoted by f^* the non-dimensional load variable:

$$f^* = \frac{f_i}{\rho_w g \cdot H_{bc}^2} \quad (3.49)$$

where:

- ρ_w = is the water mass;
- g = is the acceleration of gravity;
- H_{bc} = limiting wave height at breaking.

It has been assumed the null-hypothesis that f^* was log-normal distributed:

$$f^* \sim LN(\mu, \sigma) \quad (3.50)$$

Figure 3.96, which shows 4937 data of $\ln(f^*)$ plotted on a standard normal probability paper, seems to indicate that the null-hypothesis is reasonably based.

Figure 3.96 Experimental points on the standard normal probability paper.

To check the non-parametrical hypothesis, the chi-square test was considered. It resulted verified at a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ for all the structures under all the wave conditions.

Mean and standard deviation of $\ln(f^*)$ are reported in Table 3.LVIII for all the investigated cases.

Table 3.LVIII. Average and standard deviation of $\ln(f^*)$.

Wave attack	$B_{eq}/d = 0$		$B_{eq}/d = 1$		$B_{eq}/d = 2$		$B_{eq}/d = 3$		$B_{eq}/d = 6$	
	μ	σ								
Long crested $\beta = 0^\circ$	-0.66	1.22	0.59	1.09	0.85	1	1.44	1.09	1.88	0.95
Long crested $\beta = 15^\circ$	-1.04	0.88	-0.15	0.85	0.21	0.91	0.68	0.80	1.70	0.79
Long crested $\beta = 30^\circ$	-1.05	0.55	-0.15	0.71	0.16	0.71	--	--	--	--
Short crested $n=6$	-1.25	0.59	0.05	1.08	0.14	0.87	--	--	--	--
Short crested $n=2$	-1.29	0.69	-0.05	0.97	0.37	1.02	--	--	--	--

The table clearly shows that impact loads are quite low for a simple vertical wall ($B_{eq}/d = 0$) and increase progressively for long and/or high mounds (Figure 3.97). Similarly, wave obliquity and short-crestedness tend to mitigate loadings (Figures 3.99 and 3.100).

Figure 3.97 Berm effect on impact load distribution (long crested waves).

Figure 3.98 Effect of wave angle on impact load distribution (long crested waves-simple vertical wall).

Figure 3.99 Effect of short-crestedness on impact load distribution (simple vertical wall).

As far as the reduction factor C_{Fi} is concerned, Allsop and Calabrese (1998) proposed a simple method based on a linear regression model, which is valid for simple vertical wall:

$$C_{Fi-AC} = 1 - a_{\theta} \cdot \frac{L_c}{L_{0p}} \quad (3.50)$$

In Eq. (3.50), the coefficient a_{θ} is reported in Table 3.LIX, in the function of wave obliquity and short-crestedness.

Table 3.LIX. The regressive model by Allsop and Calabrese.

Wave attack	α_θ	Cv [%]	Correlation
Long crested $\beta = 0^\circ$	1.35	6.6	0.82
Long crested $\beta = 0^\circ$	1.69	9.2	0.77
Long crested $\beta = 15^\circ$	1.96	10.4	0.79
Short crested $n=6$	1.55	10.6	0.76
Short crested $n=2$	1.58	9.3	0.77
Short crested $n=2,6$	1.56	6.8	0.77

Calabrese et al. (2000) concluded that the Allsop and Calabrese model could be applied to vertically composite breakwater also, despite some scatter. In particular, the ratio:

$$c_i = \frac{(C_{Fi})_{1/250}}{C_{Fi-AC}} \tag{3.51}$$

can be considered a log-normal distributed random variable, with mean (of logarithm) equal to 0.067 and standard deviation (of logarithm) equal to 0.123. Table 3.LX summarizes results obtained with respect to the length reduction factors.

Table 3.LX. Summary of length reduction factors.

Loading Case	Reference model	variable	Distribution	mean (of ln)	St.deviation (of ln)
Quasi-static	Battjes-Burcharth Eqs. (3.48)	$c_p = \frac{(C_{Fp})_{1/250}}{C_{Fp-B}}$	Log-Normal	0.045	0.031
Impact	Allsop and Calabrese Eqs.(3.51)	$c_i = \frac{(C_{Fi})_{1/250}}{C_{Fi-AC}}$	Log-Normal	0.067	0.123

3.4 Failure mechanisms of seawalls

3.4.1 Experimental dataset on vertical walls acquired by UniNA

This section describes the experimental dataset on vertical seawalls in shallow water collected by UniNA. Such a dataset includes data presented by Buccino et al. (2023) along with physical experiments discussed in Tuozzo (2024a), both of which focus on the failure mechanism of wave overtopping.

Physical model setup

The present paragraph describes the model setup of two different experimental campaigns carried out in the Hydraulic Laboratory of the University of Napoli Federico II. The former investigated the wave overtopping at the Malecòn Traditionàl (MT), the vertical wall that protects La Havana city (Cuba) against flooding. Such an experimental campaign will be referred to as MT hereafter. The second one examined the wave overtopping at vertical seawalls with very and extremely shallow foreshores; it will be referred to as UniNA experimental campaign.

The MT tests have been conducted in a concrete-walled channel, which is 18.4m long and 1.55m wide. The multi-slope foreshore of La Havana has been reproduced at a scale of 1:30, using the Froude's similitude law. In particular, the foreshore was modeled from the location of the Malecón seawall, which is 0.057m below the MWL, out to a depth of 0.624m; further towards the wavemaker, a flat bottom allows the generated waves to develop appropriately. Further details of the MT experimental setup are illustrated in Figure 3.100. The experiments involved three different wall's heights, namely 0.132m above the MWL (which is the original height of the Malecón), 0.149m and 0.165m. During the experiments, four pressure transducers were arranged along the wall. However, this Section only deals with wave overtopping measurements.

Figure 3.100 Sketch of the MT physical model setup.

To measure the incoming wave conditions at the toe of the wall, the irregular sea states were run – for 200 waves – without the structure in the channel; indeed, the foreshore was extended above the MWL to perform the wave propagation tests. Simultaneously, wave conditions on the flat bottom were estimated by applying the separation method of Zelt and Skjelbreia (1992) to an array of four probes, as depicted in Figure 3.100. Subsequently, the mean overtopping discharges were estimated on a sequence of 1000 waves with the structure in place. The overtopping water was collected in a tank and then recirculated using two submersible pumps. The pumped water passed through an electromagnetic flow meter, which continuously computed the fluid volume. The water level in the overtopping tank at the beginning and at the end of each test was controlled by an additional wave probe.

With regard to UniNA experimental campaign, tests have been carried out in the small-scale flume of the Hydraulic Laboratory, which is a 0.75 m high, 26 m long, and 0.5m width. The model setup consists of a steep foreshore inclined 1/10 to the horizontal; in front of the smooth slope, a flat bottom that is long 13m guarantees the proper development of the generated waves. The vertical wall has been located at the end of the 4.0 m foreshore slope; its crest height has been gradually raised in order to model seven different seawall heights, ranging from 0.06m to 0.30m (these values refer to the toe of the wall). A sketch is illustrated in Figure 3.101.

Figure 3.101 Sketch of the UniNA physical model setup.

Analogously to the MT experimental campaign, the incident wave conditions at the toe of the wall were measured without the structure in the flume using a pressure transducer. Hence, the foreshore has been extended up to +0.5 m from the channel's bottom to execute the wave propagation tests. Moreover, wave characteristics on the flat bottom were acquired through the four wave probes shown in Figure 3.101. The Zelt and Skjelbrija method (1992) has been employed to separate incident and reflected waves. Thus, for measuring water level displacements we have used four twin-wire resistive probes and a pressure transducer. Each wave probe comprises two parallel stainless steel rods with a plastic head and foot, powered by a dual-power supply operating at a differential voltage of about $\pm 10V$. These measure the current that flows between two stainless steel wires that are immersed in water; then, the current is converted to an output voltage, directly proportional to the immersed depth, that is transferred to a control cabinet. The pressure transducers are piezoresistive sensors characterized by a voltage range of $0 \div 10V$.

The mean overtopping discharge has been measured using an additional probe located in a tank placed behind the seawall. It is worth noticing that such a tank has been divided into two parts in order to minimize the unwanted noise due to the fluctuations following each overtopping event, which could alter the flow rate measurement. The tank was divided by a partition wall that allows the water to pass underneath and to reach a zone unaffected by fluctuations. Irregular sea states composed of 250 waves were run for propagation tests, while 1000-waves tests were performed to obtain overtopping measurements.

It is worth noting that during wave overtopping tests that involve significant discharges, the generated time series has been divided into more sections, and, for each of them, the overtopping volumes have been measured. At the end of each test, a pump has re-introduced the lost volume of water in the flume. Otherwise, the whole time series would have reduced the water level at the toe of the wall compromising the measurements.

Test conditions

The MT experiments were performed with two different water levels, namely +0.06m and +0.076m above the MWL, which correspond respectively to the 50 years return period sea level rise and the surge observed during the Hurricane Wilma, which occurred in 2005. Thus, six different crest freeboards, R_c , have been tested due to the combination of three different wall's heights and two water levels. For both water levels, eight irregular sea states driven by mean JONSWAP spectra were generated; specifically, four values of H_s^t (0.083, 0.133, 0.18, and 0.217m) and two peak periods (1.83 and 2.19s) were used. It is worth mentioning that MT tests

encompass impulsive conditions at the wall, as inferred from the pressure measurements obtained via four transducers.

Overall, the 48 MT data are characterized by a relative crest freeboard, R_c/H_{m0} , that varies between 0.47 and 1.88; moreover, the ratio $h/H_{m0,0}$ is included between 0.52 and 1.52, which indicates shallow and very shallow foreshore conditions (according to the classification of Hofland et al., 2017).

The 50 UniNA laboratory tests have examined nine irregular sea states (characterized by a mean JONSWAP spectrum) along with four different water levels. The water depth at the toe of the wall has been varied from 0.01m to 0.06m. With regard to the target wave conditions, three values of H_s^t (0.08, 0.1 and 0.13m) combined with three peak period values (1.3, 1.5 and 1.8s) have been tested. Hence, UniNA experimental campaign allows us to analyze seawalls with very and extremely shallow foreshore ($h/H_{m0,0} = 0.2 \div 0.63$). Furthermore, the relative crest freeboard is included between 0.46 and 4.48. Analogous to MT data, impulsive wave loadings have been tested.

Experimental results

To analyze wave overtopping results, we resort to a new parametrization introduced by Tuozzo et al. (2024). Such a parametrization requires a different hydraulic variable, $\zeta_{1/4}$, which represents the average of the highest one-fourth water levels in a Gaussian wave process. Indeed, according to Buccino et al. (2023) and Tuozzo et al. (2024b) findings, the wave energy spectrum's shape does not affect the wave overtopping process. Therefore, the influence of the harmonic spectral period $T_{m-1,0}$ is actually negligible. Instead of the spectral distribution, the mean overtopping discharge is strongly related to the high percentiles of the distribution of the wave elevations at toe of the wall. Furthermore, it is worth noting that, for a Gaussian wave process, the variable $\zeta_{1/4}$ can be easily determined through wave set-up ($\bar{\eta}$) and the spectral significant wave height at the toe of the structure:

$$\zeta_{1/4} = \bar{\eta} + 4 \cdot \sqrt{m_0} \quad (3.52)$$

Hence, the new parametrization reads:

$$\frac{q}{g \cdot h \cdot T_p \cdot \tan(m)^P} = f\left(\frac{R_c}{\zeta_{1/4}} \cdot \gamma_{br}\right) \quad (3.53)$$

where the left-hand side term is the new dimensionless mean flow rate, q_1^* . As shown above, the latter includes the influence of the foreshore slope, $\tan(m)$; the apex P is a function of the ratio $h/H_{m0,0}$, as it accounts for the decreasing influence of the foreshore towards deeper waters. Finally, the term γ_{br} depends on both $h/H_{m0,0}$ and h/L_0 and it somehow accounts for the loading conditions' influence on wave overtopping process. Further details can be found in Tuozzo et al. (2024a,b). It is worth highlighting that this new parametrization can be adopted regardless of the foreshore conditions.

The experimental dataset described in this Section, along with reliable EurOtop data on vertical seawalls in shallow water (EurOtop, 2018), are plotted in Figure 3.102. The panel a) refers to Eq.

(3.53), while panel b) shows data plotted on the EurOtop plane (see Section 3.2.2). Results clearly highlights the larger explanatory power of new dimensionless variables; on the other hand, the EurOtop plane leads to a significant scatter of wave overtopping data (e.g., for a given relative crest freeboard, q^* can vary of two orders of magnitude). Furthermore, unlike the EurOtop empirical model, the new parametrization allows us to obtain a unique trend regardless of the impact conditions. As pointed out in Figure 3.103, impulsive and pulsating wave data do not exhibit different behaviors.

Finally, Figure 3.104 depicts both the present experimental datasets and the EurOtop data along with the empirical model proposed by Tuozzo et al (2024b), which is reported in the following.

$$\frac{q}{g \cdot h \cdot T_p \cdot \tan(m)^P} = \min \left\{ 0.0107 \cdot \frac{R_c}{\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \gamma_{br}^{-1.49} ; 0.068 \cdot \frac{R_c}{\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \gamma_{br}^{-3.04} \right\} \quad (3.54)$$

The comparison with data characterized by a wide range of shallow foreshore conditions and different loadings as well confirms the reliability of this new predictive model for mean overtopping discharge at vertical walls.

Figure 3.102 Experimental data of mean flow rate at vertical walls in shallow water. Panel a) plots data using the new parametrization of Eq. (3.25), while panel b) shows the experimental data on the EurOtop plane.

Figure 3.103 Impulsive and pulsating EurOTop data plotted on the new parametrization plane.

Figure 3.104 Comparison between experimental data and the empirical formula of Tuozzo et al. (2024b).

3.4.2 Experimental dataset on vertical walls protected by rubble mound breakwaters acquired by UniNA

This Section describes two different physical experimental campaigns concerning two main types of adaptive sea defence solutions. In particular, we will explore their capability in diminishing wave overtopping at vertical seawalls.

For the sake of clarity, we will describe and discuss these two experimental campaigns separately. First, we examine the overtopping reduction achieved by either attached or detached breakwaters. Next, we assess the protection level provided by potential provisional structures.

Physical experimental campaign of seawalls protected by rubble mound structures

The laboratory tests described in this sub-section are part of the experimental campaign carried out at the University of Naples Federico II on the Malecòn seawall (see previous Section). Indeed, it was a wide experimental campaign that investigated several defence solutions (Lopez et al., 2016); among them, the seawall protected by rock rubble mounds (*S-RMB*) or low-crested detached breakwaters (*S-LCB*).

In particular, the 36 laboratory data on *S-RMB* include three different layouts that vary both in crest width, G_c , and crest freeboard, A_c , while the offshore slope was kept constant (i.e., 2:3). The structures had no core and were composed of a median rock size equal to 1.0m in prototype scale. With regard to the 64 data on *S-LCB*, four different structures have been modelled by varying both crest's width and freeboard. Offshore and leeward slopes are equal to 2:3. Moreover, the water depth at the seaward toe was kept constant (i.e., 0.168m); thus, the larger G_c , the closer the structures are to the seawall. The low-crested breakwaters were constituted by a core which is protected by an armor of rocks with a median diameter of 1.46m in prototype. Table 3.LXI and Figure 3.105 summarize the geometrical features of *RMBs* and *LCBs* examined.

During the experiments, the displacement of rocks was avoided by securing each structure with a steel grid. Moreover, *LCB* structures were built raised above the floor to avoid the piling-up phenomenon.

It is worth mentioning that values of A_c reported in Table 3.LXI refer to the MWL. However, as the experiments were conducted with two different water levels, we can analyze the behavior of emerged, submerged, and zero-freeboard breakwaters.

Table 3.LXI Geometrical features of rubble mound structures investigated.

	G_c [m]	A_c [m]	X [m]
<i>RMB</i> – 1	0.17	0.11	0
<i>RMB</i> – 2	0.67	0.08	0
<i>RMB</i> – 3	1.00	0.06	0
<i>LCB</i> – 1	1.00	-0.01	0.55
<i>LCB</i> – 2	1.00	0.02	0.55
<i>LCB</i> – 3	0.73	0.08	0.57
<i>LCB</i> – 4	0.40	0.11	0.78

Figure 3.105 Sketch of the adaptive sea defence solutions investigated. Panel a) shows a seawall protected by an attached rubble mound breakwater (*S-RMB*); panel b) illustrates a vertical wall protected by a detached low-crested breakwater (*S-LCB*).

MT laboratory results

For evaluating the overtopping reduction rate of these protective structures, we resort to the overtopping reduction ratio, RR_q , which is:

$$RR_q = \frac{q_{PROTECTEDWALL}}{q_{UNPROTECTEDWALL}} \quad (3.55)$$

where $q_{PROTECTEDWALL}$ is the mean overtopping discharge measured when the seawall is protected by rubble mounds (*S-RMB* and *S-LCB*), while $q_{UNPROTECTEDWALL}$ refers to the measurements obtained with the sole vertical wall.

The ability of these protective structures in reducing the mean flow rate is somehow due to their energy dissipation power, which can be represented via their transmission coefficient k_t . Furthermore, the analysis of these laboratory experiments also indicates that the structure's shallowness condition (i.e., $h/H_{m,0}$) plays a role in the flow rate reduction. It is worth mentioning that the transmission coefficient has been determined via Buccino and Calabrese (2007) formula. Therefore, we have combined these two terms to obtain a predictor variable that describes the overtopping reduction capacity of these rubble mound structures (Figure 3.106), regardless of the position (i.e., attached or detached with respect to the wall).

As suggested by Tuozzo et al. (2024c), these two trends can be described by two empirical formulae:

$$RR_q = \frac{1}{\left[1 + 45 \cdot \exp\left(-13 \cdot k_t \cdot \frac{H_{m0,0}}{h}\right)\right]} \quad (3.56)$$

$$RR_q = \frac{1}{\left[1 + 120 \cdot \exp\left(-8.2 \cdot k_t \cdot \frac{H_{m0,0}}{h}\right)\right]} \quad (3.57)$$

The former refers to *S-RMB*, while the second has been derived for *S-LCB* configurations. It is worth mentioning that, to the best of the author knowledge, the literature does not provide empirical formulae for determining the mean overtopping discharge for these configurations.

Figure 3.106 Overtopping reduction rate as a function of $kt \cdot \frac{H_{m0,0}}{h}$. The figure depicts both the experimental results and the empirical formulae of Tuozzo et al. (2024c).

However, the comparison performed in this sub-section reveals a most notable result. Indeed, we can observe that detached breakwaters have a more significant effect in reducing wave overtopping at seawalls compared to attached structures.

Physical experimental campaign of seawalls protected by rubble mound breakwaters combined with ReefBall modules

The present sub-section describes a physical experimental campaign carried out in the Hydraulic Laboratory of the University of Napoli Federico II within the framework of the Project “PROMETEO”.

Laboratory tests aim to examine the overtopping reduction power of a rubble mound breakwater combined with ReefBall modules compared to a simple vertical wall. This second type of adaptive solution may also serve as temporary sea defense that can be used during winter and autumn. Indeed, ReefBalls can be placed and removed seasonally.

Model setup

Laboratory tests have been conducted in the small-scale flume of the Hydraulic Laboratory (26m long, 0.5m wide and 0.75m high). The model setup consists of a defense structure fronted by a flat bottom. In particular, three different solutions have been tested (Figure 3.107): i) simple vertical wall; ii) vertical wall protected by rubble mound breakwaters; iii) vertical wall protected by a rubble mound breakwater combined with ReefBall modules arranged in twelve different layouts (Figure 3.108).

A Froude scale law with a length scale ratio of 1:15 has been adopted. The water level and the wall’s crest freeboard have been kept constant ($h=0.39\text{m}$, $R_c=0.065\text{m}$), while the geometrical rubble mound’s characteristics vary according to Table 3.LXII. They are composed of a median rock size of 0.06m, without any core. The offshore slope is 1:2. The structure *RMB1* is then combined with ReefBall modules, which have been arranged in single and multiple (aligned and cross-aligned) rows. The ReefBall module has a base diameter of 0.122m and a height of 0.1m. Hence, for the third configuration, the presence of these modules somehow increases the global crest freeboard of the defense solution (Figure 3.107c).

Figure 3.107 Sketch of the physical model setup and the three different configurations as well. Panel a) shows the small-scale flume and the equipment used to perform the experiments, along with the first sea defense investigated; panel b) and panel c) illustrate the two types of adaptive solutions examined.

Table 3.LXII Geometrical features of rubble mound breakwaters.

	G_c [m]	A_c [m]
RMB1	0.67	0.0
RMB2	0.33	0.0
RMB3	0.33	+0.05
RMB4	0.33	-0.05

Figure 3.108 Twelve different layouts of ReefBall modules arrangement placed on the crown of the rubble mound breakwaters RMB1.

We have tested four monochromatic wave conditions, which are reported in Table 3.LXIII. The experiments lasted approximately 20 waves in order to avoid any influence of wave reflection.

An overtopping tank placed behind the wall collects the overtopped water; the mean overtopping discharge has then been computed based on the water level variation measured by a wave probe in the tank. Measurement instruments used are twin-wire resistive probes characterized by a voltage range $\pm 10V$.

Table 3.LXIII Wave conditions tested.

	H [m]	T [s]
Test1	0.16	1.55
Test2	0.1	1.8
Test3	0.09	0.8
Test4	0.083	1

Physical model results

The 44 laboratory experiments aim at comparing the overtopping reduction power of different adaptive solutions. Thus, we have only evaluated the measured RR_q .

In Figure 3.109 we have reported the results obtained for each test. For higher wave heights, we have generally observed RR_q values larger than 0.5. On the other hand, the wider rubble mound structure and the emerged one (i.e., *RMB1* and *RMB3*, respectively) actually nullify wave overtopping in *Test3* and *Test4*. Moreover, *RMB3* shows an RR_q below 12% for these two wave conditions. Among the four different rubble mounds, the submerged structure exhibits the lowest efficiency in reducing the mean flow rate; actually, it even led to a larger discharge compared to the sole vertical wall for *Test2*.

Overall, emerged and zero-freeboard rubble mound breakwaters generally reduce mean overtopping discharges, regardless of the structure's width. Indeed, the submerged structure shows the lowest performance in terms of overtopping mitigation. These preliminary results suggest that the structure's crest freeboard has a greater impact on overtopping reduction than crest width.

Figure 3.109 Overtopping reduction rates measured with the four protective rubble mound breakwaters.

Based on previous results, we have examined the second adaptive solution (Figure 3.107c) with *Test1* and *Test2*. As can be appreciated from Figures 3.111 and 3.112, the presence of ReefBall modules on the rubble mound’s crown significantly reduces the mean overtopping discharge at the vertical wall. Mitigation increases as wave height decreases (i.e., *Test2*). Finally, despite this second type of adaptive solution providing higher overtopping mitigation capacity regardless of the ReefBall modules’ arrangement, we observe that *Layout – 6* and *Layout – 7* always yield lowest RR_q values. Thus, ReefBall modules arranged in multiple aligned rows represent the most efficient layout.

Figure 3.110 Overtopping reduction rates measured with the RMB1 combined with ReefBall modules during *Test1*. The bars refer to the twelve different modules’ arrangements.

Figure 3.111 Overtopping reduction rates measured with the RMB1 combined with ReefBall modules during *Test2*. The bars refer to the twelve different modules’ arrangements.

3.4.3 Numerical dataset on vertical walls protected by beach nourishment acquired by UniNA

The present Section investigates the wave overtopping reduction at a vertical wall protected by beach nourishment. To this end, we performed a numerical experimental campaign within the framework of the Project “PROMETEO”.

The numerical analysis has evaluated the overtopping mitigation role of nourishment by accounting for the beach profile evolution due to storm events. Therefore, we have collected the dataset through two different phases:

- a) the profile response during a storm has been obtained via the numerical model SBEACH (CEDAS);
- b) the several profiles obtained during the storm event have been successively modelled in SWASH (Zijlema et al., 2011) to obtain the mean overtopping discharge at the vertical wall. In order to obtain the RR_q of beach profiles, we have previously obtained the mean flow rate with a simple vertical seawall.

Basics of numerical models

In the following, we briefly report the main characteristics of numerical models implemented in this work.

SBEACH

The software SBEACH (CEDAS) models the short-term evolution of a transversal beach profile due to a storm. It integrates the following sediment balance:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \quad (3.59)$$

where h is the instantaneous local water depth, t is the time, q is the cross-shore solid discharge, and x indicates the cross-shore direction. To solve the governing equation above, SBEACH relies on four modules:

- the wave driver, which models the refraction phenomenon via Snell’s law and accounts for wave breaking using the model of Dally, Dean and Dalrymple (1985);
- the hydrodynamic module that solves the cross-shore momentum balance;
- the morphodynamic module, which determines the sediment flux through empirical formulae;
- the overwash module that simulates – based on empirical methods – the wave uprush, along with the evolution of the emerged beach.

SWASH

SWASH is a non-hydrostatic phase-resolving model that integrates the Non-Linear Shallow Water equations extended with a non-hydrostatic pressure term. Along with the global balances of mass and momentum in the horizontal direction for a depth-averaged, non-hydrostatic, free-surface flow, the governing equations include a local continuity equation and a simplified local momentum balance in the vertical direction:

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial hu}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3.60)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + g \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial p_b}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{p_b}{h} \frac{\partial (\zeta - d)}{\partial x} + c_f \frac{u|u|}{h} = 0 \quad (3.61)$$

$$\frac{\partial \omega_s}{\partial t} = \frac{2p_b}{h} - \frac{\partial \omega_b}{\partial t}, \omega_b = -u \frac{\partial d}{\partial x} \quad (3.62)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\omega_s - \omega_b}{h} = 0 \quad (3.63)$$

where u is the depth-averaged velocity in x-direction, ω_s and ω_b are the velocities in z-direction at the free surface and at the bottom respectively, ζ is the free surface elevation from the still water level, d is the still water depth and h the total depth, p_b is the non-hydrostatic pressure at the bottom, g is the gravitational acceleration and c_f is the dimensionless bottom friction coefficient.

Such a non-hydrostatic model assumes a single-valued representation of the free surface in the horizontal plane, meaning that the computation of free surface flow requires no additional treatment methods. Furthermore, it is worth to emphasize that SWASH may be run either in depth-averaged mode or in multi-layered mode, i.e. the computational domain is divided vertically into a fixed number of layers. Thus, the vertical structure of the flow should be in a way part of the solution. The Hydrostatic Front Approximation (HFA) developed by Smit et al. (2013) allows an appropriate reproduction of the bulk characteristics of wave breaking when few layers are employed. The HFA indeed ensures that, during the breaking, vertical accelerations are no longer resolved and the non-hydrostatic pressure is set to zero – the governing equation are locally reduced to the classical NLSW equations.

SBEACH numerical setup

As initial condition, we implemented a simple beach profile characterized by a berm height of 0.25m and a width of 10m. The profile then continues seaward with a steep slope (1/2) up to the water depth of 4.0m (Figure 3.112). This initial profile somewhat recalls a rigid structure.

The length of the numerical domain is 100m; it has been discretized using $dx=1.0m$. Behind the beach, a wall boundary condition is used (dotted line in Figure 3.112). Sediments are not allowed to leave the domain seaward.

The tested storm is characterized by a constant value of wave height and period, which are equal to 2m and 6s, respectively. Its duration is 48h.

Three different sediment median diameters have been tested: 0.2mm, 0.6mm and 1.0mm.

Figure 3.112 Sketch of initial beach profile and test conditions implemented in SBEACH.

SWASH numerical setup

The numerical experiments have been conducted in a 1-D mode, using the non-hydrostatic correction. Along with the vertical wall ($R_c=1m$), the SBEACH profiles have been modelled as impermeable bathymetry in the numerical flume. At the up-wave edge of the numerical flume, a weakly reflective boundary condition is imposed, which radiates the waves propagating from onshore. Rear the vertical wall, a Sommerfield condition minimized wave reflection at the end of the channel. A monochromatic wave generation has been used; wave height and period are 2.0m and 6.0s, respectively.

The HFA approach has been used to model wave breaking; the Manning coefficient has been set to $0.012m^{-1/3}/s$. The water depth has been divided into 2 layers, and a grid size of 1m has been selected. The adaptive

Numerical results

In Figures 3.114 and 3.115, we show various beach profiles at different storm durations for either finer or coarser sediment sizes. The comparison highlights two different morphological responses. The nourishment characterized by finer sand exhibits an erosive behavior; indeed, sediments move seaward, and the profile becomes more submerged and wider over time (i.e., a sort of reef-type response). It is worth specifying that similar results have been obtained with $d_{50}=0.6mm$. On the other hand, coarser sediments led to a quick reconfiguration of the beach profile, which reached an approximate equilibrium slope of 1:7 after a few hours of the storm.

SWASH results have been reported in Figure 3.115. In particular, we plot the overtopping reduction rates of the three different beach nourishments over time. Despite an initial increase in the mean flow rate, numerical results show that a seawall protected by beach nourishment may be a successful solution for overtopping mitigation, regardless of sand characteristics. However, finer sediments provide lower reduction rates. Furthermore, we can observe that the mean flow rate is quickly reduced after a few hours of storms. Then, the reduction rate appears stable (i.e., approximately 0.8 for $d_{n50}=1mm$, and 0.3 for finer grain sizes).

It is worth noting that the $RR_q=2.5$ obtained at $t=0h$ may be due to the numerical modelling of the beach initial condition, since in SWASH we have modelled profiles as impermeable.

Figure 3.113 SBEACH results: morphological response of a beach nourishment with $d_{50}=0.2mm$.

Figure 3.114 SBEACH results: morphological response of a beach nourishment with $d_{50}=1.0 mm$.

Figure 3.115 SWASH results: overtopping reduction rates of the three different beach nourishments over the time.

3.4.4 Numerical dataset acquired by UniSALENTO

New numerical simulations were performed to analyze the morphodynamic response of seawalls protected by beach nourishments, specifically focusing on the evolution of overtopping volumes as the artificial beach reshapes during storm events. The numerical experiments investigate the mean overtopping discharge to assess the effectiveness of beach fills in mitigating water volumes reaching the structure. In the preliminary phase, simulations considered two different grain sizes—medium sand ($d_{n50} = 0.227$ mm) and fine gravel (1 mm) and two initial fill slopes (1:2 and 1:4). The initial beach profiles were characterized by a linear slope transitioning into a horizontal berm adjacent to the seawall. The duration of each test was determined based on the time required for the beach to reach morphological equilibrium, ensuring a minimum exposure to 1000 waves. The numerical analyses were conducted using two different models: XBeach was employed for the sandy nourishments, while XBeach-G was used for the fine gravel scenarios. The latter is specifically designed to simulate groundwater flow within porous media, making it more suitable for predicting the morphodynamic evolution of gravel beaches characterized by high permeability.

XBeach numerical simulations: sand fill

XBeach is a two-dimensional model for wave propagation, long waves and mean flow, sediment transport and morphological changes of the nearshore area, beaches, dunes and backbarrier during storms. The model comprises a wave and roller module, non-linear shallow water equations (NLSWE) module and morphological module based on Soulsby-van Rijn (van Rijn, 1985) Van Thiel-Van Rijn (van Rijn, 2007; van Thiel de Vries, 2009) e van Rijn (van Rijn, 1993) sediment transport equations. The wave module is based upon the Wave Action Balance Equations (WABE) and solves for short waves only on the scale of wave grouping, the long wave being solved through the NLSWE. The short-wave motion is solved using the wave action equation which is a time-dependent forcing of the HISWA equations (Holthuijsen et al., 1989). These equations solve the variation of short-waves envelope (wave height) on the scale of wave groups. It employs a dissipation model for use with wave groups (Roelvink, 1993; Daly et al.,

2012) and a roller model (Svendsen, 1984; Nairn et al., 1990; Stive and de Vriend, 1994) to represent momentum stored at the surface after breaking. These variations, through radiation stress gradients (Longuet-Higgins and Stewart, 1962, 1964) exert a force on the water column and drive longer period waves (infragravity waves) and unsteady currents, which are solved by the nonlinear shallow water equations (e.g. Phillips, 1977). Thus, wave-driven currents (longshore current, rip currents and undertow), and wind-driven currents (stationary and uniform) for local wind set-up, long (infragravity) waves, and runup and rundown of long waves (swash) are included. Using the surfbeat mode it is necessary when the focus is on swash zone processes rather than time-averaged currents and setup. This assumption is valid on dissipative beaches, where the short waves are mostly dissipated by depth-induced wave breaking. On intermediate beaches and during extreme events the swash motions are still predominantly in the infragravity band and so is the wave runup.

Xbeach numerical model was preliminary calibrated against laboratory data acquired during a previous experimental campaign performed on a 2D small scale physical movable-bed model. The physical model (Figure 3.116) was constructed in a 2D wave flume (50 meters long and 2.5 meters wide) using a 1:10 scale based on Froude similarity. The initial beach profile was designed with a submerged slope of 1:30 and an artificial nourishment slope of 1:8, utilizing fine sand with a median grain size (d_{50}) of 0.227 mm. During the laboratory tests, the beach was subjected to irregular wave conditions (JONSWAP spectrum) to simulate erosive storm events up to equilibrium conditions.

Figure 3.116 Cross-section of the physical model with overlapped the plan view of the (Saponieri et al., 2018).

Following the laboratory phase, the numerical analysis was performed using the XBeach 1D model. XBeach was selected for its sophisticated ability to simulate "surf-beat" dynamics—specifically, the interaction between short waves and long (infragravity) waves, which are the primary drivers of morphological changes during storms.

The preliminary numerical analysis was performed to evaluate the model sensitivity to computational grid as well as wave boundary spectrum discretization. The effect of the above model inputs was evaluated on selected outputs, considered relevant for the aim of the study: 4 variables related to the morphodynamic model response, namely profile evolution z (m), relative bed elevation changes dz (m), shoreline variation $\Delta s.r.l.$ (m) and eroded volumes EV (m^3) and the 2 hydrodynamic-related variables, the significant wave height H_{rms} (m) and the groundwater head (m) inside the beach. The attempt was to obtain grid-independent results,

not either affected by wave spectrum discretization at the offshore boundary, so as to separate numerical errors from model errors. The predicted post-storm bed level change after 15 min was chosen for the purpose. By using default settings of XBeach, 9 uniform and 18 non-equidistant cases were modelled (Table 3.LXIV). Non-equidistant grids (Tests 10÷27) vary according to i) different maximum grid size to water depth ratios (depthfac) equal to 0.2 and 2 and ii) minimum cross shore grid size (around the region close to the shore) (Δx_{\min}) for a constant number of grid points per wave length of 12.

Table 3.LXIV Test cases for XBeach grid sensitivity analysis in 1D mode.

Uniform cell size grid		
Test ID	Δx (m)	n_x
1_UNIF	0,015	2666
2_UNIF	0,025	1600
3_UNIF	0,03	1333
4_UNIF	0,04	1000
5_UNIF	0,05	800
6_UNIF	0,06	666
7_UNIF	0,07	571
8_UNIF	0,08	500
9_UNIF	0,1	400
Refined cell size grid		
Test ID	Δx min (m)	depthfac
10.11_REF	0,015	0,2/2
12.13_REF	0,025	0,2/2
14.15_REF	0,03	0,2/2
16.17_REF	0,04	0,2/2
18.19_REF	0,05	0,2/2
20.21_REF	0,06	0,2/2
22.23_REF	0,07	0,2/2
24.25_REF	0,08	0,2/2
26.27_REF	0,1	0,2/2

In Figure 3.117 (left panel), final computed profiles (a) and shoreline retreats, ΔSRL (b), are compared for all uniform test cases in surf-beat (SF) mode, by assuming absorbing boundary conditions on both front and back sides. On the right panel of Figure 3.117, the relative bed level changes (c) with respect to the initial profile (Δz_b) for tests 3, 4, 5 and 6 are reported, together with the eroded sand volumes, EV (d). The graphs show that the finest grid ($dx = 0.015$ m) induces model instability related to an excessive erosion of the emerged beach with a lowering of the horizontal berm. More reliable results are obtained with coarser grids. Results are fairly comparable in the active zone, even if slight differences can be highlighted close to the shoreline. Despite the shoreline retreat is quite independent from the grid spatial discretization (Figure 3.117 (b)), grid sizes ranging from 0.05 m up to 0.1 m show a steeper gradient of bed level changes with respect to the others. Figure 3.117 (c), showing bed level changes for tests 2, 3, 4 and 5, considered representative among the others, emphasizes these points. Very comparable results are obtained when grids spacing is equal to 0.03 m and 0.04 m, in the eroded area, whereas greater differences are depicted within the accretion area (order of centimeters), especially beyond the closure depth, at about 33 m far from the wave paddle. In order to reduce computational time, each grids was refined by imposing the minimum grid size equal to the constant space discretization used for uniform grids. The varying grids are characterized by

coarse cells offshore and a size refinement near the shore, based on the maximum grid size (Δx , imposed equal to 0.1 m) to water depth ratio.

Figure 3.117 Left panel: comparison of computed final profiles (a) and shoreline retreat (b) with different uniform grid sizes; Right panel: bed level changes (c) and eroded volumes (d) for 0.025 m, 0.03, 0.04 m and 0.05 m equally spaced grids.

In Figure 3.118 the final profiles modelled with the refined grids for both maximum grid size to water depth ratios, for selected grid size for tests 2, 3, 4 and 5 are shown, together with the final profile computed with the relative uniform grid. It can be observed that the use of different cell sizes along the cross-shore section slightly affects the results. In most tests, the use of coarsest grid offshore and along the active zone (cyan curves) induce the steepen of final profiles close to the shore. The same behaviour can be observed when a *depthfac* 0.2 is used for minimum grid size equal to 0.025 m and 0.04 m. For test 5 the refinement with a *depthfac* 0.2 reduce the steepen of the beach, whereas it induces bed peculiarities which are wanted to be avoid in the sensitivity phase of the model analysis. For the test 3, slight differences with respect to uniform grid can be highlighted. For the grids refinement not reported in Figure 3.118 with the minimum cell size equal to 0.015 m and greater than 0.05 m, except for the finest grid ($dx = 0.015m$), whose varying grids based on both values of *depthfac* improve the numerical results (even if steeper gradients around the shoreline always remain), the use of coarser grid outside the active zone (based on both *depthfac* ratios) has no effects for varying grids, since the minimum grid size imposed for varying grids tends to the maximum (set equal to 0.1 for all grids). The sensitivity of the model was also evaluated with reference to wave spectral angle discretization at the offshore boundary for both uniform and varying grids with a maximum grid size to water depth ratio 0.2.

Figure 3.118 Computed profiles with varying grid size (solid lines), computed profile with uniform grids (red dotted lines) and grid varying cell sizes (dotted lines) for depthfac equal to 0.2 (blue lines) and 2 (light blue lines) - Tests from 12–19.

Figure 3.119 reports bed level changes computed for uniform (upper panels) and varying grid (lower panels), respectively, with a spatial discretization equal to 0.025 m, 0.03 m, 0.04 m and 0.05 m, constant for uniform grids and equal to minimum size cell for varying grids. Such examples are chosen, since they easily represent the overall tested conditions and general behaviours. The influence of the offshore spectral boundary discretization angle is more remarkable for uniform grids than for varying ones, except for dx equal to 0.05 m. In line with previous findings, the model seems to be more sensitive to spectral discretization as the dx increases. When uniform grids are used, a smaller than default boundary spectral discretization, namely equal to 30° and 10° , give more similar results, whereas smaller differences are observed for refined grids, expected for grid with a minimum cell size dx of 0.05 m. In such a case the smaller spectral discretization induces greater relative bottom variations in the landward beach inner zone.

Figure 3.119 Computed relative bottom level changes (dz) with varying boundary spectral angle discretization for uniform (upper panels) and refined (lower panels) grids with dx equal to 0.025 m, 0.03 m (b), 0.04 m and 0.05 m.

Hydrodynamics was also considered for the sensitivity analysis. The greatest differences in the spatial variation of the total significant wave height (H_{rms}) are mainly due to the low frequency components, which are higher influenced by the grid spatial resolution rather than the high frequency partitions. For this reason, in Figure 3.120 the influence of grid refinements on the significant wave height low frequency partitions HRMS-LF are reported. Among the results obtained, only the most representative ones (derived from the sensitivity analysis on beach profile evolution) are reported (i.e., dx equal to 0.025 m, 0.03 m, 0.04 m, 0.05 m). Some numerical instabilities occurred in the intermediate waters, specifically for smallest grids (i.e. dx less than 0.03 m) and in shallow waters for grids equal to 0.015 m. More reliable results are observed, as for morphodynamics, with coarser uniform grids (i.e. $dx \geq 0.05$ m), for which the influence of both grid size and spectral discretization is negligible. Differently from what observed for morphodynamics, varying grids sensitivity is more remarkable.

Figure 3.120 Spatial variation of significant wave height low frequency partition HRMS-LF and groundwater head GWH inside the beach (lower panels) for selected uniform spacing and refined grids with offshore spectral discretization equal to 180° .

The above considerations were used for selecting the optimum computational grid to be used in the present work, by taking into account i) the sensitivity to cell size, ii) the sensitivity to boundary wave spectra angle discretization in SB operational mode and parallel runs and iii) the computational time. No modifications were made to the other parameters with respect to their default settings.

After the sensitivity analysis, the experimental results were used to calibrate the model and optimize the key parameters selected for the purpose of the work, and reported in Table 3.LXV, following the 'one-at-a-time' approach (Simmons et al., 2017). Among the several parameters which are considered in XBeach (about 250) and based on previous studies, 7 were regarded important in the present study for wave transformations, run-up and beach erosion processes. In addition to the above-mentioned 7 parameters, the influence of breaker formulation on both hydrodynamics and morphodynamics is also accounted for.

Table 3.LXV Calibration parameters and applicability ranges.

Calibration Parameter	Default	Range
f_w	0	0-1
$facua$	0.1	0-1
$break$	Roelvink2	Roelvink1, 2
$gamma$	0.55	0.40-0.90
$bedfric$	55	20-100
$wetslp$	0.30	0.10-1.00
$dryslp$	1	0.1-1.00
$Reposeangle$	30	0-50

The modeled profile was compared with the measured one, quantifying the differences using RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) and BSS (Brier Skill Score). The calculation of the energy dissipation rate during wave propagation depends proportionally on the f_w parameter. Indeed, it is observed that as f_w increases, there is a corresponding reduction in offshore sediment transport (Figure 3.121). The maximum BSS value was observed for $f_w = 0.4$; beyond this threshold, the score decreases, indicating an underestimation of the erosive process. This value does not correspond to the minimum RMSE, confirming that this parameter may not be significant if considered in isolation for comparing measured and modeled bed levels.

Figure 3.121 Comparison between measured and calculated profiles against f_w .

The *facua* parameter improves the model's response to wave non-linearity effects (asymmetry and skewness), influencing sediment transport phenomena (e.g., Vousdoukas et al., 2012). The best reproduction of the beach profile was obtained for *facua* values between 0.50 and 0.75, where the BSS exceeds 0.8 (Figure 3.122). Subsequently, with f_w fixed at 0.4, the *facua* parameter was varied within a range of 0.55 ± 0.1 , allowing for the identification of the optimal combination of the two parameters ($f_w = 0.4$ and *facua* = 0.55), for which the BSS reaches its maximum value (0.83).

Figure 3.122 Comparison between measured and calculated profiles against *facua*.

As highlighted, for instance, by Roelvink et al. (2009), the wave breaking formulation used in numerical modeling can have a decisive effect on the results, as the two proposed formulations (*roelvink1* and *roelvink2*) differ in the calculation of the breaking index. Figure 3.123 shows the measured and modeled profiles at the end of the 13-hour test, using both default values for f_w and *facua* (solid lines) and calibrated values (dashed lines). The comparison includes the energy dissipation formulation for breaking by *roelvink2* (in black) and *roelvink1* (in gray). For both breaking formulations, the model response was compared considering both default and calibrated values for f_w and *facua*. The BSS value is significantly higher in the second case for both adopted breaking formulations. Regardless of the values assigned to f_w and *facua*, the use of the *roelvink2* formulation (default) for calculating wave breaking energy dissipation leads to a greater retreat of the shoreline, as the wave-related turbulent energy dissipation D_w is lower compared to the *roelvink1* formulation (e.g., Simmons et al., 2017). In this specific case, the *roelvink2* formulation was selected as it yielded BSS values closer to unity.

Figure 3.123 Comparison between measured and calculated profiles against breaking model (R1 and R2), f_w e $facua$.

The model results were further analyzed by varying the breaking index γ used in the *roelvink2* formulation, testing values of 0.42, 0.55 (default), 0.6, and 0.7 (Figure 3.124). The minimum γ value of 0.42, selected as suggested by Simmons et al. (2017), yielded the lowest BSS. In this case study, it is reasonable to expect that as γ increases, the simulations would produce profiles more similar to those measured in the laboratory, given the general overestimation of the erosive phenomenon under default conditions ($\gamma = 0.55$). Indeed, an increase in BSS is observed as the breaking index rises, reaching its maximum value (BSS = 0.83) at the default setting. For higher values of gamma, the BSS decreases, while remaining approximately equal to 0.8.

Figure 3.124 Comparison between measured and calculated profiles against breaking parameter γ .

The model was further calibrated relative to other parameters involved in the morphodynamic process formulations. Simmons et al. (2018) emphasize the need to evaluate the model's response to variations in the bed friction coefficient (*bedfriccoef*) when using the Chézy formula, as its calibration can significantly improve results. Hartley and Simmons (2016) highlight how the morphodynamics of the beach profile can be influenced by the critical slope for sediment transport, which the model distinguishes as *wetslp* (wet) or *dryslp* (dry), depending on whether the particles are located below or above the water level. Therefore, it is possible to refine the post-storm profile slopes by searching for the optimal values of *wetslp* and *dryslp*. At least, where the angle of repose of the material—representing the natural inclination of a material relative to the horizontal—is unknown, it is possible to calibrate the *reposeangle* parameter to achieve a final profile that best approximates the actual evolution of the beach profile. Table 3.LXVI lists the values used for these parameters, with the values selected after the model calibration indicated in bold. The corresponding default values are reported in Table 3.LXVI.

Table 3.LXVI Morphodynamics parameter considered in model calibration.

Calibration Parameter	Default	Tested values
<i>bedfric</i>	55	20-45-55-65-75-100
<i>wetslp</i>	0.30	30-35-37-40
<i>dryslp</i>	1	0.10-0.25-0.30-0.50-0.75-1.00
<i>Reposeangle</i>	30	0.25-0.50-0.75-1.00

No significant variations in the profile were observed as the friction coefficient was varied. No improvement was noted in the modeling of the submerged bar, with BSS values across the entire profile remaining medium-to-high, ranging from a minimum of 0.7 to a maximum of 0.83 at the default value. It was not possible to identify a clear trend between the friction coefficient and the statistical metrics used to evaluate the model's accuracy. The angle of repose was varied within the range of 30°- 40°, as the angle of repose for non-cohesive soils typically ranges

between 30° and 38° , reaching a maximum of 40° for wet sand. The modeled profiles maintain substantially the same trend as the angle of repose varies, proving to be a non-influential parameter in this study. The BSS shows a slight decrease as ϕ increases, but the trend remains fairly regular without clear minimum or maximum peaks. The critical slope values above and below the mean sea level were varied according to the literature (e.g., Vousdoukas et al., 2012). While no significant variation in the profile was observed when varying the *wetslp* parameter while keeping *dryslp* at its default value, an improvement in the modeling of the subaerial beach evolution was achieved by modifying the critical slope of the emerged part. By reducing the *dryslp* value to 0.25 (compared to the default value of 1), a lower slope of the emerged beach section near the shoreline was obtained, more closely resembling the laboratory observations and corresponding to the maximum BSS value (0.90).

Figure 3.125 shows the comparison between the final measured profile and the one obtained from the calibrated model, for which a BSS of 0.91 was calculated. Although XBeach includes the processes necessary to model bar behavior, it does not correctly simulate its formation, as it lacks an accurate simulation of vertical mixing effects induced by turbulence (Trouw et al., 2012). The modeled profile reflects an average trend in the zone where the bar-trough system forms in the physical model. The closure depth is correctly modeled. Furthermore, Figure 3.125 illustrates the evolution of the profile over time at the measurement intervals of the physical model, along with the relative BSS values. It shows that the BSS increases as the profile approaches the equilibrium configuration. This variation of the BSS over time is primarily driven by the formation of the submerged bar, which appears after only the first 15 minutes of the test and, under wave action, migrates offshore until reaching an equilibrium configuration. At this configuration, although the model is unable to replicate the bar, the modeling of sediment volumes can be considered satisfactory.

Figure 3.125 Temporal evolution of modelled profiles, BSS and cross-shore submerged bar position with respect to the initial shoreline.

The calibrated XBeach model has been then used to evaluate the performance of the seawall in presence of a fill. The Figure 3.126 report the sketch of the numerical model, representative of a fill placed in front of the seawall. The profile is characterized by two distinct material zones: an erodible nourishment (represented in orange) and a rigid seawall (represented in grey).

Figure 3.126 Sketch of the model simulated in XBeach.

The seawall, located at the landward end of the profile, is defined within the XBeach environment as a non-erodible (hard) boundary. This is achieved by setting the sediment thickness to zero, namely using a non-erodible layer mask at its coordinates. The nourishment consists of erodible sand with a median grain size (d_{50}) of 0.227 mm. It is placed directly in front of the seawall with an initial slope of 1:4 and 1:2. No transitional slope was considered.

Figures 3.128 and 3.129 illustrate the temporal evolution of the beach nourishment under irregular wave action ($H_{m0} = 2$ m, $T_p = 6$ s, JONSWAP spectrum with $\gamma = 3.3$) over a 72-hour duration, considering initial fill slopes of 1:2 and 1:4, respectively. In both scenarios, a quasi-equilibrium state is reached after approximately 48 hours of storm exposure.

Figure 3.127 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 72 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 0.227$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:2).

Figure 3.128 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 72 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 0.227$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:4).

Figure 3.129 illustrates the temporal variation of the free surface elevation, the horizontal velocity component, and the resulting overtopping discharge at the landward edge of the seawall for both investigated slopes.

Figure 3.129 Upper panel: temporal evolution of water free surface elevation (left panel), cross-shore velocity component on the wall crest /centre panel) and overtopping flow (right panel) under 2 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 0.227$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:2). Lower panel: temporal evolution of water free surface elevation (left panel), cross-shore velocity component on the wall crest /centre panel) and overtopping flow (right panel) under 2 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 0.227$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:4).

XBeach-G numerical simulations: fine gravel fill

XBeach-G (McCall et al., 2014) is a one-dimensional cross-shore extension of the XBeach storm-impact model specifically developed for gravel environments. This version diverges from the standard formulation by incorporating three critical components that define its hydrodynamic and morphodynamic architecture. Firstly, the inclusion of a non-hydrostatic pressure correction term enables wave-by-wave modeling, allowing for the precise resolution of surface elevation and depth-averaged flow for individual waves rather than time-averaged wave groups. Complementing this capability is a specialized groundwater module designed to simulate infiltration and exfiltration processes through the highly permeable gravel bed, which significantly influences swash zone dynamics. Furthermore, the model integrates sediment transport relations specifically parameterized to account for gravel bedload transport.

Simulations were performed using a mean grain diameter of 8 mm, representative of a fine gravel beach. In the preliminary phase, two initial slopes (1:2 and 1:4) and two berm widths (10 m and 20 m from the seawall) were investigated. These scenarios were subjected to two hours of wave action, utilizing the same spectral parameters as the sandy nourishment simulations. Figures 3.130 through 3.133 report the temporal evolution of the beach profiles, along with the corresponding time series of free surface elevation, cross-shore velocity, and overtopping discharge, all measured at the landward edge of the seawall.

Figure 3.130 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 2 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 8$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:4).

Figure 3.131 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 2 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 8$ mm, berm width = 10 m, slope 1:2).

Figure 3.132 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 2 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 8$ mm, berm width = 20 m, slope 1:4).

Figure 3.133 Temporal evolution of beach fill, under 72 h wave attack ($D_{n50} = 8$ mm, berm width = 20 m, slope 1:2).

3.5 Failure mechanisms of beach nourishments

As pointed out in sub-section 2.3.4, beach nourishments are unstable defence solutions due to sediment losses. Among them, the present Section analyses long-shore sediment losses. Specifically, we focus on the time interval related to a certain percentage of volume loss, which may represent an interesting variable for engineering purposes (Ciccaglione et al., 2023). The analysis has been conducted via the numerical model GENESIS (CEDAS).

3.5.1 Numerical experiments on beach nourishment acquired by UniNA

GENESIS model

GENESIS (Generalized Model for Simulating Shoreline Changes) is a numerical model that simulates shoreline evolution due to spatial and temporal differences in longshore sediment transport (Hanson and Kraus, 1989).

The model integrates the one-line contour equation, which relates the temporal variation of shoreline profile to the alongshore gradient of sediment transport:

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{D_B + D_C} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3.64)$$

where y is the cross-shore coordinate of the shoreline, Q is the littoral drift rate, D_B and D_C are the berm height and the depth of closure, respectively.

It is worth mentioning that Eq. (3.64) is based on the main hypotheses that the beach profile moves in parallel to itself and littoral transport is included between D_B and D_C .

The littoral drift rate is related to wave parameters at breaking point and sediment's characteristics via the following equation:

$$Q = (H_s^2 \cdot c_g)_b \cdot \left[\frac{k_1}{C_1} \cdot \sin 2\alpha + \frac{k_2}{C_2 \tan(\beta)} \cdot \frac{dH_s}{dx} \right]_b \quad (3.65)$$

in which c_g is the group celerity, α is the angle between wave front and shoreline, $\tan(\beta)$ is the average beach slope, C_1 and C_2 are coefficients related to sediment properties and k_1 and k_2 are transport coefficient. The subscript "b" indicates incipient breaking condition.

GENESIS actually relates the littoral drift to two different terms: the first is the well-known CERC formula (SPM, 1984), which accounts for longshore sediment transport induced by oblique incident waves at breaking; the second one take into account the alongshore gradient in breaking wave height (e.g., diffraction currents).

Numerical setup

Numerical experiments concern a rectangular beach fill over a linear shoreline. The stretch of coast extends for 1km, with a beach fill of 1000m² (base equals to 100m and height of 10m) placed symmetrically with respect to the center of the domain. Both nourishment and native beach has a median diameter of 0.34mm (medium sand), $D_B= 1.5$ m and $D_C=9$ m. Offshore wave characteristics are reported in Table 3.LXVII; the offshore wave angle has been varied from 0° to 40° at a 5° step. The experiments have been conducted without the second term of Eq. (3.65), which means $k_2=0$. The transport coefficient k_1 has been set to 0.01.

After a grid sensitive analysis (which has been omitted for the sake of brevity), a 5m grid size and a time step of 1h have been selected.

Table 3.LXVII Offshore wave parameters tested.

$H_{s,0}$ [m]	T_p [s]	α_0 [°]
0.8	5	0 ÷ 40

Boundary conditions varied depending on the case investigated (Figure 3.134):

- for a pinned coast case, $\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} = 0$;
- for a gated coast case, $Q = 0$.

Figure 3.134 GENESIS numerical setup. The pinned coast case is reported on the left, while the gated coast case is reported on the right.

Numerical results

In this sub-section, we analyze numerical results and compare them to the analytical solution provided by Ciccaglione et al. (2023). The latter indeed determined a general solution for beaches of finite length by solving the Diffusivity Equation, which can be derived from the one-line equation (Eq. 3.41) under certain assumptions. Further details can be found in Ciccaglione et al. (2023). Overall, the analytical solution ensures to assess the reduction percentage of a beach fill, M , and the related temporal variation as a function of the shoreline diffusivity, which depends on the active beach width ($D_B + D_C$), sediment characteristics and wave parameters (wave height, wave period, and wave angle). The shoreline diffusivity can thus be determined as:

$$\varepsilon^* = \frac{K \cdot g^{0.6} \cdot H_{s,0}^{12/5} \cdot T^{1/5}}{8 \cdot (s - 1)(1 - n)2^{1.4}\pi^{0.2}\gamma_b} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{D_B + D_C}\right) \cdot \cos[2(\beta - \alpha_0)] \quad (3.66)$$

where K is a sediment transport parameter, s indicates the relative density parameter of sediment with respect to water, n is the porosity, γ_b is the breaking coefficient and β represents the shoreline normal azimuth.

Pinned coast case

In Figure 3.135, we report the ratio between analytical and numerical reduction times as a function of both offshore and breaking wave angle. In particular, the graph shows t_{25} and t_{50} , defined as quarter-life and half-life reduction time, respectively. The subscript value actually indicates the reduction percentage of the initial fill volume. Results show that numerical and analytical reduction times are consistent, with the exception of t_{25} at a very large angle. It is worth highlighting that differences between numerical and analytical solution does not depend on time for smaller wave attacks (less than 15°). Higher wave angles instead lead to larger errors (Figure 3.136). However, these discrepancies reduce over time. In Figure 3.136, the deviation between analytical and numerical results have been determined via the normalized root mean square error (i.e., ratio between RMSE and RMS of numerical data).

Overall, we can observe that analytical and numerical beach fill evolution are always quite consistent (Figure 3.137). Here, the non-dimensional reduction time has been used:

$$t_M^* = \varepsilon \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} \right)^2 t_M \tag{3.67}$$

where ε is the shoreline diffusivity, L is the coast's length, and the subscript M indicates the general percentage of volume fill reduction. Hence, Figure 3.137 shows a satisfactory agreement regardless of the offshore wave angle.

Figure 3.135 Ratio between analytical and numerical reduction times for t_{25} and t_{50} as a function of wave angle for pinned coast case.

Figure 3.136 Normalized RMSE error for the pinned coast condition plotted against the offshore wave angle, for the selected times 1, 2, 6, 8, 10, 15 and 20 years.

Figure 3.137 Analytical and numerical reduction curves for different offshore wave angles.

Gated coast case

Unlike previous results, numerical and analytical reduction times are consistent up to a 25° offshore angle for the gated coast case (Figure 3.138). Then, the difference increases as the offshore wave attack becomes more oblique. Interestingly, for the gated coast case the error is always lower than 0.1, with the exception of the 1 year (Figure 3.139). Finally, the dependence from offshore wave angle can also be seen in the beach fill reduction curves (Figure 3.140);

indeed, unlike analytical solutions, numerical results appear affected by α_0 . The larger the offshore wave angle, the larger the difference.

Figure 3.138 Ratio between analytical and numerical reduction times for t_{25} and t_{50} as a function of wave angle for gated coast case.

Figure 3.139 Normalized RMSE error for the gated coast condition plotted against the offshore wave angle, for the selected times 1, 2, 6, 8, 10, 15 and 20 years.

Figure 3.140 Comparison between analytical and numerical reduction curves for different offshore wave angles.

The analysis reported above concerns a beach compartment enclosed between non-bypassing groins. We are now considering the solution with a bypassed-groin compartment.

It is worth highlighting that GENESIS and the analytical solution differ in bypassing modelling. Indeed, unlike the numerical solution, the analytical one accounts for a linear relationship between sand bypassing and shoreline position. Therefore, some discrepancies between solutions are expected.

Figure 3.141 depicts the normalized RMSE. The error magnitude appears reasonable; it keeps below 0.15 up to 35° offshore wave attack. Moreover, the presence of sand bypass does not modify the beach fill response in term of temporal evolution for offshore wave angle lower than 25° (see Figure 3.142 and Figure 3.138).

Figure 3.141 Normalized RMSE error for the gated coast condition (including sand bypassing) plotted against the offshore wave angle, for the selected times 1, 2, 6, 8, 10, 15 and 20 years.

Figure 3.142 Ratio between analytical and numerical reduction times for t_{25} and t_{50} as a function of wave angle for gated coast case with sand bypassing.

Boundary conditions influence

The study on the influence of boundary conditions on the shoreline response is particularly useful for asymmetrical beach fills (see Figure 3.143). The degree of asymmetry can be defined via the nourishment's barycenter to beach length ratio, X_g/L .

Figure 3.143 Definition sketch for an asymmetrical rectangular beach fill.

For a pinned beach, we can observe the influence of boundary on the reduction curve (Figure 3.144). The panel on the left illustrates the results obtained with $B/L = 0.1$, while results on the right are related to $B/L = 0.3$. Moreover, a comparison with the analytical solution for an opencoast condition (Dean, 2003) has been reported.

We can see that, the closer the nourishment to the beach's bound, the lower the reduction curve, which tends to lie very far from the open coast solution.

Figure 3.144 Sand reduction curves at the different asymmetrical beach fill placements compared to the open coast case (pinned coast). Panel on the left refers to $B/L = 0.1$, while panel on the right refers to $B/L = 0.3$.

For a gated coast, we compare the response for two offshore wave attacks (i.e., 0° and 20°), being $B/L = 0.3$. For normal wave attack, Figure 3.145 (left panel) shows that the larger X_g/L the higher the reduction curve compared to the open coast. This is because the boundary conditions tend to keep the sediments in the neighbourhood of the area of placement. On the other hand, for 20° wave angle, the volume of nourishment reduces increasingly faster (Figure 3.145 right panel), as the consequence of being initially placed in the downdrift area of the cell.

Figure 3.145 Sand reduction curves at the different asymmetrical beach fill placements compared to the open coast case (gated coast). Panel on the left refers to a normal wave attack, while the panel on the right refers to 20° oblique wave attack.

Results

The comparison between numerical experiments and analytical solutions confirms the stability and strengthens of analytical results. Therefore, for practical purposes, explicit equations relating reduction times to the percentage of remaining sand $M(t)$ have been provide (Ciccaglione et al., 2023). Specifically, for pinned coast, equations read:

$$t_M^* = 1.572M(t)^{-1.506} \left(\frac{B}{L}\right)^2 \quad \text{for } M(t) < 0.25 \quad (3.68)$$

$$t_M^* = 66.823 \cdot \exp[-6.855M(t)] \left(\frac{B}{L}\right)^2 \quad \text{for } M(t) \geq 0.25 \quad (3.69)$$

while, for gated coast case:

$$t_M^* = \max\{0.0206M(t)^{-4.244}; 78.213 \cdot \exp[-7.047M(t)]\} \left(\frac{B}{L}\right)^2 \quad (3.70)$$

where B is the base of the rectangular beach fill.

Thus, the closer the nourishment to the beach’s bound, the lower the reduction curve.

4. Conclusions

The present deliverable examines in depth some of the main failure mechanisms associated with coastal and harbor defense solutions. The primary aim is to collect updated conceptual/empirical formulations useful for the probabilistic design framework, which is the core of the PROMETEO Project. To pursue this objective, we have acquired a large amount of experimental and numerical data that allowed us to analyze structures' failures and, thus, determine conceptual/empirical formulae. Physical experimental campaigns and numerical investigations have been carried out in different Hydraulics Laboratories and with various numerical models.

The analysis focused on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

As concerns rubble-mound breakwaters, we have examined wave overtopping and armor hydraulic instability as failure mechanisms. Physical experimental models and numerical investigations have been performed within the framework of this Project. Other numerical and experimental data have been acquired from previous studies. In particular, physical model tests have been conducted to improve our knowledge of the hydraulic stability of rubble-mound breakwaters. Laboratory results have enhanced the predictive capability of several existing empirical formulae, which have been re-calibrated against experimental data. The van der Meer (1988) formula for cubic armor units has been indeed modified to be more suitable for the existing structures with an additional armor layer, which behave differently from conventional rubble-mound breakwaters. Moreover, with specific reference to design formulations for shallow-water conditions, the Van Gent (2003) model has been modified to account for these effects by introducing the influence of spectral wave steepness (i.e., wave period) as a function of the spectral significant wave height. In addition, numerical datasets have been developed to investigate the internal pressure within rubble-mound breakwaters, with particular attention to the characteristic pressures at the interface between the armour and filter layers and the attenuation of the pressure field during water infiltration into the porous structure. Regarding wave overtopping, numerical analysis allowed us to provide site-specific formulas for the prediction of mean wave overtopping discharge that overcome the limits of the existing empirical models referred only to newly built structures.

Successively, we focused on wave loadings acting on vertical breakwaters. Various laboratory experiments carried out over two decades in different European laboratories (including an experimental campaign carried out in the small-scale flume of UniNA) have been collected to provide empirical formulae for determining wave actions on the vertical breakwater within a probabilistic framework. Specifically, we have reported the extension of Goda's formula for determining wave loadings on a vertical breakwater within this framework. A two parameters Weibull distributions has been proposed to describe wave forces and moments of quasi-static waves. Then, a breaking criterion to identify the upper limit of the percentage of impact waves in a sea state, ensuring the determination of the exceedance probability of wave loadings on vertical breakwaters. Furthermore, to account for the effects of oblique wave attacks on the probability of impulsiveness, a reduction factor has been introduced. Finally, analysis of the

experimental data showed that the impact loads on the structure increase for composite breakwaters; the probability of impulsive waves increases progressively for long and/or high mounds. Thus, this chapter suggests how to manage such influences when determining wave loadings on composite vertical breakwaters.

With regard seawalls, we have focused on the wave overtopping failure in shallow water conditions. Specifically, we have examined both the configuration of a simple vertical wall and some adaptive defense solutions. Physical model experiments have yielded an empirical formula for estimating the mean overtopping discharge regardless of both shallow foreshore conditions and loadings (i.e., impulsive or pulsating). Such a new formula relates the mean flow rate to a new hydraulic variable, which takes into account both wave energy and wave setup at the toe of the wall. Then, by combining experimental and numerical data, we have examined the overtopping mitigation of a seawall protected by rubble-mound breakwaters (either attached or detached), breakwaters combined with different ReefBall modules, and beach nourishments composed of different grain sizes (i.e., both sand and gravel materials). A comparative analysis allowed us to understand the most efficient adaptive solution and, for some configurations, to derive some empirical formulae.

Finally, we have numerically analyzed long-shore sediment losses as a failure mechanism of beach nourishments. In particular, we have used numerical data to investigate sediment losses of a rectangular beach fill and verify some analytical solutions in case of a finite beach length. The analysis has involved both pinned and gated coasts. Based on these results, an empirical model has been developed to estimate the time taken for a certain percentage of the initial fill volume to be lost.

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